

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

DOCTOR OF COMMUNICATION

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**TELEACTING AN AUTHORITY IN A COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICE:
COMPLIANCE CERTIFICATE AS A NON-HUMAN AGENT
IN SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT**

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9 September 2024

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Acceptance Page

This paper, prepared by **MICHAEL JUDE TADUYO CASALJAY** with the title: **TELEACTING AN AUTHORITY IN A COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICE: COMPLIANCE CERTIFICATE AS A NON-HUMAN AGENT IN SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT**, is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Doctor of Communication**.

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Biographical Sketch

Michael Jude Tadyo Casaljay is currently the Department Head of the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) of the Municipal Government of Sta. Margarita, Samar, Eastern Visayas (Region 8). Before this role, he served as a School Principal I at Clarencio Calagos Memorial School of Fisheries' Senior High School Department for three years. Prior to his promotion to school head position, he worked as a classroom teacher for 10 years, teaching English, Physics, and Chemistry. In 2014, he was promoted to the position of Head Teacher III of the Academic Department of the Junior High School of the same school.

Some of his humble accomplishments include being a winning coach in radio scriptwriting and broadcasting competitions at the National Schools Press Conferences (NSPCs) for 12 years, that is from 2004 to 2019. Also, he has been a winning coach in Television scriptwriting and broadcasting contests at the NSPCs for four straight years from 2017 to 2020. At the regional level, he has also been a champion coach in radio scriptwriting and broadcasting tilts in the Eastern Visayas Regional Schools Press Conferences for 15 years, from 2004 to 2019; and in TV scriptwriting and broadcasting for three years, from 2017 to 2019. Furthermore, he has been a champion coach in radio scriptwriting and broadcasting contests at the Samar Division Schools Press Conferences (DSPCs) for 16 years, that is from 2003 to 2019. In the year 2017, he played as the brain of the school's – Clarencio Calagos Memorial School of Fisheries – achievement as the 1st Best ICT Innovation for Teaching and Learning in the Eastern Visayas Region. He also contributed to the school's achievement of Level III accreditation in the Regional School-Based Management (SBM) accreditation as the school's SBM Coordinator.

In 2013, he was recognized as the Most Outstanding School Paper Adviser of the Philippines by the Department of Education, Philippines, during the National Schools Press Conference in Ormoc City. In 2018, he received the Avant-Garde School Paper Adviser of the Philippines award from the Associated Editors, Inc., an organization of professional mainstream media practitioners, during the Word Cup National Journalism Training and Contests in Boracay Island, Malay, Aklan. That same year, he was honored by the Manila Teachers' as the 2018 Ulirang Guro and Pambansang Ulirang Guro from Eastern Visayas, in recognition of his dedication and sacrifices as a classroom teacher for over a decade.

His passion for teaching has led him to his current role as an Associate Professorial Lecturer III at the Institute of Teacher Education and the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc., Calbayog City. In this position, he teaches mass communication, campus journalism, public speaking, and other courses. In 2024, he passed the Career Executive Service Written Examination (CESWE), administered by the Career Executive Service Board (CESB), on March 17, 2024, at the University of Cebu – Banilad. In February 2026, he passed the CES Assessment Center Examination, the most difficult stage of the CES eligibility process, also administered by the CESB on December 13, 2025 at the CESB Headquarters in Diliman, Quezon City.

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Acknowledgment

Gratitude is the language of the heart.

These words from the American writer, educator, and motivational speaker, William Arthur Ward, are what I have always believed in. From the deepest abyss of my heart, I would like to sincerely express my gratitude to the following for their valuable contributions to the completion of this magnum opus:

To **Dr. Jean A. Saludadez**, Vice-Chancellor of the University of the Philippines Open University and Program Chair of the Doctor of Communication Program of the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, my professor and dissertation adviser for all the knowledge, wisdom, patience, and understanding she imparted to me since the day I started my DComm journey in the University. I am also grateful for her weighty insights, suggestions, and recommendations for improving this dissertation. Your unparalleled knowledge and expertise in organizational communication and communication research inspired me to delve into this field. The best dissertation adviser ever! A million thanks, Dr. Jean. You will always be in my prayers;

To **Dr. Melinda F. Lumanta** and **Dr. Emely M. Amaloza**, my Dissertation Committee Members, for their valuable insights that helped me shape, polish, and enhance my dissertation. Your expertise in the field made me realize that I need to work more to fill my cup with everything that I need to strengthen my knacks in the field of organizational communication;

To **Dr. Yourgin O. Montejo**, my classmate and friend from the Professional Regulations Commission Regional Office No. 8 in Tacloban City, for the guidance, tips, and suggestions he provided the author during the crafting of this dissertation.

To **Dr. Jay Neil G. Verano**, professor at the University of Eastern Philippines

in Catarman, Northern Samar, my former 4th-year high school student-advisee and campus journalist, for pushing and inspiring me to enroll in the University of the Philippines Open University. His words of encouragement drove me to finish this journey;

To **Dr. Gerald T. Malabarbas**, research and publication coordinator, and professor of the Institute of Teacher Education and Institute of Graduate Studies and Research of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc., Calbayog City, my best friend, best buddy, and influencer, for the motivation to pursue and finish my DComm journey and to embrace the enthralling world of research. He has always been there to guide and assist me in everything. Thank you always, best friend;

To our **Municipal Mayor Felix R. Panganoron**, my boss and uncle, for all the thoroughgoing support he has been extending to my Offices – Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) and Municipal Information Office (MIO). Thank you for the love, care, trust, confidence, patience, and understanding you have always given me that inspired me to finish this journey;

To **Ma'am Hazel Camarines**, our Human Resources Management Officer, for all the patience, understanding, and consideration given to me during the completion of my dissertation;

To my family in the **MIO** of **Sta. Margarita, Samar** – **Tiyo Jun, Marlon, Nichole**, and **Windy** – thank you for the friendship and inspiration. Thank you for making my tasks and responsibilities lighter and easier. Your creativity, intelligence, diligence, focus, and concentration on your tasks are commendable. I love and am honored to work with you;

To my family in the **MENRO** of the same municipality, **Jacky, Mark, Leif, Ramil, Rene, Balanhoi Carlo Eduard**, and **Baby Bunso Edward**, for their dedication

and commitment to our mandate of promoting the ecological management and utilization of our environment and natural resources of our hometown. Your being active in the performance of your responsibilities is praiseworthy. You're the best staff I've ever had;

To my special friend from afar, **Babs Minggoy**, for being my go-to friend whenever I feel down and need enlightenment, encouragement, and motivation. May all the life goals and dreams that we share come true, and may the Universe grant all our hearts' desires;

Ate Elma, Ate Ica, Ate Indang, Ate Elvie, Kuya Chev, Avin Carl, Namnam and Kids, Alvie, Caina, Hazel, EJ, Tyron, Shammy, Saac, and my other cousins, nephews, and nieces, for the unceasing love, understanding, patience, concern, respect, and obedience shown and expressed that inspired me to never give up, instead to fight and continue improving my life for me to be productive, helpful, and purposeful;

To **Nanay Inday and Tatay Benit (+)**, my most-loved parents, for the love, care, concern, and support they extended to me all my life that inspired me to pursue and continue living, loving, and learning. You will always be the parents I wish to have in the next lives that I may have;

Above all, to the **Lord God Almighty**, my creator, Father, and night-in-a-shining armor, who never ceases to show His unfathomable love and wisdom, and incessant blessings He showered upon me despite some unavoidable moments of irresponsibility, imperfections, disobedience, and transgressions.

Jude

Dedication

“If others can, why can’t I.”

These words have been guiding me in almost all of my endeavors in life for years. It has been very effectual for me in achieving my goals and dreams in life.

Nevertheless, apart from these guiding lexes, there are individuals who have been serving as the winds beneath my wings. And to them, this simple emblem of his academic toils and sacrifices is dedicated.

In specificity, I would like to dedicate this book to my beloved family -

Purie, my mother;

Avin Carl, my nephew; Namee, my cousin; Alvie, my cousin;

Shammy and Saac, my nephew and niece, whom I consider my beloved siblings;

Ate Elma, my cousin, whom I consider my older sister;

and, to the rest of the members of my family.

This work is also dedicated to Gerald, my best friend, whose words of encouragement have motivated me to succeed in every feat.

Above all to the Lord God Almighty,

whose love, care, and concern are interminable and immeasurable.

Jude

Dedication

To the late

+Anecita Catalan Tadyo,
my dearly beloved aunt...

and

+Benito Roa Casaljay,
my most-loved father

*this work is also
dedicated.*

Jude

Table of Contents

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	vi
Dedication	ix
Table of Contents	xi
List of Tables	xiv
List of Figures	xv
ABSTRACT	xvi
CHAPTER I: RATIONALE	1
Agencies in Shaping Contemporary Societal Structures	1
Agents in Solid Waste Management	4
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	6
The Authority and Influence of Non-Human Agents on Organizational Dynamics	6
<i>Natural and Environmental Agency</i>	6
<i>Floral and Faunal Agency</i>	10
<i>Objectual and Spatial Agency</i>	16
<i>Technological Agency</i>	22
<i>Textual Agency</i>	35
<i>Other Forms of Agencies</i>	41
The Ventriloquism of Various Non-Human Agencies	46
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS	60
Research Framework	60
Research Questions	67
CHAPTER IV: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	68
Research Design	68
Study Site	70

Data Collection	73
Data Analysis and Interpretation	77
Ensuring Plausibility in the Findings	82
CHAPTER V: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	87
Figures that Appeared in the Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate	87
<i>First and Second Figures: Seal or Logo and the Letterhead</i>	89
<i>Third Figure: Certificate Number</i>	91
<i>Fourth Figure: RA 9003</i>	92
<i>Fifth Figure: Declaration of Compliance</i>	110
<i>Sixth Figure: The Date of Issuance</i>	115
<i>Seventh Figure: The Place of Issuance</i>	116
<i>Eighth Figure: The Date of Inspection</i>	118
<i>Ninth Figure: The Signatory</i>	121
<i>Tenth Figure: The QR Code</i>	122
The Performance of the MSWMCC as a Non-Human Agent Teleacting the Authority in the Accomplishment of Solid Waste Management	127
<i>Representing the Government</i>	128
<i>Regulating Business Operations in Accordance with Solid Waste Management Practices</i>	130
<i>Affirming Business Entity's Compliance</i>	132
<i>Informing the General Public of the Business Entity's Participation in Solid Waste Management</i>	134
<i>Authorizing Business Operations in Consideration with Solid Waste Management</i>	137
<i>Documenting Business Entity's Participation in Solid Waste Management</i>	139
The Non-Human Agency of MSWMCC	145
The MSWMCC as a Textual Agent	148
CHAPTER VI: RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	153
Summary	153
Conclusion	154
Implications	156
Recommendations	158
<i>Theoretical</i>	159
<i>Practical</i>	161
Epilogue	163

REFERENCES	165
APPENDIX	178
Appendix A – Municipal Ecological Solid Waste Compliance Certificate	178

List of Tables

Table 1	<i>Matrix of Ventriloquial Analysis of the Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC)</i>	79
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List of Figures

Figure 1	The Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC)	88
Figure 2	The Official Seal or Logo and the Letterhead on the MSWMCC	89
Figure 3	The Certificate Number on the MSWMCC	91
Figure 4	RA 9003 on the MSWMCC	94
Figure 5	The Ventriloquized-Animated Authority of the MSWMCC as a Non-Human Agent in the Accomplishment of Organization Goals	104
Figure 6	The Declaration of Compliance on the MSWMCC	110
Figure 7	The Date of Issuance on the MSWMCC	115
Figure 8	The Place of Issuance on the MSWMCC	116
Figure 9	The Date of Inspection on the MSWMCC	118
Figure 10	The Signatory on the MSWMCC	121
Figure 11	The QR Code on the MSWMCC	122
Figure 12	The Figures Ventriloquized and Animated in the MSWMCC	126
Figure 13	The Activities or Events Performed by MSWMCC	127

ABSTRACT

This study is anchored on the Non-Human Agency Framework advanced by Francois Cooren (2006), which attempts to explain 'how one can act from a distance' or 'teleact' or the act of making present or presentifying something or someone in communicative practices. Teleaction can happen in a manner that non-humans represent other entities. By examining a compliance certificate used by a government regulatory body in solid waste management, the study sought to answer the research questions: 1) what figures appeared in the solid waste management compliance certificate that ventriloquized its authority; 2) what does the compliance certificate perform in solid waste management? Using Cooren's (2010) Ventriloquial Analysis Approach, this study analyzed the Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC), a document issued by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO), a local government regulatory body in solid waste management in a municipality in the Province of (Name of the Province). From the analysis, it was revealed that there is a total of ten (10) figures explicitly invoked in the certificate – 1) official logo, 2) letterhead, 3) certificate number, 4) RA 9003, 5) declaration of compliance, 6) date of issuance, 7) place of issuance, 8) date of inspection, 9) signatory, and 10) QR code. These explicit figures that appeared in the compliance certificate implicitly convey significant messages relative to environmental protection and sustainability. Also found in the analysis are six (6) acts that the compliance certificate performs in accomplishing solid waste management – 1) representing the government, 2) regulating business operations in accordance with solid waste management practices, 3) affirming business entity's compliance, 4) informing the general public of the business entity's participation in solid waste

management, 5) authorizing business operations in consideration with solid waste management, and 6) documenting business entity's participation in solid waste management.

From the findings of this study, the researcher advances the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority Theory. Non-human agents, like the compliance certificate, possess ventriloquized and animated authority. Ventriloquized-Animated Authority is that kind of authority that the non-human agents derive from their being ventriloquized (given voices to speak) and animated (acted upon to act) by some higher unseen principals. The voices given to non-human agents by more powerful unseen principals grant them the strength and the power to speak about influential messages that move human agents to act. Likewise, the force of persuasion exerted on the non-human agents by a more powerful unseen principal also pushes the human actors to perform something geared toward the accomplishment of organizational goals. Thus, as a textual agent, the compliance certificate possesses this authority that compels business entities to participate in solid waste management, contributing to the accomplishment of organizational goals and the national vision. With this, this study contributes this concept that non-human agents, like the compliance certificate which is a textual agent, really exert influences on and contribute to organizational dynamics and accomplishment as they participate in various communicative practices that shape and define organizations, as emphasized by the concept of CCO (Communication as Constitutive of Organization) under the Montreal School of Organizational Communication.

Keywords: Authority, Non-Human Agency, Ventriloquism, Solid Waste Management, Regulatory Body, Issuances

CHAPTER I

RATIONALE

Agencies in Shaping Contemporary Societal Structures

The dynamic and symbiotic relationship between humans and the artifacts that fill our environment was highlighted by Cooren et al. (2006), emphasizing their active role in influencing our perception, understanding, and navigation of the world, even the world we live in is structured and organized. This organization can be explained by recognizing various agencies, both human and non-human, that play a role in shaping this structure.

In our modern world, as a matter of fact, we are surrounded by a plethora of artifacts - physical objects, technological innovations, and cultural constructions - that have a significant impact on the way humans think and create (Cooren, et al., 2006). These artifacts are not passive entities, but rather active contributors to the intricate fabric of human activities and thought. Whether they are tangible or digital, these artifacts play a dynamic role in shaping human interaction, driving innovation, and shaping our collective experiences (Cooren, et al., 2006). Hence, an organization is not solely due to human influence but the result of the combined influence of various elements, both humans and non-humans. Through their actions, decisions, and societal systems, humans play a significant role in shaping the world. Notwithstanding, non-human agencies, such as natural forces, technological systems, and environmental factors, also have a considerable influence in determining how everything is organized. To truly understand the structure of the world, for Cooren, et

al. (2006), we must recognize the diverse contribution of both human and non-human agencies as, together, they shape the fabric of our existence.

Communication, within Cooren's (2011) agency framework, is comprehended as 'not only a matter of people speaking or writing to each other, but that "other things" are continuously inviting and expressing themselves in day-to-day interactions'. In Cooren's (2011) agency framework, communication is conceptualized beyond the traditional perspective of human verbal or written exchanges. Instead, communication is seen as a dynamic process in which entities beyond human agents actively participate in everyday interactions. Cooren (2011) argues that communication goes beyond human speech or writing; it encompasses a broader spectrum in which various elements continuously invite and express themselves within the context of ongoing interactions. This standpoint puts emphasis on the concept that communication is not solely a human-centric activity, but is also influenced by the active participation and expression of non-human elements or entities. This highlights the complex and multifaceted nature of communicative processes.

What Cooren (2011) refers to as these "other things" are "agents." As he pointed out, to be an agent means to hold the ability to act or speak "on behalf of" someone else, known as the principal. The term "agents" pertains to entities possessing the ability to undertake actions or express themselves with the authority to act on behalf of the principal. Being recognized as an agent entails the capacity to represent or advocate for someone or something. According to Saludadez (2015), the notion of a "principal," in the context of narrative economy, refers to a collective entity, typically a group, organization, or society. Fundamentally, these agents operate within this structure-function pattern as representatives or spokespersons, act on behalf of a larger collective entity, and employ their potential to influence or effect changes in

support of that principal. This idea emphasizes the interconnectedness and the dynamic relationships that are present in narratives where individuals or even entities undertake the role of agents that exercise the power to convey meaningful messages and carry out actions that align with the interests or objectives of the overarching principal.

Cooren et al. (2006) explain that “agency” is the built-in capacity of any entity to spark change or bring about transformation through a series of actions. When an actor, whether human or non-human, uses that capacity, others in the chain of events (individuals or groups) can observe the results and link them back to the original actor. This process of linking actions to actors, called attribution, becomes a key rhetorical tool people use to describe the complexities of the world. Additionally, attribution involves recognizing each participant along the sequence of actions, which lets us form a detailed understanding of how different agents interact and contribute to shaping the ever-changing fabric of existence. In essence, agency provides a lens for seeing the interconnectedness of actions, illuminating the elaborate network of influences and attributions that make up the world’s unfolding narrative (Cooren et al., 2006).

Using the influential work of Michel Callon (1986), Bruno Latour (1996, 1999< 2004), and John Law (2002), we see that machines, documents, architectural elements, and other artifacts inside groups play a vital role that people often overlook. It distinguishes a general neglect of these elements in social sciences, including organizational studies. Acknowledging the active contribution of these elements can offer solutions to both theoretical and analytical challenges (Cooren, et. al, 2006).

Agents in Solid Waste Management

In the implementation of the solid waste management program, objects or non-human agents play a vital role. These non-human agents serve as significant tools in achieving the program's objectives, acting as agents of change or catalysts for transformation. More specifically, the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) of the Philippines and other relevant government agencies, utilize and issue artifacts in compliance with the mandates of Republic 9003 otherwise known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. Such artifacts as notices, executive orders, memorandum circulars, compliance certificates or similar instruments, embody the goals and directives necessary for initiating positive shifts in solid waste management practices. Here, these non-human agents function as channels through which the overarching objectives of waste management initiatives are communicated and implemented, underscoring the crucial role of regulatory bodies and the artifacts they issue in guiding the trajectory of change in the field.

The Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) plays a crucial role in the implementation of various programs to support the execution of the solid waste management program as mandated by RA 9003. One of the initiatives of the MENRO is the organization, establishment, and functionalization of Barangay Ecological Solid Waste Management Committees (BESWMCs) in all 36 barangays within the office's jurisdiction. Adhering to the directives of the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) through its Memorandum Circular 2018-112 titled "Organization or Reorganization of the Barangay Ecological Solid Waste Management Committee (BESWMC)," the barangays assume a vital role in executing comprehensive ecological solid waste management programs. In this issuance, the

responsibilities of the barangays in solid waste management include maintaining cleanliness within the barangays, supervising the operation of Materials Recovery Facilities (MRFs), collecting segregated solid waste from households, and ensuring the proper management of solid waste at the MRF. In addition to the initiatives mentioned, the MENRO also required all business entities in the municipality to adhere to the mandates of RA 9003 by complying with all the requirements for solid waste management in their respective establishments.

Being involved in the issuance of the Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC), the researcher's observation of business entities consistently responding promptly to directives from the MENRO prompts curiosity regarding the influence of these non-human artifacts on human behavior. Understanding how non-human agents influence behavior can enhance regulatory effectiveness and promote sustainable practices.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Authority and Influence of Non-Human Agents on Organizational Dynamics

Various empirical studies on non-human agents and the influence they exert on other entities have already been conducted. These studies have covered many different categories of non-human agency, including nature and environment, flora and fauna, objects and spaces, technology, texts, and other forms of agencies like theoretical, spiritual and medical condition agencies. Researchers have argued that these non-human agents, as agents or actants that have the ability to bring about action or transformation (Cooren, 2008), possess an effect or influence on other entities.

Natural and Environmental Agency

As demonstrated by the empirical studies here, natural and environmental materials such as wastes, landscapes such as rivers and oceans, and phenomena such as fires and hurricanes exhibit agency that contribute to organizational dynamics and accomplishments.

The Atlantic Ocean is found to be a non-human agent in institutional dynamics that plays a vital role in spurring a reevaluation of local planning and surfing practices in a locality in France. In Taupin's (2019) study, the role played by a nonhuman entity, the Atlantic Ocean, in institutional work was examined. The study made use of the findings of a comprehensive case study on the local economy of a seaside town in the

southwest of France that is known for its surfing, where institutional work has changed the town's relationship with the ocean brought about by a severe coastline erosion brought on by winter storms in 2013–2014. Recognizing the relationship between the local economy and the Atlantic Ocean, Taupin's (2019) work attempted to transform the institutions of surfing and local planning in the said coastal town. Including the ocean, these actions were carried out by the players of the local economy. In order to determine the function that a non-human entity plays in intentional action to affect institutions, thirty-two (32) interviews with stakeholders in the local surfing business were qualitatively analyzed for the study. Mobilizing the anthropologist Philippe Descola theoretical framework on the various relationships between humans and nonhumans, two things occur: 1) it is suggested that institutional work consider the non-human agency of natural elements; and 2) the relational influence of the material dimension in organization and management theory is reexamined.

In topographical studies, rivers as non-human agents are also central to molding and administering international borders through natural processes that annually impact the boundary as in the case of Bangladesh's border with India. This concept is supported by the study conducted by Boruah (2021) titled "Human Folly and Border Fences: Looking to Non-Human Actors at the Indo-Bangladesh Border." In his research, the Boruah (2021) highlighted how a discourse on borders and their administration that is primarily concentrated on people is produced when interstate territorial boundaries and associated features of border management and security are the main emphasis. Investigating how rivers function as non-human actors – or rather, actants - in defining and regulating international borders was the primary goal of the study, making the riverine region of Bangladesh's border with India as the study's primary emphasis. Here, the international border is constantly being redrawn by such

transnational rivers as Gangadhar and Brahmaputra due to floods, erosion, and silt buildup. Even though people remain the main agents in the management of borders, the study argued that they are not the only players by looking at how rivers affect the borders and border management strategies. Boruah's (2021) study proposes to acknowledge the inherent equality of human and non-human agents based on the principles of the Actor Network Theory (ANT). Both human and non-human agents can be included in an actor-network to provide insightful information on border management in complicated borders.

In the realm of art, wastes are also identified as non-human agents that actively contribute to the material-discursive character of artworks. In the study of Jain and Roy (2022) titled "Mapping the Agency of Trash," it was argued that waste has growing concerns and inherent artistic and creative potential. In their work, the ontological status of waste materials and materiality as active elements or actions in the creation, production, and perception of art were re-investigated. Utilizing a new-materialist paradigm, the research rejects a purely representational interpretation in favor of emphasizing the dynamic, multifaceted, material-semiotic nature of art. Looking into the works of Indian artists from the twenty-first century, the study investigated the various ways that rubbish functions both physically and intellectually. In carrying out their research objective, Jain and Roy (2022), made use of case studies to show how different human and non-human actors play a relational, co-constructive function. Eventually, the study confirmed the material-discursive nature of art by examining the repurposing of garbage under three overlapping categories: as metaphor and symbol; as relics; and as substance/physical matter (considering physical features like texture, color, etc.). With meaning and material co-constructing each other, the study provides a more comprehensive understanding of the materials and things used in art.

Additionally, a hurricane is also seen as a non-human agent that plays a crucial role in exposing socio-political implications of disasters and contributing to the civil rights movements through the introduction of new arguments and methodologies that encompass human agency alone. Arffman and Holmila (2023), in their study titled, "Race, Environment, and Crisis: Hurricane Camille and the Politics of Southern Segregation," suggest that, when Hurricane Camille made landfall on the Mississippi coast in August 1969, the disaster caused by the hurricane was a result of the interaction between human and non-human factors. As an inanimate object, Hurricane Camille exposed the political and cultural ramifications of the socio-economic conditions that prevailed in the segregationist South. The local political establishment was displeased with this as they had long sought to keep civil rights and desegregation movements outside southern politics. As a result, Hurricane Camille gave the civil rights movement and the politics of that era a new life and significance because it introduced fresh ideas and strategies that would not have been conceivable via human action alone. They made the case that historical agency should be viewed as a complex interaction of human and non-human forces rather than only from a human-centric perspective after closely examining both local and national media conversations about the Hurricane Camille situation in Mississippi in August 1969.

The recognition of fire as a non-human agent challenged the concept that cultural landscapes are exclusively shaped by human activity alone. As a matter of fact, fires are perceived by Pikangikum residents as sentient or responsive entities that possess agency for their gradual configuration of settings in shaping aboriginal cultural landscapes. This is supported by the study conducted by Miller and Davidson-Hunt (2010) called "Fire, Agency, and Scale in the Creation of Aboriginal Cultural Landscapes," stating that recent scholarly works delve into the practice of controlled

burning employed by multifarious cultural groups to shape landscapes. Given that humans have only lately developed the capacity to put out large-scale fires, these papers emphasize the significance of localized actions in forming cultural terrains. Miller and Davidson-Hunt's (2010) study investigated the roles that fire plays in shaping Anishinaabe cultural landscapes in the northwest Ontario's boreal forest. The researchers explored Anishinaabe perspectives on and interactions with fire across many geographical and temporal dimensions in collaboration with elders from Pikangikum First Nation. The people of Pikangikum see forest fires as intelligent, intentional landscape organizers. This viewpoint from the people of Pikangikum prompted doubt on the idea that cultural landscapes are entirely the product of human activity by emphasizing the plausible contribution of non-human elements to the construction of landscapes. This realization pushes one to reconsider the parameters of the investigation as well as the fundamentals of cultural landscapes.

Floral and Faunal Agency

Plants and animals, scientifically called flora and fauna, are also found to possess agency as they have the ability to influence human agents' decision-making processes and to bring about changes and transformations that contribute to organizational accomplishment.

Endangered species, alongside other forms of non-human agents, were found to have an influence on urban design and planning policies. To support this, Ruming conducted a study in 2008 on the importance of non-human actors in the planning and development processes in Wyong, Australia, utilizing the Actor Network Theory (ANT) framework. Ruming (2008) asserted that urban planning and development is a field that unconsciously recognizes the role of non-human actors in transforming the market

environment – a process that often starts with exploring the constraints of sites or the cost implications of altered development forms. In Ruming's (2008) study, a Sydney, Australia periphery development site's non-human players that are essential to planning and development were investigated. In order to establish the conceptualization that non-human actors are essential to the creation and upkeep of any networked reality, not least residential development, it made use of ANT. Ruming's (2008) study demonstrated that non-human agents act as key players and middlemen who move through networks related to planning and development. An in-depth examination of residential development and planning policy is made possible by the ANT, making it easier to identify and track down intermediaries and players who may otherwise go unnoticed or forgotten. Ruming's (2008) study discovered that non-human actors collaborate to support the growth of residential real estate and related legislative frameworks, with a specific emphasis on geography and endangered species.

In addition, tree species are also seen to act as non-human agents that especially affected decisions related to logging and planting, thereby providing inescapable premises for the actions of forest science practitioners, and ultimately contributing to both enable and constrain agencies. This was discovered by Aspøy (2024) in his study that explored the distribution of agency in forest science. To Aspøy (2024), studies of forest science tend to perceive it primarily as seeking to control and exploit natural resources. On the contrary, new developments in social theory allow for a deeper understanding of the relationship between humans and the environment. Aspøy's (2024) study investigated the potential implications of these realizations on our knowledge in forest science, inquiring as to how humans and non-humans interact in the context of forest scientific methods and together produce certain types of

agency. Aspøy's (2024) paper attempted to answer these research questions: 1) what effect do non-human beings have on the activities that lecturers and students engage in?; 2) and, what reaction do they have to non-humans? His paper's focus was on the interactions between bachelor's degree students and instructors. As Aspøy (2024) narrated, in June 2023, a fieldwork was conducted by going on trips with instructors and students where eleven (11) pupils were interviewed as well. His study noted how educators and learners deliberately separated themselves from the forest science of the past by neglecting the needs of trees and the ecosystem services that surrounded them. As a matter of fact, lecturers frequently discussed the behaviors and preferences of non-human animals. This bears significant effects on the judgments that could be made. Based on Aspøy's (2024) research, there were several interactions between humans and non-humans. What were elicited from both professors and students were responses like climate, soil, fauna, and trees. As a consequence, they unavoidably molded the practices of forest scientists and eventually helped to both enable and restrict agency.

Furthermore, even an animal like a dog was seen to act as a non-human agent that also performs some tasks in aiding visually impaired individuals to achieve mobility. This was found by the study conducted by Due (2022) titled "Guide Dogs Versus Robot Dog: Assembling Visually Impaired People with Non-Human Agents and Achieving Assisted Mobility through Distributed Co-Constructed Perception." Due's (2022) study showcased how dogs, which are non-human agents, possess essential multisensory and semiotic abilities that aid visually impaired individuals in achieving assisted mobility, underlining the distinct role and sensory capabilities of guide dogs compared to robodogs in shaping the practical perception of the material world for mobility. In particular, it was demonstrated by Due's (2022) study that guide dogs are

useful non-human agents that help visually impaired people (VIP) achieve movement. The study also looked at the possibility of a robot dog taking the role of a guide dog, exposing the multisensory and semiotic capacities of these non-human aides using video recordings and ethnomethodological dialog analysis of VIPs navigating streets with either a remotely operated robodog or a guide dog. Due's (2022) study emphasized how their forms of agency and sensory capacities differ, and how their roles in supported mobility and mobility with a handicap are differing. His research advances our understanding of assisted and disability mobility by proving that these systems operate as combined entities – "VIP + guide dog" and "VIP + robodog + operator" – rather than as individual agents. Also, Due's (2022) study demonstrates how these combinations shape and share the practical perception of the material world that is essential for mobility.

Such non-human agents as those in the flora and fauna – butterflies, elephants, birds, man-fish, and bamboo forests – are also seen to perform a vital role in shaping Taiwan's historical representation and political identities that challenge anthropocentric perspectives and highlight the broader ecological and historical context of the nation's narrative. In Chang's (2020) study, he investigated the ways that non-human actors, as well as human characters, have affected Taiwan's history via postcolonial Taiwanese literature. Traditionally, this literary style has focused on stories that use human characters to explore political identity, historical memory, or social struggle. Chang (2020), however, examined Wu Ming-yi's novels "Routes in a Dream" (2007) and "The Stolen Bicycle" (2015), which break from that pattern by putting non-human agents at the center. These novels cast butterflies, elephants, birds, man-fish, and bamboo forests as active participants in Taiwan's colonial past. Using an ecocritical perspective, Chang (2020) shows how these non-human agents

shape Taiwanese political identities and historical representations. Offering a non-anthropocentric narrative that questions common wisdom, these books highlight the powerful role non-human agents play in Taiwan's political and cultural world. They drive readers to think again about the larger historical and ecological settings that shape the country's story, in addition to the citizens' experiences.

Alongside other forms of non-human agents, dogs are also used to represent non-human humanitarians that are portrayed as important players in international operations that have a major influence on humanitarian services and bring about changes with both positive and harmful outcomes. According to Meiches (2019) in his research titled "Non-human Humanitarians," most studies on humanitarian interventions concentrate on the victims and rescuers who are people in armed conflict or natural catastrophes. Additionally, justifications for the benefits of humanitarian ethics and norms place a strong emphasis on the fact that suffering is experienced by everyone and, therefore, humanitarian actions are innately compassionate. Notwithstanding, Meiches' (2019) paper delves into the underappreciated context of "non-human humanitarians," particularly discussing three instances of non-human actors – dogs, drones, and diagrams – that amplify and complicate global humanitarian efforts. Meiches' (2019) study made the case that non-humans have unique abilities that significantly increase and change humanitarian operations, ranging from relief to medical to conflict resolution, by drawing on new materialist and posthuman pieces of literature. Therefore, emphasizing non-human humanitarians blurs the lines between humanitarian norms and provides a fresh look at the tools at our disposal for addressing mass violence over war. Contrariwise, Meiches' (2019) paper shows that non-humans not only frequently outperform humans in providing humanitarian aid, but they have also altered humanitarian procedures in ways that

have severe side effects. Humanitarians who don't kill people expose hitherto underappreciated players in world politics and the crucial roles they perform in a range of international actions.

In another important study, whales, matsutake mushrooms, and mosquitoes have their own agency to shape history. In Blair's (2021) study titled "Non-human Agency in Environmental History," she argues for a wider view of agency, one that goes beyond looking only at people. This means recognizing how animals, fungi, and insects can drive historical events. Blair's (2021) study emphasizes the reason why we must pay attention to these living organisms. She provides examples of how whales, mushrooms, and mosquitoes have actively altered events and changed ecosystems. In her investigation, Blair (2021) uses three case studies. First, Bathsheba Demuth's *Floating Coast: An Environmental History of the Bering Strait* examines how whales interact with industrial whaling and Yupik whaling techniques in the Bering Strait. Demuth shows that whales are sentient beings with free will, culture, and the ability to resist human activity. She calls this idea of a world full of acting beings a "will-filled universe." Second, Blair (2021) draws on Anna Lowenhaupt Tsing's *The Mushroom at the End of the World: On the Possibility of Life in Capitalist Ruins*, which demonstrates how matsutake mushrooms adapt to ruined landscapes by forming linkages with pine and oak forests. In her work, Tsing challenged the human-centric perspective of progress and disaster by arguing that these non-human organisms are "world-builders," underlining the significance of acknowledging the agency of multispecies assemblages in determining ecological outcomes. Third, Blair (2021) also uses J.R. McNeill's book *Mosquito Empires: Ecology and War in the Greater Caribbean, 1620-1914*. This work shows how mosquitoes shaped the Caribbean's geography by spreading yellow fever and malaria, which in turn influenced European

colonization and conquest. McNeill contends that one of the best illustrations of non-human agency influencing historical results is the influence of mosquitoes on human behavior. With the utilization of these case studies, Blair (2021) discovered that whales actively participated in human activities, interacting with Yupik and industrial whaling techniques and exhibiting sentience, culture, and resistance. The anthropocentric theory of human dominion over the environment is challenged by matsutake mushrooms and their related assemblages, which include pine and oak trees. Matsutake mushrooms showed persistence and world-building capacities amid devastated settings. Also, Blair (2021) discovered that mosquitoes had a significant impact on the geopolitical evolution of the Caribbean, influencing European colonization and conquest by dispersing yellow fever and malaria. Matsutake mushrooms show persistence and world-building capacities amid devastated settings. Blair (2021) contends that comprehending historical transformation and promoting a more sustainable future depends on acknowledging the action of non-human agents, inspiring environmental historians to embrace a broader definition of agency that recognizes the interdependence and transformational potential of the natural world, moving beyond human-centered viewpoints.

Objectual and Spatial Agency

Another forms of agency, such as objects and spaces, possess agency as they also act and speak on behalf of someone or something that cause transformations for organizational dynamics and accomplishment, as illustrated by empirical studies discussed below.

Firstly, a self-propelled box acts as a non-human agent that can be attributed to goals by human agents as young as infants. In Luo's (2011) study, it was

investigated if babies as young as three months old – the earliest known to be capable of goal-related reasoning regarding human agents – would likewise behave as though they were attributing objectives to a brand-new non-human agent, a self-propelled box. In two trials, when the babies saw the box approach object A during familiarization rather than object B, they appeared to interpret the box's behavior as goal-oriented. When the box got close to object B during the test, people replied more intently, acting as though they expected it to continue pursuing this objective. However, the infants' responses were consistent with realizing they had no information to predict which of the two objects the box should choose during the test, when object B was absent during the test, when object B was absent during familiarization and introduced later, the infants responded similarly when the box approached either object. Notwithstanding, in the event that object B was not present during familiarization and object A was in various positions but the box continued to approach it, exhibiting equifinal variations in its actions, the infants once more behaved as though they attributed to the box a goal directed towards object A and anticipated the box to maintain this goal even upon the introduction of object B. As a result, they responded with prolonged staring when the box failed to accomplish this goal during the experiment. These results support the following theories: 1) babies as young as three months old seem to ascribe objectives to both human and non-human agents; and 2) even young infants may deduce the aims of agents from specific behavioral clues, such as equifinal fluctuations in the behaviors of agents.

Within the ambit of how adults and children perceive and evaluate agents, non-human agents significantly influence how agents are perceived, encouraging designers to take into consideration these perceptions in creating artificial agents for various ages. In their study titled "From Non-human to Human: Adult's and Children's

Perceptions of Agents Varying in Humanness,” Krumhuber, et al. (2015) investigated how adults and children perceive and evaluate agents based on their degree of human-like appearance. Their study showed that children may focus less on traits that only humans have when judging an agent’s skills. Instead, they pay more attention to simple thinking and social abilities. To explore this idea, the researchers showed four different characters to both adults and children. These characters ranged from a blob-like non-human form to a realistic human figure, with two designs in between. Participants were then asked to put these figures in order based on how well they thought each one could feel emotions and solve problems. The results revealed that both adults and children based their judgments largely on appearance. However, adults showed a more detailed pattern: the more human-like a figure looked, the higher the rating, but with nuances depending on the specific design. Children, by contrast, seemed to base their ratings more on core cognitive and social features than on how much the figure resembled a real person. Based on Krumhuber et al.’s (2015) study, designers of artificial agents should think about how different age groups perceive and interact with characters, taking into account their looks and assumed abilities. Additionally, designers may produce artificial agents and interfaces that are more successful and meet the social and cognitive expectations of both adults and children by considering these distinctions.

New materialist concepts see spaces, materials, and forces as non-human agents that help shape creative practices in the performing arts. Choat (2020) explains this in his study “Performance and Materialism: Towards an Expanded Notion of Non-Human Agency.” His study shows that materials, locations, and forces can act beyond human plans and drive changes in performance. It shows that matter is always shifting and interacting with living beings. This notion emphasizes how objects, surfaces, and

energies join with people in networks of action and reaction that produce creative forms that we might otherwise overlook. Choat's (2020) study uses two case studies to show these ideas in practice. In *"Material Interactions,"* performers work directly with fabrics, metals, and natural elements on stage. These materials push back, adapt, or change as they are handled, creating new effects and meanings. In *"Body-Body Experiments,"* human bodies interact with plants, animals, or microbes. Each body's agency appears through touch, shared rhythms, or changing surroundings. These studies show how human intention blends with material response, blurring the line between creators and their tools and leading to surprising forms of creative expressions. They highlight the active role of non-human agents in shaping each moment. Choat's (2020) work shows that these collaborations between humans and non-humans can transform how we create and understand performance art. He urges artists and researchers to rethink the material world not as a static backdrop but as a partner with its own power to shape form, mood, and meaning. This view can inspire more engaging productions. Choat (2020) connects his findings to broader discussions about how technology and science reshape our creative landscapes. He invites theater makers, designers, and scholars to notice everyday materials, such as stage lights, costumes, set pieces, and weather conditions, as participants in performance. Involving these elements from the start of a project, teams can uncover new ideas. This perspective opens paths in theory and practice and marks non-human agents as essential collaborators in crafting experiences on stage.

Presentified by objects possessing agency, non-human agents are considered integral to shaping human interactions and co-creating the world in the post-humanist era. Research by Kwak and Park in 2020 evaluated how human agency is mediated in scientific education in the post-humanist era. The phrase "the nano-self" embodies

this era's blurring of the lines distinguishing human and non-human beings. The nature of our interaction with objects in this day and age and its educational significance are among the issues raised by the Kwak and Park's (2020) study. Given the technologically hybrid and dehumanizing tendencies of our society, their study attempted to answer the research question – what meaningful relationships can we, as human actors, make with both artificial and natural things? According to Bruno Latour, renowned materialist and philosopher of technology, “objects” have agency in the same way as people do. Therefore, in order for us to co-shape our reality, there is a need for us to be able to translate the language of things into the language of people, and vice versa. Kwak and Park's (2020) paper aimed at reformulating Latour's conceptualization of the mediating function of human agency while critically analyzing his theory. The goal is to develop a post-humanist concept of human agency that is tenable from an educational standpoint, as it can point the way toward environmentally and politically responsible methods of teaching, especially in the context of scientific education.

Moreover, interior architecture (space) and ordinary objects in the intensive care unit (ICU) such as the glove box, alcoholic dispenser, monitors, and handwritten clinical records are found to possess agency for their influence on the identification of the “right course of action” and their contribution to the philosophical underpinnings of medicine with the ICU landscape. Caronia and Mortari's (2015) study titled “The Agency of Things: How Spaces and Artifacts Organize the Moral Order of an Intensive Care Unit,” investigated the role of space and objects in defining the moral order of a specific context. Employing post-humanistic phenomenology, their study enhances our comprehension of communication as a multifaceted phenomenon that encompasses both human and non-human agents. This claim was empirically

supported by the study's ethnographic research conducted in an ICU, examining how the ICU's commonplace items, including the glove box, liquor dispenser, monitors, and handwritten clinical record, and its interior design affect the "right course of action" and contribute to the overall medical philosophy of this specific ICU.

In the performing arts milieu, costumes, props, and stage settings are seen to act as non-human agents that play a significant role in molding the negotiation of embodied agency, specifically in ballet and fashion alongside human actors like dancers and models. In the study of Satama and Huopalainen (2018) titled "Bring Down the Controlled Movements! – Exploring the Possibilities of and Limitations on Achieving Embodied Agency in Ballet and Fashion, the complexities of exercising embodied agency in two contexts influenced by ideals and norms (ballet and fashion) was investigated. The researchers particularly concentrated on how models and dancers continuously negotiate their potential and constraints for establishing agency during the off-stage practices that precede their on-stage performances. While embodiment has received a lot of attention lately in the subject of organization studies, little is known about the practice and choreography of embodied agency between the "hidden" offstage areas and the front stages that are visible to the public, or in connection to the various human and non-human agents that are present in the field. Two distinct ethnographic investigations provided the empirical data for Satama and Huopalainen's (2018) work. In order to obtain a greater comprehension of this intricate phenomena, the researchers integrated findings from both perspectives. Their work advances our comprehension of embodied agency as a micro-level relational activity and sheds light on the surprisingly stale discourse around embodied practices in organizational studies.

Technological Agency

With the mushrooming of technology in the world, it has become one of the subjects of research, specifically on non-human agencies in communication research. As demonstrated by the empirical studies below, technological agents like robots and robot avatars; digital media, program, models, and platforms; gaming gadgets; the now-famous artificial intelligence; and cyborgs also possess agency as they have the capability to presentify their respective principals. As elaborated on the succeeding paragraphs, these technological agents have been proven to have influenced other agencies to effect organizational dynamics and accomplishment.

Robot avatars are seen to possess agency bearing significant influences on the behaviors of humans. In their research on the empathic embarrassment towards non-human agents in virtual environments, Hapuarachchi, et al. (2003) assert that humans feel empathic embarrassment by witnessing others go through embarrassing situations. The researchers, even with robot avatars, investigated if they experience the same kind of humiliation. In the conduct of their study, an array of humiliating and non-embarrassing circumstances was presented to the participants by a human avatar and a robot avatar. A 7-point Likert scale was used to collect data for both cognitive empathy and empathic humiliation. Comparing the humiliated condition to the non-employed condition for both avatars, there was a substantial increase in both cognitive empathy and empathic embarrassment, with the human avatar manifesting greatest increase in social empathy. Watching the human avatar experiencing uncomfortable situations tended to cause participants to exhibit higher levels of skin conductance than the robot avatar. According to a subsequent experiment, the average believability of the humiliated condition was much greater with the human avatar than with the robot avatar. Nevertheless, plausibility ratings for emotion did not change substantially

between their circumstances. According to these findings, humans are capable of experiencing both cognitive empathy and empathic embarrassment towards robot avatars, while robot avatars exhibit relatively less cognitive empathy. It is possible that this discrepancy in plausibility is due to some of the empathic differences between human and robot avatars.

Additionally, non-human agencies, the agency of technology, are also actants in the social system that generates creative outputs. This was discovered by Holmes (2012) when he conducted a heuristic case study incorporating non-human agency in the incidence of social creativity of one short cycle in the iterative development of a temporally emergent technological system being developed for use in underground coalmines that utilizes this pool of knowledge. According to Holmes' (2012) in his research, in order to ensure the safe running of an underground coalmine, a control room where all communication between workers below ground and those on the surface is monitored, together with data from various sensory devices. This is where any emergency response is commenced. Any one of several automated or manual alarms will set off specific danger management tactics and emergency procedures. The control room operator may get cognitively overwhelmed by the huge amount of information that has to be processed, particularly in a situation when a catastrophic disaster might occur. A rules engine, a unique computer software-based system called Nexsys™, provides control by means of a single interface and helps with real-time monitoring and reaction. This study of Holmes (2012) was based on the experience of a designer who was tasked with suggesting a user interface design for a particular location that would permit for effectual operational condition monitoring and prioritized, contextually appropriate access to technical papers, protocols, and communications. This thoughtful study report consults trans-disciplinary literature for the purpose of

theorizing the nature of the creativity necessary in putting a user-centered design approach into practice. The heuristic analysis of Holmes' (2012) study suggests that before a convincing account of the sources of creativity involved may be proposed, Csikszentmihalyi's (1999) "systems perspective for the study of creativity" be appended to include non-human agency. This is from the perspective of a creative industry practitioner working in an industrial situation not commonly associated with creativity.

In a different study, digital media, which include technology and content, were seen to act as non-human agents playing a crucial role in the teaching and learning process. They are particularly significant in mentoring and achieving the educational goals of individual courses through teacher-student interactions. The 2015 study by Saludadez tried to clarify why and how open universities fulfill their mission of education. The study investigated how to examine and explain how learning and education are feasible at a distance using the Agency Framework as a theoretical anchor. Saludadez's (2015) paper provided examples of how digital media might act as facilitators to help facilitate online research-based teaching and learning. The study used a ventriloquial approach, which consists of three steps: 1) gathering recorder and archived online interactions; 2) identifying markers that give the impression that digital media express themselves iteratively and recurrently in the recorder interactions; and, 3) comprehending or hearing what the markers are intended to convey. With this approach, the Saludadez's (2015) study demonstrated how interactive activities in a graduate-level research course at an open university may be created through digital media, allowing students to experience the process of creating and carrying out research using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. It became clear why

education may be achieved remotely when the agentive responsibilities of digital media are abstracted from teacher-student interactions.

In the live video game performances landscape, gaming consoles, actual games, data, pixels, and other tangible props were found to have agency and were also discovered to bear influence on the quality of the live game performances. This was discovered by Huuhka (2022) in his study which focused on the relationship between humans and non-humans in live video game performances. Here, non-humans include tangible things like gaming console, actual games, data, pixels, and other props that kids employ for their performances. During their classes, the students were given a set of ambiguous criteria, including “recreate a classic” or “create a performance for pixel audience,” to follow when creating performances in or using video games. Although the students were given a lot of freedom to select the games, the selection was partly constrained by the availability of gaming equipment. Including actual props, inspiration, allusions, and ideas, video games have a variety of roles in the performances. Alongside real actors, they were also provided stage time. Games or gaming consoles have taken the place of the audience in certain shows. Non-human performers can sometimes be dismissed as mere lifeless puppets, but when looking at things such as video games, pixels, or game devises, it is clear that they have more agency than one might think. It is a fact that all technology can fail, and all intermedial/live media performances face the possibility of failures, power outages, glitches, bugs, and various other disruptions. These disruptions can be considered as manifestations of agency. During intermedial/live media performances, failures and disruptions add an improvisational element as the non-humans temporarily control the stage. During the workshops, these failures and disruptions happened frequently, partly because the rehearsal time was relatively short. Unanticipated non-human

components and occurrences gave meanings that could not have been obtained by human interactions alone. Utilizing the illustration from performance workshops, Huuhka (2022) underlined the importance of non-humans to game performance and gameplay as well.

In the field of sociology which centers on human interactions, non-human agents, alongside human actors, are also considered decision-makers, providing insights into their interactions and demonstrating how technology and humans interact in a symmetrical relationship. The study conducted by Fink and Weyer (2013) titled “Interaction of Human Actors and Non-Human Agents: A Sociological Simulation Model Hybrid Systems,” accentuated the necessity for a sociological explication of hybrid systems (HMSE), claiming that a model that considers both non-human and human decision-makers operating based on subjective anticipated utility (SEU) provides important insights into how they interact. Sociological theory has always placed a strong emphasis on human agency, leaving human factors research or ANT to handle the role of technology in human-machine interactions. This gap is filled by Fink and Weyer’s (2013) paper, which suggests an experimental approach to investigate these processes within a sociological framework. According to their HMSE model, technology and humans interact or engage in “co-action” in a way that makes it possible to do empirical research on the agency of non-human entities. Bruno Latour’s idea that humans and non-humans should be seen equally inspired Fink and Weyer (2013) to suggest that sociological theories can address these issues. They focused on Hartmut Esser’s model of sociological explanation (MSE). In their study, they created computer simulations based on the MSE to show that people treat technological systems as agents. They found that even when responsibility was divided equally in the experiments, participants still saw people and robots as equally

responsible and blamed them both the same for successes and failures. Fink and Weyer (2013) stressed that the MSE model can help us understand how human and non-human actors interact in mixed environments. They clarified the complex relationships in highly automated systems through the combination of sociological theory and experimental work. Their approach shows that seeing machines as tools, people view robots as partners, reflecting new shared agency between humans and technology.

Additionally, when we look at how young and older adults understand feelings, virtual agents that are not humans become a way to send and judge those feelings. A study by Numata et al. (2019) explores this idea. It focuses on how people from different age groups interpret emotions shown by a virtual agent whose facial expressions change in real time. They wanted to see how well younger versus older people recognize emotions when they interact with such agents. Their results show that older users had more variations in their ability to identify emotions than younger users did. The goal of their work is to improve emotional communication between people and non-human robots or virtual agents, which can help with everyday activities. For these agents to interact emotionally with humans, they must express emotions clearly and be correctly understood by users. Even though we still do not know exactly how age affects emotion recognition for non-human characters, past research shows that age plays a strong role. In an earlier study, Numata et al. (2015) used a forced-choice questionnaire featuring seven basic emotions. They asked 39 older and 62 younger participants to choose the emotions they saw in the virtual agent's face. This study looked at how expressions made by non-human agents influence emotion recognition. It found that older adults showed greater differences in their emotion identification skills compared to younger adults. Understanding these

individual differences in how people perceive emotions is crucial for good emotional interactions between older adults and non-human systems. Numata et al. (2015) emphasized that we must adapt emotional communication strategies in new technologies to support a wide range of users. They also noted that studies should explore a wider variety of emotions and include diverse cultural groups to see if these patterns hold across backgrounds.

Moreover, Multidimensional Gradual Agency is a rigorous framework that explains how both people and non-human elements, like computer programs, can have agency in social and technical systems. It shows that digital artifacts do more than act as tools; they join in interactions as active partners. Thürmel's (2015) study, "The Participatory Turn: A Multidimensional Gradual Agency Concept for Human and Non-Human Actors," carefully examined and compared various detailed computer simulations with different complex real-world laboratory scenarios. The use of a multidimensional framework to categorize joint and individual agency made it possible to investigate dispersed and collective agency in socio-technical systems. Thürmel's (2015) study emphasized the growing ways software agents, robots, and humans work together. It highlighted that computer-based tools have moved even beyond mere instruments to become active participants in interactions that take on roles rather than just following user commands. Social computing systems are fundamental for simulating complicated human and non-human interactions and connections in the sense that they utilize agent-based modeling (ABM) and multi-agent systems (MAS). These simulations can take place in cyber-physical systems or virtual settings, where MAS might affect both the virtual and real worlds. Practically speaking, these systems show their effects in real-time applications controlling natural processes (real actuality) and in controlled testbeds testbed settings (virtual actuality). This approach made it

possible to look at different dispersed agency and inter-agency configurations. The four characteristics of the framework, which include activity level, adaptivity, interaction, and personification of others, are essential for understating how various agency configurations appear in sociotechnical settings. Through contrasting human-only situations with simulations built using this categorization approach, scientists were able to learn more about the dynamics and efficacy of dispersed and collective agency in complex systems.

WeChat, a digital platform, was also identified as a non-human agent that plays a significant role in facilitating connective actions through the assemblage of dispersed individuals, information, and resources into cohesive protest networks. This concept is supported by Cao's (2022) research on the role of articulative labor in organizing protest networks within the fragmented digital sphere of WeChat, a notable WeChat-based protest campaign primarily spearheaded by Chinese Americans. The main purpose of Cao's (2022) study was to question accepted ideas about the roles of human and non-human actors in digitally mediated activism and to provide light on the complicated dynamics of coordinating across disjointed digital platforms. As recent scholarly study has shown, it underscored how connected action is emerging as a new kind of grassroots activism made possible by digital networks and platforms. In contrast to traditional social movements that are propelled by coordinated collective activities, connective actions mostly depend on non-human agents particularly digital platform, which take advantage of their innate connection to bring disparate people, data, and resources together to establish coherent protest networks. However, this standpoint sometimes ignores the restrictions placed on platform by proprietary systems and "walled gardens," which can impede rather than help connection. Created to function inside China's tightly regulated digital market, the well-known

Chinese social media site WeChat serves as an example of this difficulty because of its architecture. Even with its connection attributes, WeChat's controlled environment limits the free flow of information and resources that are essential for successful mobilization. Cao (2022) utilized observations, interviews, and textual analysis to show how these difficulties affected the course of the WeChat-based protest movement. Contrary to the idea that WeChat helps non-human organizations function, activities had to put in a lot of articulative work because of the platform's limitations. This labor entailed negotiating resources to articulate and maintain the protest network, breaking through limitations imposed by the platforms, and linking disparate digital spaces. Through the analysis of these processes, the research not only revealed the important but sometimes disregarded function of articulative labor in network activism, but also challenges popular technological determinism viewpoints that place an excessive emphasis on the agency of non-human actors in influencing activism. It persuaded academics and activists to reexamine the intricate relationships that exist between human agency, non-human platforms, and the intricate socio-political environments that give rise to and shape collective actions. Cao's (2022) research prompted a fresh look at how people connect and organize modern online communities. It showed that digital spaces, fragmented and controlled by rules and policies, constantly change. The study also revealed how activism develops complex strategies to adjust and persist despite these shifting challenges in the global digital environment.

Going further, artificial intelligence systems today act as non-human agents in sharing and shaping memory. They do more than store information. They help bring back memories, create new memory-like content, and guide how people find, understand, and pass on memories. Makhortykh's (2024) study looked closely at how these non-human agents work in digital memory communication. It described three

simple models of agency: human-to-human exchange, human-to-robot exchange, and robot-to-robot exchange. These models show modern digital tools, especially AI search engines and chatbots, play a central role when people interact with memory. Before digital technology, memory sharing happened mainly between people talking to each other. Now, AI systems join in. They search for old photos, suggest past events, and even generate stories that connect to personal or shared experiences. This shift means that memory communication is no longer just a human task. Instead, non-human tools take part. They shape what memories appear, how clearly they come back, and how people talk about them afterward. Makhortykh (2024) emphasized that digital tools are active participants rather than passive pipes. They can talk with each other and with humans. As an example, one chatbot might pass information to another, or a person might ask a robot to find old messages. These interactions change the way memories return and how people describe or remember them. As a result, the landscape of memory communication keeps evolving. The three agency models have effects beyond technology improvements. They invite us to rethink how culture and individuals create and interpret memory. New forms of memory activity now exist, ranging from direct human conversations to automatic memory retrieval and processing powered by AI. These forms challenge older ideas about how memory moves from one mind to another. Makhortykh's (2024) work also highlights questions for future study in memory communication. Researchers will need to examine how non-human agents shape memory stories at both personal and social levels. They should look at how these new digital interactions affect the truthfulness, clarity, and cultural value of memories in our digital world. Makhortykh's (2024) study shows that the field of memory transmission is changing fast. AI-powered tools introduce new

agency models that alter how we share, process, and save memories in modern society today and for future generations.

Aside from AI systems acting as agents in memory communication, researchers saw cyborgs as having agency and used them to study how people grant moral status to beings whose ways of sensing, acting, and understanding the world change through technology. In their 2022 study “Towards Turing test 2.0 – Attribution of Moral Status and Personhood to Human and Non-Human Agents,” Lukaszewicz and Fortuna explore non-human agency. They redesigned the Turing test to examine how people recognize different artificial and augmented beings as moral individuals. The study looks at non-human agents with varying bodies and asks whether they deserve moral consideration. Based on their research, moral recognition is not only exclusive to “natural” Homo sapiens but can also apply to improved humans, including cyborgs. The study meticulously looked into how people now feel about cyborgs and found signs that these opinions could change in the years to come. In this milieu, the term “cyborg” refers to a literal interpretation of the term, meaning that people who have had their technological abilities enhanced have shifted perceptions, ways of being, and self-awareness. In the empirical portion of the research, 322 Polish men and women were surveyed to examine the moral status of different agents, including humans, cyborgs, fembots, social robots, animals, and algorithms. The findings revealed that people do, as a matter of fact, give a variety of actors – both human and non-human – moral standing. Significantly, determining someone’s moral standing is not a simple binary decision; rather, it is dynamic and gradable, changing depending on a variety of circumstances and experiences. This complicated stance draws attention to the potential for wider moral contemplation in an increasingly technologically associated world.

Aside from cyborgs, robots are also believed to possess agency and exert influence in the emergence of social actions and interactions within the human-robot network. Collins and Trajkovski's (2006) study titled "Robot Without Organs?: Assemblage, Agency, and Networked Sociality in Human-Robot Interaction" provides an overview of the results of an experiment on Human-Robot Interaction in a near zero-context environment. The experiment's primary goal was to investigate how social behaviors and situations arise when a network between human and non-human creatures is formed. Without being aware of the robot's sensory or motor capabilities beforehand, teams of three to four human subjects are tasked with talking a robot into moving from one side of a table to the other. Using any method of communication, the exercise aimed at "moving" the robot while simultaneously encouraging emergent interactions between human and non-human beings. Collins and Trajkovski (2006) evaluated the social phenomena that occur in this human-machine assemblage, concentrating on turn-taking and conversation in particular. Although, this may appear counter-intuitive, their findings implied that the "transparency" of non-human beings may not be the best strategy to develop multi-agent sociality.

Within the ambits of the creation of intelligent reality in virtual reality (VR) simulations, technology and the digital twin (DT) were also seen to have agency and perform an integral role in the shaping of meaningful sonic experiences within Virtual Environments (VE). Geronazzo's (2022) study titled "Egocentric Audio in the Digital Twin of Virtual Environments," asserted that, in VE, audio technologies play a significant role in immersive and interactive experiences. VR simulations need to be environmentally performed through a network of human and non-human actors – a participatory investigation of sense-making. The DT is the protector of this center of agency, facilitating human-technology interactions and dynamically and fluidly

recreating all the configurations needed for meaningful auditory experiences. In Geronazzo's (2022) study, the concept of human-machine entanglement is mostly rejected from an egocentric, spatial viewpoint that is connected to growing understanding of the subjectivity of the listener. Based on adaptive and reflective behaviors of VR technologies, a systemic approach like this may be understood as a working definition of intelligent reality: a perceptual and cognitive co-constitution of physical and virtual worlds. The fundamental theoretical conclusions given in Geronazzo's (2020) study are based on the premise that auditory experiences can be regarded as a multi-layered, linked network of actors at two primary levels: immersion and coherence. These levels are linked by a deep theory (DT), which has the potential to change the listener's perception.

Lastly, social media, alongside other non-human agents, were seen to exhibit agency as they were highlighted as important forces that work in tandem with human actors to shape participation and create an environment that fosters inclusivity, variety, and unpredictability. This was supported by the study of Junttila (2020) titled "Exercises in Intra-Acting: A Zone of Potential," which examined the participatory performance event "Speak for Yourself" (Snakk för Deg Sjol). As part of the Norwegian Cultural Schoolbag program (Den kulturelle skolesekken), the event is primarily offered to teenagers in schools; however, it is also available to the general public at Halogaland Theatre and the Arctic Arts Festival. The focus of the conversation is on what might pique people's interests and create a viable zone for his performance event. Junttila's (2020) study was based on the author's perspective as an artist-researcher, as she is one of the performers. A feminist theorist and physicist named Karen Barad is credited with creating the concept of agential realism, which serves as the study's theoretical underpinning. According to the research findings, participation

initiation is a complicated process influenced by both interactant human and non-human performative actors. In this performance event, the study focused on how exercises, performance items, social media, multiplicity, and emotion were created as performative agents. Junttila (2020) says watching different performers and how people respond to them can help build a space that supports inclusion, diversity, and surprising outcomes. Other hands-on projects that mix art and education might gain a lot from this kind of space. It shows how creative actions can lead to new and meaningful learning experiences.

Textual Agency

François Cooren (2004, 2008), a communication expert from France and Canada, studied textual agency in depth. His important work looks at how texts play an active role in organizations, questioning the old idea that only people have agency in communication (Cooren. 2004; 2008). Cooren (2004, 2008) shows that text can influence how organizations work, talk, and make decisions. He highlights how both people and non-human things, like written documents, interact in communication. This view helps us see how texts help shape relationships and choices in organizations. Cooren's (2004) research not only questions the traditional way of thinking but also helps us better understand how communication works on many levels. His ideas show that texts are not passive tools, but they are also active parts of how organizations function and grow through communication.

According to Cooren (2004), documents like reports and memos, which are non-human agents, are not just static records but have real influence. They help shape and guide how organizations develop and function. This idea matches Putnam and Fairhurst (2001), who also stress that texts and their active roles are key to

understanding organizational relationships. Cooren (2008) uses semiotics and pragmatics to show how written materials start conversations and drive communication processes. His work emphasizes the energetic interaction between language, text, and ongoing organizational change processes.

Additionally, Cooren (2004) says non-human agents like texts can perform assertive, commissive, and directive actions within various distinct organizational communication processes. Using the category of assertives proposed by Searle (1979) and Vanderveken (1990), it can be concluded that texts can inform, indicate, say, tell, assert, deny, suggest, foretell, and even prophesy. Texts may also attest, confirm, contradict, dispute, critique, contest, question, accuse, denounce, or even declare. On the other hand, texts cannot recognize, confess, or express pride in their deeds. These verbs imply a human quality that cannot be transferred to writings and papers. The act of “admitting” is unique to humans and can only be accomplished through speaking. As a result, the written or spoken material developed for this purpose can only be seen as a means of communicating information, disseminating it, or acting as a physical medium.

Furthermore, texts have a unique ability to have an intangible influence, which is especially evident when it comes to commissive behaviors like swearing, accepting, agreeing, or refusing, which are not normally linked with documents. Contracts, on the other hand, make people accountable for certain actions or rewards, thereby binding them to meet commitments or give promises. A promissory note, as an illustration, expresses a promise to repay money on demand or at a specific time. The ability to commit is not inherent in the text itself, but rather depends on the participation of other parties. Although a document cannot commit an activity on its own, it can facilitate

commitment on behalf of the parties concerned, thereby exercising agency when signatories are required to execute certain activities in the future (Cooren, 2008).

Certain papers, such as formal invitations, might seek action from people. Furthermore, different texts can provide advice, make requests, suggest, extend invitations, recommend, warn, alert, issue orders, seek, demand, exert pressure, summon, command, instruct, prohibit, forbid, permit, authorize, or stipulate. It is worth noting that certain illocutionary activities, such as requesting, demanding, allowing, or authorizing, can only be carried out by legally binding documents, such as constitutional, legal, or official documents. Nevertheless, this also applies to any person to whom we assign the ability to perform such an action. Work orders are an example of such paperwork.

Peace process documents, which are textual agents, have been discovered to have a significant role in resolving a conflict between two parties in Mindanao, Philippines. It was found out in Isla's (2024) study that addressed the research questions "what is the authority of peace agreements" and "how do peace agreements perform/invoke their power." His study looked into two landmark peace agreements in the Mindanao, Philippines peace process: 1) the 1996 Final Peace Agreement and Implementation of the 1976 Tripoli Agreement, and 2) the 2014 Comprehensive Agreement of Bangsamoro (CAB), based on François Cooren's groundbreaking theories on non-human agency and Searle's Speech Act Theory. The efficacy of the peace agreement in ensuring the implementation of the stipulations it contains is the primary source of its authority. Directives hold a secondary position, followed by commissives, with assertives and declarations being the least significant. Under the terms of the peace accord, two conflicting parties may be compelled to sign an agreement. Additionally, the agreements serve the following purposes: under the

directives, they command or order the implementation of essential monitoring and transition mechanisms, the drafting and enactment of fundamental laws, the creation of a normalization program, and the establishment of equal representation. The assertives of the Mindanao peace agreements are to: 1) recognize the Bangsamoro identity for the realization of long-term peace; 2) affirm the autonomy of the Bangsamoro; 3) highlight the need for transition; and 4) emphasize the importance of socioeconomic, cultural, and educational development.

Other textual agencies can also presentify their respective principals to act and speak on their behalf to contribute to organizational dynamics and accomplishment. Accentuating the importance of considering their influence in translation activities, textual agents play an active role alongside human actors in shaping the translation process and outcomes. This is demonstrated by the study of Luo and Zheng (2017) on “Visiting Elements Thought to Be ‘Inactive’: Non-Human Actors in Arthur Waley’s Translation of *Journey to the West*.” Their research centered on the investigation of non-human actors involved in the translation and publication of “*Monkey*,” which is an English translation of the ancient Chinese text *Xi You Ji*. The ANT was used to look at how publisher George Allen and Unwin, translator Arthur Waley, and book jacket and title page designer Duncan Grant worked together. The main evidence came from letters they sent each other. The researchers also looked at the publishers’ autobiography and Waley’s Preface to *Monkey* for more details. Through their investigation, Luo and Zheng (2017) split non-human actors into two groups, as ANT scholars usually do. One group was composed of documents, such as Waley’s Preface to *Monkey* and emails between Waley and Unwin, which explain why they made a second translation of *Monkey* and how they did it. They reviewed each letter, email, and document to track how texts and events moved ideas, shaped decisions,

and guided actions during the translation process. The other group was composed of big historical events that stopped Monkey from being reprinted, like the flu pandemic in the 1940s and World War II. Based on this, Luo and Zheng (2017) said that to really understand translation as a process, we need to include non-human actors as well as people because both shape the work and results of major translation projects.

Additionally, people believe books can shape a country's history by acting like non-human agents. This idea shows why it is important to teach students about agency so they can better understand complex events and how history affects our world today. Nieuwenhuysse (2019) supports this idea in his study "Between Non-Human and Individual Agents: The Attribution of Agency in Chapters on the Cold War in Flemish History Books." In this study, he compared four Flemish textbooks used by twelfth graders to see how they present the Soviet Union and the USA in their Cold War chapters. Using content and discourse analysis, he examined how these books give agency to different actors, from states and institutions to individual people. Nieuwenhuysse (2019) argues that teaching agency helps students grasp its role in both past and present events. His findings suggest that history classes should offer nuanced views, avoid one-sided accounts, and include multiple perspectives on the Cold War. This way, students learn that both individuals and groups can influence outcomes now and in the future. These ideas help learners see that history is not fixed but shaped by many forces. Recognizing agency shows how decisions by people and systems can create change. This approach also actively enriches classroom discussion.

Moreover, research showed that noun phrases act like non-human agents. They help shape differences in how Indo-European languages mark agents in passive sentences. In his 1986 study "On the Distribution of Instrumental and Agentive

Markers for Human and Non-Human Agents of Passive Verbs in Some Indo-European Languages,” Luraghi (1986) showed that these languages differ in signaling agency in passive sentences. He noted that marking agents depends on whether they are humans. Indo-European languages can mark agents with agentive or instrumental endings. Agentive endings suggest that the agent has strong control over the action. Instrumental endings usually show that an instrument or tool does the action in active sentences. Based on data from several Indo-European languages, Luraghi (1986) developed a simple classification of agent noun phrases. His work shows the complex but clear patterns behind marking agency in different languages that truly highlight language diversity. Languages are categorized into three groups: Type A languages identify human agents using a type A morpheme and non-human agents using a type B morpheme; Type B languages identify both human and non-human agents using a type A morpheme; and Type C languages identify both human and non-agents using a type B morpheme. Languages categorized as Type A exhibit a deep structure that reveals a semantic distinction, Type B languages prioritize agentivity, while Type C languages concentrate on delegating the agent’s syntactic function of the subject.

In order to improve pilgrimage travels that transcend physical sites and influence narratives and experiences beyond Kent, pilgrim passports and stamps were found to act as non-human agents, portraying an important role in increasing the emotive and transformative components of pilgrimage routes. Shenar’s (2022) study on “Affective Stamps: The Animating Force of Pilgrim Stamps” investigated the relationship between religion, animism, and pilgrimage, with a particular emphasis on the role of pilgrim passports and stamps. Through the investigation of the agency of these artifacts, a profound comprehension of pilgrimage as an idea that is associated with both human and non-human entities can be obtained. Shenar (2022), in his study,

evaluated several facets of pilgrimage in Kent, England, including pilgrimage walks, festivals, and businesses, drawing on modern literature that underscores the significance of materiality. In doing so, Shenar (2022) drew attention to the intricate associations that exist between individuals, things, locations, and abstract concepts. The primordial focus of Shenar's (2022) contribution is on how pilgrimage's tangible components – such as passports and stamps – can elevate the allure and metamorphic potential of pilgrimage routes. Consequently, these pathways influence stories, encounters, morality, and ideas not only in Kent but also in other places.

Other Forms of Agencies

Apart from those agencies discussed, there are other non-human agents that do not fall under any of the categorized agents above. These other forms of agencies – theoretical, spiritual, and even medical condition agencies – also participate in communicative practices, presentifying their respective principals and influencing human agents' decision-making activities. As discussed below, these other forms of agencies also contribute to organizational dynamics and accomplishment.

For the purpose of expanding Marxist theory and incorporating non-human entities as agents, it is crucial to recognize the significance of these entities within Marxist and communist frameworks. By challenging the exclusion of non-human beings from agency considerations and emphasizing their interactions with human actors in shaping uncertainty and the existence of objects, Umbrello's (2018) paper investigated the necessary reworking of Marxism and the derived theory of communism. The researcher criticized the binary opposition of action, which is characterized by creativity and a future-oriented approach, and behavior, which is algorithmic and rooted in the past. By disregarding human entities as actors and

focusing solely on capitalist individuals rather than the proletariat, the researcher argued that this opposition fails to capture the inherent coexistence or “haunting” of these elements, resulting in extreme ambiguity. Instead of treating these antagonisms as separate entities, the researcher suggested synthesizing them into a cohesive phrase. Uncertainty serves as the foundation for all contrasts, oppositions, and the basic existence of any entity. It is in the interaction of the past and future within the present that solidarity resides, not only in either the past or the future. Furthermore, the author asserts that inherent ambiguity should not be equated with indeterminacy. To illustrate this concept, the researcher employed the example of quantum behavior, clarifying that the superposition of states does not imply their fusion. Despite interacting with one another, these states maintain distinctive boundaries, albeit challenging to precisely define. The “uncertainty” of the superposition signifies the “accuracy” of its physical description. The researcher argues that this inherent quality exists in all objects, extending beyond humans and quantum phenomena, yet Marx confines it to the concept of “species being.” Addressing potential accusations of anthropomorphism, the author contends that such charges primarily stem from implicit anthropomorphic assumptions. In order for Marxism to thrive as an ideology and function as intended, it is imperative to incorporate non-human beings within its framework.

Spiritual forces were even seen to act as non-human agents playing a significant role in religious narratives and interactions, but are often overlooked due to the emphasis on human agency in modern paradigms. In Meyer’s (2022) study called “Agency and the Critical Study of Religion,” it was asserted that the study of religion faces challenges in the complexities of modern issues, which often limit the scope and plausibility of scholarly research. The superiority of the modern, secular human vision

is still largely uncontested, despite criticism of secular and modern ideas in recent decades. This devotion to contemporary, secular paradigms limits the study of religion, a field that includes stories about supernatural powers and non-human entities. An evaluation of European trends throughout history suggests that the development of contemporary political and social frameworks necessitated a diminishing emphasis on non-human action, which underscores the central role of human agency in shaping society. Nevertheless, this human-centric focus restricts the study of religion, which inherently includes narratives involving interactions with non-human entities and transcending human perspectives. Scholars are encouraged to explore non-modern conceptual frameworks that offer alternative avenues for theoretical inquiry, in order to address this dilemma and restore a critical examination of religion in the twenty-first century. By embracing non-modern perspectives and expanding beyond the limitations of contemporary notions of agency, researchers can uncover new dimensions and insights in the study of religion. Adopting a non-modern conceptual framework can shed light on previously overlooked aspects of religious narratives, rejuvenating scholarly discourse and fostering a deeper understanding of the complex interaction between humans, non-human entities, and spiritual realms in the modern world.

Withal, in the field of sustainable wine production, metrics were also found to possess agency and were considered material and ontological actors in the context of production, influencing user interactions and activities. Rosin et al.'s (2017) study titled "From Compliance to Co-production: Emergent Forms of Agency in Sustainable Wine Production in New Zealand," investigated the concept of non-human agency by examining the growing role of metrics in governing sustainability in New Zealand's primary sector. Anchoring on earlier studies that examined the influence of verified

best practices on the attitude and actions of producers and processors, the researchers contend that metrics possess agency in and of themselves. Resulting in unanticipated and uncontrollable changes, they considered how measurements actively influence social networks of production. Rosin et al.'s (2017) study evaluated the indicators utilized in the Wine Industry Sustainability Engine, which serves as a "learning" tool illustrating transition management. Their study found that metrics are already perceived as active participants in users' interactions with and utilization of the tool, as indicated by user evaluations of the pilot program. While the aim of benchmarking is to promote specific behaviors and ethics, the metrics of this tool are also employed in production to ensure compliance with regulations, facilitate discussions about complex relationships and practices, and provide self-evaluation data. Based on these observations, the researchers argued that metrics are tangible and non-human entities that exhibit context-specific variations in their manifestations. The findings of Rosin et al.'s (2017) study shed light on the objectives and limitations of metrics and carry broader implications for the use of transition management.

Besides, established mental disorders were conceptualized as exerting causal influence on members' experiences and activities within the organizational milieu, which underlines the dynamic interconnection between social processes and the emergence of mental disorders as meaningful objects that influence interactions and practices within the social ambits. Weinberg's (1997) study, called "The Social Construction of Non-Human Agency: The Case of Mental Disorder," emphasizes that constructionist studies manifest the profound relevance of social processes to the emergence and assessment of mental disorders in various organizational settings. Notwithstanding, there is a lack of discussion in the constructionist literature about the potential causal effects that mental diseases may have on members' experiences and

behaviors when they are identified as significant objects of discourse and practice. Weinberg (1997) employed the notion of social issues work in his study to describe the real-world dynamics by which participants give life to the category items they think make up their worlds. The exploration of social issues not only involves the identification of tangible elements within the discourse of social problems, but also acknowledges these elements as non-human actors capable of exerting causal influence. Consequently, individuals engage in interactions with these entities that mirror their interactions with each other, thereby continuously shaping local affairs. Weinberg's (1997) study primarily focuses on the social construction of mental illnesses as non-human agents with causal influence, serving as a case study within a broader context. The diagnosis and evaluation of mental health problems within organizational settings are heavily influenced by social dynamics, as demonstrated by Weinberg's (1997) research on mental disorders. Contrariwise, the influence of mental illnesses on an individual's emotions and actions remains unclear. Drawing from the study of social problems, Weinberg (1997) elucidates how individuals endow category objects with agency by attributing to them non-human actors capable of exerting causal influence. Weinberg's (1997) study investigated a specific manifestation of this prevalent phenomenon.

These various non-human agencies reviewed in this section demonstrated their influence on other non-human and even on human agencies. Notwithstanding, proponents of Structuration Theory (Giddens, 1984) do acknowledge that objects can function as both resources and constraints. Nevertheless, they prioritize human agency as the starting point, considering the knowledgeable and capable actor as the source of all forms of agency. This analytical approach, shared by ethnomethodologists and conversation analysts, leads to a neglect of the actual

actions performed by human-created artifacts in the world. By reducing objects to mere resources and constraints, their contributions are frequently overlooked and fail to receive proper recognition.

The Ventriloquism of Various Non-Human Agencies

Cooren et al.'s (2021) concept of ventriloquism elucidates the manner in which individuals, specifically human agents, lend their voices to other entities such as policies, missions, facts, and people. These entities can be seen as dynamically engaging in routine communicative practices. Moreover, Cooren (2021) posits that different forms of agency can be invoked or mobilized within a particular interaction or dialogue. This assertion regarding the ventriloquism of diverse agencies is explored through an analysis of various empirical studies, which are discussed in the succeeding narrations.

The studies dissected here demonstrate that various agencies, both human and non-human, can be ventriloquized to contribute to organizational dynamics. Employing Cooren's (2021) ventriloquial analysis approach, such agencies as visions, graphic images, organizations, digital platforms like Tiktok, documents like diplomatic agreements and researches, concrete structures like statues and monuments, AI speaking agents like Siri and Alexa, films, recorded voices, hotel guest service, and even everyday service are given voices to speak about and act on something on behalf of someone or something, playing a significant role in organizational accomplishment.

In their study titled "Speaking About a Vision, Talking in the Name of So Much More: A Methodological Framework for Ventriloquial Analyses in Organization Studies," Cooren et al. (2018) examined how organizations have been seen as stable

and unchanging because they have solid buildings, well-known names, and clear goals. They introduced the Communicative Constitution of Organization (CCO) view, which focuses on how communication helps appear and evolve as living processes. This view asks researchers to study how conversations and texts shape organizational events and structures over time. To explain this concept, the researchers used the concept of ventriloquism, showing how different voices, documents, and ideas come alive and influence one another through interactions. It also includes context. However, ventriloquism lacked a clear way to analyze these complex exchanges. To address this gap, Cooren et al (2020) presented a simple four-step methodological framework for ventriloquial analysis. This framework uses employee discussions about visions and strategic statements as core examples. It guides scholars to identify ventriloquial elements, organize them into coherent categories, and present their effects on how organizations communicate and decide. The authors also gave detailed examples applying these steps in real organizational settings. Introducing this practical tool, Cooren et al. (2020) offer a valuable resource for organizational communication scholars. It helps them carry out systematic studies of how language, dialogue, and non-human artifacts shape the way organizations form, operate, and change.

The ventriloquism effect also occurs in the agency of virtual reality when the loudspeaker's position is used. In 2023, Kawai and Muto ran a study called "Investigation into Ventriloquism Effect Considering Indication of the Loudspeaker Position" to explore how this sound illusion changes when people know where the speaker is located. Their goal was to study an audio and visual effect known as the ventriloquism effect, which takes place when listeners believe that a sound is coming from a visible image, even though the actual sound source sits in a different spot. Earlier work on this topic did not tell participants where the sounds was coming from,

and it only measured the illusion in the dark. Kawai and Muto (2023) suggested a new approach that uses a single loudspeaker shown as a 3D scanned model inside a virtual reality environment. To measure how strong the ventriloquism effect became, the researchers used something called the angular discrimination threshold. This threshold shows the difference in perceived angle between where the sound actually comes from and where the image appears to be. The team compared their results, where the loudspeaker's position was clear to participants, with previous results where the position was hidden. They found that making the speaker's location known makes the ventriloquism effect stronger and more reliable.

Besides, sponsored content acts like ventriloquism, shaping how people see an organization. Trust, credibility, and online proof greatly affect how people judge a restaurant's overall quality. In the study conducted by Edor et al. (2023) titled "Exploring the Role of Ventriloquism in Warranting Organizational Perceptions," sponsored content was examined from the perspective of warranting theory. Organizations frequently engage in activities to influence and alter others' perceptions of them. Edor et al. (2023) focused exclusively on companies' usage of sponsored material and promotions, allowing them to investigate a previously undiscovered part of warranting theory. The experiment involved exposing 91 college-aged people to an online tweet about a restaurant written by either the organization itself (first part), an unrelated individual (third party), or an individual who indicated that their post was an advertisement sponsored by the organization (external ventriloquism). The findings of the study demonstrate a partial mediation effect, in which both the claimant's trustworthiness and the warranting value of the claim influenced participants' views of restaurant quality. There was no difference in warranting value between the message

posters. These findings are examined in terms of warranting theory and their implications for practitioners.

The metaphor of ventriloquism, when viewed as a performance act, provides valuable insights into how organizations are constructed through communication, particularly focusing on the meticulous preparations and rehearsals involved in shaping organizational presentations and influencing future practices. In their study titled "Preparing the Show: Organizational Ventriloquism as Autocommunication," Christensen and Christensen (2022) underlined the concept that communication plays a constitutive role in organizations, particularly through the ventriloquial perspective, which suggests that organizations become present when human and non-human agents speak on their behalf. While this perspective has mostly been employed as an analytical technique for studying talks, understanding ventriloquism as a specific type of performance act provides further insights into how organizations are built through communication. Ventriloquial performances are frequently rigorously planned and rehearsed, particularly when they are intended to be performed in front of an audience. In this conceptual study of Christensen and Christensen (2022), they built on previous research on organizational ventriloquism by looking at how these preparations affect organizations. To accomplish so, they employed the concept of autocommunication, which refers to communication in which collectives are powered by their own constructions. The researchers specifically concentrated on the behind-the-scenes circumstances where official presentations of organizations are considered and developed. In these situations, corporate ventriloquists carefully consider the appropriateness of specific figures and explore how crucial stakeholders would view these organizational presentations. Through the definition of this preparation as autocommunicative ventriloquism, Christensen and Christensen (2022) investigated

how the conjured figures in such contexts can affect organizations and determine their future activities.

Networked ventriloquism on Yiddish TikTok was explored as how the platform facilitates dissociation and reconfiguration of users' bodies and voices, delving into how the platform contributes to language, cultural heritage, and activism, ultimately serving as an algorithmic platform for interconnectedness between human and non-human voices. In Ramati and Abeliovich's (2022) research, which delved into the phenomenon of "Network Ventriloquism" on Yiddish TikTok, the intricate relationship between body and voice within the TikTok platform was investigated. The study proposed that TikTok serves as a medium for networked ventriloquism, in which users' bodies and speech are dissociated and reconfigured using audiovisual technology. Through the utilization of Yiddish as a case study, the researchers investigated how TikTok's qualities provide a framework for language, cultural heritage, and activism. They looked to YiddishToks as examples of TikTokers demonstrating technolinguistic and ventiloquistic interconnectivity, establishing linkages with previous generations. YiddishTokers combines different chronological and spatial dimensions, providing new contexts for Yiddish media history. TikTok's algorithm plays an important part in recreating Yiddish's past, acting as an audible, transparent director steering the network backstage. TikTok is essentially an algorithmic framework for networked ventriloquism, allowing for the interaction of human and non-human voices.

Double ventriloquism was also seen to be engaged in to indicate the narrative and resolution of historical wrongdoings, ultimately marginalizing subaltern voices, also providing opportunities for the colonized to challenge official narratives and demand justice. In his paper titled "The Negotiated Apology: 'Double Ventriloquism' in Addressing Historical Wrongs," Bentley (2022) investigated two diplomatic

agreements between colonizing and post-colonial states concerning grave historical injustices. Specifically, he examined the 2021 Germany-Namibia “Joint Declaration,” addressing Germany’s colonial history, and the 2015 Japan-South Korea “Joint Press Occasion,” addressing Japan’s use of “comfort women” during the imperial era. These accords represent an increasing trend in which states participate in open negotiations, coordination, and the sharing of apologies in response to past wrongdoings. Through the reevaluation of Gayatri Spivak’s question, “Can the subaltern speak?”, Bentley (2022) demonstrated how the colonized subject is spoken for not only by the colonizer but also by indigenous elites and Western intellectuals. He identified a similar process occurring within these agreements, referred to as “double ventriloquism.” Within this framework, both the former colonizing state and the post-colonial government collude to speak on behalf of the colonized, dictating the narrative of the wrongdoing, determining corrective measures, and concluding that the matter is resolved. This collusion effectively marginalizes subaltern voices, making the state the sole mediator in the transitional justice system. Nonetheless, although Spivak views the subaltern’s ability to speak with pessimism, Bentley’s (2022) study shows that apologies accidentally offer possibilities for the colonized to undermine official narratives in public and reaffirm their demands for justice.

Additionally, monuments were seen to shape political imagination while highlighting the dangers of downplaying racist commemoration for liberal pluralism or national unity. In Hooker’s (2024) study titled “Statues Made of Sugar: Martí, Monuments, and Hemispheric Ventriloquism, he proposed that monuments have the ability to articulate ideas and shape the political imagination of citizens. Hooker (2024) claimed that Cuban philosopher José Martí’s connection with Confederate solidarities stems from hemispheric ventriloquism, citing his article on Confederate memory.

Martí's use of hemispheric ventriloquism was motivated by three factors: 1) concerns about US imperial expansion, 2) a need to counter critiques labeling Latin American republics as inherently unstable post-independence, and 3) his desire for Cuban national unity after independence. Martí uses hemispheric ventriloquism to demonstrate the serious dangers of ignoring racist history in the name of liberal pluralism or broader collective national unity.

Likewise, AI voice assistants such as Siri and Alexa demonstrate algorithmic ventriloquism by using machine-learning algorithms to craft humanlike personalities. These systems blur lines between physical and virtual spaces, human and non-human agents, and spoken speech versus written text. The effects span cultural norms, economic models, philosophical questions, and sociolinguistic practices. In his 2024 study "Algorithmic Ventriloquism: The Contested State of Voice in AI Speech Generators," Ramati explored how text-to-speech generators intertwine human and machine voices. He examined the human roots of synthetic speech and the modification of voice using machine-learning algorithms. His study contends that AI-speaking agents such as Siri, Alexa, and many TTS applications, including TikTok, participate in algorithmic ventriloquism. AI speech technologies manipulate professional voiceover artists' voices to create personalities that embody a web of interconnected tensions between the physical and the virtual, the specific and the general, the human and the non-human, and speech and writing. The idea of algorithmic ventriloquism provides an analytical framework for connecting the TTS system's technical and vocal operations to their cultural, economic, philosophical, and sociolinguistic ramifications.

Paid puppeteering on digital platforms like Cameo was also discovered, where celebrities monetize their public persona through personalized shout-out videos,

reshaping the power dynamic of fan-celebrity relationships and highlighting the emergence of new income streams amid the pandemic through digital ventriloquism. Drenten and Psarras (2021), in their study titled “Digital Ventriloquism and Celebrity Access: Cameo and The Emergence of Paid Puppeteering on Digital Platforms,” explicated that Cameo is part of a growing set of new media platforms trending towards direct routes for monetizing fame. It allows fans to book personalized shout-out videos and provides celebrities – celestoids and reality stars in particular – access to new modes of income, which became increasingly important amid the pandemic. Drenten and Psarras’ (2021) study investigated how the direct monetization of the fan-celebrity relationships is altering the power dynamics of these parasocial relationships. Utilizing digital ventriloquism as an analytical lens to study reality stars (e.g., Real Housewives) on Cameo, their study introduced the concept of “paid puppeteering” on digital platforms, which is defined as a type of digital ventriloquism in which a celebrity’s public persona is manipulated and incentivized through financial means on a paid digital platform to create the illusion of close parasocial connections with fans. Paid puppeteering reinforces celebrities as gig workers, whereas Cameo limits fan access to superstars – for a cost.

Distant-voice ventriloquism was also investigated as Edgar Allan Poe masterfully incorporated ventriloquial techniques into his narratives, exploring the unsettling connections between voice and identity, power, and death, shaping his tales across various genres while manipulating sound to create effects that engage the audience’s imagination. Sweeney’s (2021) qualitative study called “Echoes of Ventriloquism in Poe’s Tales” focused on the profound influence of distant-voice ventriloquism on Edgar Allan Poe’s writings. The study evaluated how this popular form of entertainment during the 1830s and 40s, which involved performers engaging

in conversations with invisible speakers or imitating the sounds of unseen animals and objects, shaped the narratives crafted by Poe. Sweeney (2021) established a strong correlation between ventriloquial techniques and effects in Poe's storytelling by examining Poe's exposure to ventriloquism through literary works, potential attendance at performances, and frequent references to specific performers. Through an analysis of over a dozen of Poe's tales, particularly "*The Murders in the Rue Morgue*" and "*The Fall of the House of Usher*," Sweeney (2021) demonstrated how ventriloquism influenced Poe's writing style and thematic concerns. Throughout these stories, Poe skillfully used techniques familiar to his antebellum audience, such as breath control, the use of various vocal apparatuses to produce distinct tones, the use of mechanical devices to aid in speech, the ability to speak without visible lip movement, the orchestration of various noises, and the placement of sounds in concealed or confined spaces. Through the use of these strategies, Poe steered readers to the desired outcome. Ventriloquism also helped shape Poe's narratives in a variety of genres, including horror, detective fiction, hoaxes, and humor. It enabled him to blend the process of creating an effect with sounds into a story's plot, narration, picture, or theme. In addition, ventriloquism allowed him to investigate disturbing linkages between the voice and ideas like identity, imposture, masculine authority, and death. Conversely, Poe went beyond mere allusions to distant-voice ventriloquism, depicting noises that readers never physically heard. Each story alluded to the idea that, regardless of the apparent provenance of a sound, its ultimate source was in the audience's imagination.

In a related study, Gilovich-Wave (2021), titled "The Camera Chooses the Star: Trans-medial Ventriloquism in Punchdrunk's *The Drowned Man*," argued that despite its predominantly non-verbal nature, Punchdrunk's 2013 production of "*The Drowned*

Man” employed a ventriloquist paradigm to frame its engagement with form – specifically, the physical body as a medium of performance. “*The Drowned Man*” reimagines the multi-medial potential of immersive theater by delving into the relationship between voice and shape, drawing on ventriloquism’s cinematic and theatrical heritage. The production invites spectators to consider how much they, like the staged dummy, are surreptitiously controlled, eventually altering form to promote a self-reflexive discourse about voices, bodies, and performances. As a consequence, the sensation created is frequently creepy, disturbing, confusing, and fascinating, much like the art of ventriloquism itself.

Archival ventriloquism was also introduced, where audiovisual appropriation allows the appropriationist to “speak through” recorder subjects like Barack Obama, creating “technovocalic bodies” that can neither reveal nor obscure their altered voice-body relationship, underscoring the ethical implications and potential for exploitation in this practice. Baron’s (2021) study titled “Ventriloquizing Obama, or, the Ethics of Archival Ventriloquism” placed a specific emphasis on the contemporary practice of audiovisual appropriation, enabling the appropriationist to “speak through” the voice and body of a recorded subject through an act of “archival ventriloquism.” As recorded subjects become, to some extent, ventriloquist dummies, they lose agency over their own voices and are “spoken through.” As a consequence, new “technovocalic bodies” emerge, imagined bodies inextricably linked to the recorded subjects’ actual bodies. On the contrary, some technovocalic bodies overtly state their technovocality, whereas others do not. When media technologies are used to obscure the shift in the relationship between voice and body, both the recorded subject and the viewer are subjected to a sort of media ventriloquism that smacks of exploitation. Throughout the study, Baron (2021) investigated several video works that rely on the reuse of

recordings depicting former US President Barack Obama, underlining the critical, comic, and abusive potential inherent in this type of media ventriloquism.

Exploring beyond archival ventriloquism, digital ventriloquism is a new technique to make sound seem to come from everyday objects instead of smart speakers. It offers directionality and intelligibility without changing any objects or the environment. In their 2020 study “Digital Ventriloquism: Giving Voice to Everyday Objects,” Iravantchi et al. looked at how common smart speakers with voice assistants have become. They found that no matter where a speaker sits, and regardless of whether the voice matches the room’s context or location, the sound always comes from the device itself. To fix this, the researchers created digital ventriloquism, which lets smart speakers send sound so it appears to come from ordinary items, making objects seem to speak. This works without modifying the items or surroundings. They used a highly directional pan-tilt ultrasonic array to produce an inaudible, modulated 40 kHz ultrasonic signal. When this beam hits a surface, it demodulates into normal, audible speech through acoustic parametric interaction. Their work shows potential for developing more immersive and context-aware audio experiences in cultural, public, commercial, social, and everyday digital environments worldwide.

Adding to that, academic ventriloquism highlights the difficulty of including participants fairly while keeping their identities safe in research. It shows how researchers can dominate the narratives and risk treating people as tokens or misrepresenting them. In their 2021 study “Academic Ventriloquism,” Silverio et al. examined this tight balance between inviting participants into studies, telling their stories in papers, and protecting their privacy. They warn that as researchers push for more participant voices, they may unknowingly harm confidentiality. Similarly, methods that aim to be inclusive can lead to participants feeling that their experiences

were not accurately portrayed. The authors compared this situation to walking a fine line: advocating for participants while maintaining the power to shape study design and interpretation. To tackle these ethical and practical problems, the team analyzed real examples of how participants took part in published health and social science research. Their review shows that weak research practices can create tokenism or power imbalances, giving researchers more say than participants. This work calls for methods that respect contributions and protect privacy. It demands clear, strong guidelines to build research relationships. Silverio et al.'s (2021) study developed the concept of "academic ventriloquism," which uses the metaphor of ventriloquists "throwing" their voices. This notion refers to the tendency for participant voices to be eclipsed or ignored in published research, or to compete for prominence. The researchers evaluated the interconnectedness of inclusion, representation, and anonymity, as well as the issues that come with balancing these principles. Despite advancements in the conduct of research "with" rather than "on" participants, the researcher remains primarily responsible for writing up the academic study. As a consequence, researchers must learn to "throw" their voice in order to accurately portray the voices of their subjects. Nonetheless, the study identified potential issues with this approach and made recommendations to improve the inclusion and correct depiction of participants in written research. The purpose was not only to amplify and make participant voices heard, but also to authentically chronicle them as a true reflection of the people from whom they came.

Utilizing ventriloquial analysis, the communicative constitution of hospitality organizations was also investigated, highlighting how guest service is embodied and expressed through various entities, including human beings, organizational structures, and technological agents, shaping interactions and experiences within the hospitality

industry. In her study titled “The Communicative Constitution of Hospitality Organization: A Ventriloquial Analysis of Guest Service,” Manaluz-Torres (2019) developed a theory of guest service that is rooted in a communicative constitutive comprehension of hospitality organizations, utilizing Cooren’s (2008) ventriloquial analysis approach. Manaluz-Torres (2019) defined guest service as the manifestation, realization, presentation, and embodiment of numerous elements, such as humans, intangible or tangible forms, organizational structures, and technology agents. Additionally, communicating involves giving these creatures a voice, enabling them to directly act and speak for themselves through front-line services. Front-line employees’ devotion and enthusiasm are visible in the way they speak, act, perform, and conduct themselves, making them embody these entities. As a result, a variety of agents and figures are invoked, summoned, and evoked during their encounters.

Cooren’s (2006) conceptualizations of non-human agency and ventriloquism are so intertwined that they are able to surface a reality in communication research that non-human entities, when given voices (ventriloquized) and animated, exert a considerable amount of influence on other agencies, especially on human agents. The influence these non-human entities exert on human agencies contributes to how organizations are structured, operate, and accomplish their goals and objectives.

The majority of the empirical investigations mentioned above are anchored on Cooren’s (2006) agency paradigm. Employing mostly Speech Act Analysis, Actor Network Theory, and Ventriloquial Analysis Approaches, multifarious forms of agencies, including figures and vents, were analyzed to surface a reality that these agents truly have influences on and contribute to organizational dynamics and accomplishment as they participate in many communicative practices that shape and define organizations, as emphasized by the concept of CCO (Communication as

Constitutive of Organization) under the Montreal School of Organizational Communication.

While current research gives useful insights into the impact or influence of many types of non-human agents on other entities, ranging from institutional work and residential development to human behavior, there are still gaps to fill. Specifically, there has been little research on the authority and effect of non-human agents, such as regulatory issuances and directives, in influencing people's behavior and fostering compliance with solid waste management standards. Further research is required to determine how non-human agents create organizational processes, influence human behavior, and contribute to the success or failure of solid waste management projects. Additionally, further study is required to investigate the effects of regulatory organizations' communication strategies and the efficiency of their enforcement mechanisms in encouraging sustainable waste management practices.

The muted voices were the non-human agents representing the regulatory bodies in solid waste management, and the authority of these non-human agents that compels the people to act. Thus, this study attempts to give voice to or to unmute the communication knowledge that will be derived from the qualitative content analysis of the issuances and directives handed down by solid waste management regulatory bodies to the people in the field.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Research Framework

This study was undertaken within the Montreal School of Organizational Communication which theorizes Communication as Constitutive of Organization (CCO) (Saludadez, 2021). From the point of view of this school of thought, organization, and communication are seen as equivalent. That is, the organization can be seen in communication. Further, the Montreal School of Organizational Communication posits that organization and communication are inseparable. According to their perspective, communication is not just a tool used within an organization but is actually what shapes and defines the organization itself. In other words, the organization is seen as something that emerges from communication (Saludadez, 2021).

Within the CCO, Cooren, et al.'s (2006) Non-Human Agency Framework attempts to explain 'how one can act from a distance' or 'teleact'. Teleaction is representation, which is the act of making present or presentifying something or someone in communicative practices. Teleaction can happen in a manner that non-humans represent other entities. In the present study, the non-human agents in the form of notices, memorandum circulars, executive orders, and certifications perform teleacting or acting from a distance as they represent the regulatory body they come from.

Indeed, we live in a world full of interactions, but through representation by language, memory, and technology, entities from the past or from a remotely located

area can teleact and make a difference in any given situationality (Cooren, 2006). In the context of solid waste management, these non-human agents in this study do teleacting and are making a difference on behalf of the regulatory body they are representing from a remotely located area.

Further, the framework 'views interactions as streams, flows, or processes' and assumes that the 'ultimate origin of what is happening in a given interaction' is not the participants and their actions/moves 'precisely because these participants are themselves moved or acted upon by specific reasons that they come to stage (or not) in their discussions' (Cooren, 2010). In a chain of agencies, Cooren's (2010) Non-Human Agency Framework assumes that action is shared between human and non-human agents configured upstream and downstream. Animate interlocutors such as principles, values, and policies and what the agents 'make represent or represent in their interactions' are the upstream agents. Downstream agents point out to the signs that interlocutors produce 'whether under the form of texts, gestures, kinesic expressions, and what they do or make interlocutors do' (Cooren, 2006). In this present study, the upstream agent that can be considered is the environmental legislation governing solid waste management practices in the country, the Republic Act 9003 or the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. This legislation makes the regulatory bodies represent them through the non-human agents they issue to the field. These non-human agents like notices, memorandum circulars, executive orders, and certifications are the downstream agents that the regulatory bodies produce to represent them and make a difference from a distance. These downstream agents play a crucial role in influencing the actions or responses of the participants.

Communication, within the Non-human Agency Framework, is visualized as 'not only a matter of people speaking or writing to each other, but that other things are

continuously inviting and expressing themselves in day-to-day interactions” (Cooren, 2011). These “other things” pointed out by Cooren (2011) are agents and being an agent entails being able to act or speak ‘on behalf (or in the name) of principal.’ Principal, in the context of narrative economy, refers to a collection entity such as a group, organization, or society (Cooren, 2011). Building on this concept, the term "agents" pertains to entities possessing the ability to undertake actions or express themselves with the authority to act on behalf of a principal. Being recognized as an agent entails the capacity to represent or advocate for someone or something. Within the framework of the narrative economy, the notion of a "principal" refers to a collective entity, typically a group, organization, or society. Fundamentally, agents operating within this structure-function as representatives or spokespersons, acting on behalf of a larger collective entity, and embodying the potential to influence or implement changes in support of that principal. This concept emphasizes the interconnectedness and dynamic relationships present in narratives, where individuals or entities assume the role of agents, wielding the power to articulate and carry out actions that align with the interests or objectives of the overarching principal. Here, the non-human agents like notices, memorandum circulars, executive orders, and certifications act or speak on behalf of the principal – the MENRO – and possess the potential to influence or execute actions in support of these principals.

In terms of organizational structure and framework, from the point of view of the Montreal School, the structure is a configuration of agents. Also, from the viewpoint of this school of thought, communication implies not only an agent and a recipient but also that an agent is always acting on behalf of, in the name of, or for someone or something else (that is, a principal) (Saludadez, 2021). To elaborate on this concept, for Montreal School, organizational structure is seen as a configuration of individuals

or entities present within the organization. In this context, communication is not just a simple exchange between an agent and a recipient. Instead, it involves agents acting on behalf of, or representing, other people or things. This means that when someone communicates, they are often doing so with the intent of representing the interests, views, or directives of others or the organization itself. This thought is supported by Cooren's (2015) ventriloquism which he defines as denoting "actions through which someone or something makes someone or something else say or do things".

Also, according to Cooren (2010), ventriloquism assumes that 'various forms of agency can be invoked or mobilized in a given interaction or dialogue'. Cooren's ventriloquial approach extends this idea by defining ventriloquism in organizational communication as actions where one entity makes another say or do something. Cooren's approach suggests that in any interaction or dialogue, multiple forms of agency (people, ideas, norms, legislations, etc.) can be invoked or mobilized. Essentially, individuals in an organization often speak or act not just for themselves but as representatives or voices for other entities, such as organizational values, policies, or other people. Hence, the Montreal School emphasizes that agents communicate on behalf of others, shaping the organization while Cooren's ventriloquial approach explains these dynamics occur in the manner that agents or entities in an organization give voice (ventriloquizes) and are given voices (ventriloquized), with these various forms of agency influencing what is said and done in organizational interactions, Hence, both perspectives focus on the multifaceted nature of communication in organizations, where individuals often act as conduits for broader organizational forces and influences.

Additionally, also consistent with its view of communication as constitutive of organization, in terms of organizational culture, the Montreal School would see it not

as what an organization has or what an organization is, but as cultures in interaction (Saludadez, 2021). This means that the Montreal School views organizational culture not as a static attribute or identity of the organization but as a dynamic process of cultures interacting. In this view, organizational culture is continually created and recreated through the interactions and communications of its members. As Cooren's (2015) ventriloquism displays the manner in which people give voice to other beings such as policies, missions, facts, persons, etc. that can then be deemed as participants in communicative praxis (Cooren, Matte, Benoit-Barné, & Brummans, 2013; Cooren & Sandler, 2014), this conceptualization of the Montreal School is complemented by Cooren's (2016) ventriloquism by describing how people within an organization give voice to various elements such as policies, missions, facts, and other individuals. These elements then become active participants in the communication processes within the organization, thereby creating and recreating organizational culture. Generally, both perspectives emphasize that organizational reality is constantly shaped through dynamic interactions and communication, with various voices and elements influencing and participating in this ongoing process.

The organization that is represented by a non-human agent to be analyzed in this study falls under the Montreal School of Organizational Communication – the MENRO. In this organization, communication is inseparable and that is not just a device used in these organizations but it is what actually molds and defines them. The Montreal School's emphasis on communication as the foundation of organizational existence aligns with the notion that regulatory bodies communicate their directives through various non-human agents such as compliance certificate, executive orders, and memorandum circulars. The concept of an "authorized agent" as proposed by the Montreal School further contributes to understanding the authority of non-human

agents. In the regulatory context, these non-human agents, representing the regulatory bodies, act on behalf of or in the name of a higher authority. In essence, the regulatory issuances are embedded with serve as authorized agents that embody the authority and intentions of the regulatory bodies. In the context of Cooren's (2015) ventriloquism, these agents - both human and non-humans, embedded in the issuances of regulatory organizations that presentify them are ventriloquized (given voices to speak and act) by the principal (which can be a principle, policy, regulation, or legislation).

This study examines the subtle dynamics of non-human agents that are actively involved in communication practices and are deeply interwoven into the functioning of regulatory bodies. It falls under the category of communication research. Through a process called teleaction, these non-human agents enable the presence or representation of someone or something in communication encounters. These non-human entities serve as channels via which the wishes and expressions of the represented entities are transmitted, acting as messengers for the entities they represent through the use of teleaction. These non-human agents do more than only act as messengers; they also execute duties and fulfill obligations as directed by the entities they represent. Through their acts, they reflect the goals and intents of the entities they represent, carrying out their duties and participating in activities that lead to the intended results. By carrying out assigned duties, these non-human agents become essential elements in the communication processes; they not only send signals but also actively engage in activities that mirror the desires and instructions of the entities they represent.

This study mainly utilized the Ventriloquial Analysis Approach advanced by Cooren in 2021 in his research called, "Speaking About Vision, Talking in The Name

of So Much More: A Methodological Framework for Ventriloquial Analyses in Organization Studies. In this paper of Cooren's, et al. (2021), they defined ventriloquism as the manner the people give voice to other beings - policies, missions, facts, persons, etc. - that can then be deemed as participating in an interaction (Cooren, Matte, Benoit-Barné, & Brummans, 2013; Cooren & Sandler, 2014). In their definition, Cooren, et al. (2021) emphasized that humans act both ventriloquists and dummies, and organizations are talked into existence through this oscillating dynamic: they make things and people speak to achieve their goals, as much as these things and people make them speak through what they say and do. In this concept, in the performance of ventriloquism, the humans who give voice to other beings are the personnel of the MENRO – the head of office, and his team who prepare the certificate, who conduct the inspection or validation, who approves and releases the document.

As Cooren, et al. (2021) also assumes that various forms of agencies – human and non-human – can be invoked or mobilized (made to say or do something) in a given communication practice, here, it is the certificate, a non-human agent, is that “other being” that is ventriloquized or given a voice by the MENRO personnel to say or do something.

According Cooren, et al. (2021), in the artistic performance of ventriloquism, ventriloquists call themselves ‘vents’ and their puppets ‘figures’. A vent makes someone or something do or say something, it animates a dummy to speak; in the same way as a principle that matters to us (such as equality) leads us to speak up in situations of perceived inequity. A figure, in contrast, is being made to do or say something by someone or something else; similarly, to a rule that is made to say something when pointing out someone’s wrongful behavior.

Research Questions

In consideration of the theoretical framework explicated above, this study aimed to investigate the authority of non-human agents used by regulatory bodies in solid waste management. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. *What figures appeared in the solid waste management compliance certificate that ventriloquized its authority?*
2. *What does the compliance certificate perform in solid waste management?*

CHAPTER IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The theory advanced by the Montreal School of Organization, which is communication as constitutive of organization is greatly intertwined with Cooren's (2015) ventriloquism, which is the main research methodology utilized in this present study. In the realm of organizational processes, consistent with its assumption that communication constitutes organization, the Montreal School views the organizing process as a co-orientation of agents or actors with respective worldviews; by 'respective worldviews' we mean differences of perspectives that are occurring in language that have conversational and textual dimensions, making up or constituting a collectivity called the organization (Saludadez, 2021). According to this view, communication is not just a part of an organization but actually constitutes the organization itself. This process is seen as a co-orientation, where different agents or actors within the organization align their perspectives, even though these perspectives are different and expressed through conversations and written texts. These varying perspectives and interactions collectively form what we understand as the organization.

According to Cooren (2010), the ventriloquial approach assumes that 'various forms of agency can be invoked or mobilized in a given interaction or dialogue'. Cooren's (2010) ventriloquial analysis approach answers not only the question of what communicatively constitutes realities but likewise the question of how voices enter interactions. Cooren's (2010) ventriloquial analysis approach enables understanding

of the details of the materializations of visions by connecting concepts to specific people, things, and sources that talk vision into being with the use of ventriloquial dynamics. In the context of this present study, non-human agents present in issuances in the forms of notices, memorandum circulars, executive orders, and compliance certificates are mobilized to compel people to act in solid waste management.

As Cooren's (2010) ventriloquial analysis approach answers not only the question of what communicatively constitutes realities but likewise the question of how voices enter interactions, Cooren's (2010) ventriloquialism relates to this concept of CCO by exploring how different voices (or perspectives) or ventriloquized agents (agents that are given voices) enter into interactions within an organization. Ventriloquism seeks to understand not only what these voices are saying and how they shape realities within the organization but also how these voices interact and influence each other in communicative practices that form an organization.

Ventriloquism displays the manner in which someone or something gives voice to other beings such as policies, missions, facts, persons, etc. that can then be deemed as participants in communicative praxis (Cooren, Matte, Benoit-Barné, & Brummans, 2013; Cooren & Sandler, 2014). Here in this study, ventriloquism illustrates that people, who comprise the regulatory bodies in solid waste management, give voice to policies, missions, and objectives of the solid waste management program seen to be taking part in the communicative interactions with the people in the field. With this action, ventriloquism inquires the predominant lessening of communication to people interacting with one another and shows that interactions include additional elements of a situation that are voiced through what people say or do (Cooren, et al., 2010). Through the concept of ventriloquism, the actual communicative interactions of the people in the regulatory bodies and the

people in the field are lessened. Instead, these communicative interactions of these people involved in solid waste management include other elements which, in this study, are the issuances by the regulatory bodies in solid waste management. These 'other elements' or issuances that communicate policies, missions, and objectives are voiced by the people in the regulatory bodies to accomplish things on their behalf. Additionally, for Cooren (2015) ventriloquism is defined as denoting "actions through which someone or something makes someone or something else say or do things". Here, ventriloquism is illustrated in the fact that the notices, memorandum circulars, executive orders, and compliance certificates do actions that make people to do something in solid waste management.

Study Site

Regulatory bodies, as pointed out by Schmandt (1984), are government groups that create and enforce rules across different areas, such as science and technology. They set clear guidelines, check that people follow them, and make sure standards are met. This work helps confirm that processes and methods are safe and work well. In short, these organizations play a key role in keeping things in order, protecting public safety, and making sure people are responsible in areas where oversight supports the public good and helps knowledge and progress.

Adding to that, regulatory bodies, as Reddy (2017) emphasizes, make sure that rules and laws are followed properly. They enforce regulations in areas like environmental protection, public safety, and social welfare. Watching over organizations and penalizing those who break the law, they keep order and ensure people do what is right. These agencies protect society's interests by holding leaders

and companies accountable. Their work upholds the rules of law, makes processes clear, and supports long-term progress. In this way, regulatory bodies help society operate fairly and responsibly.

Governments worldwide, including the Philippines, passed laws to fight growing problems with improper solid waste management. They established regulatory bodies to create and run effective programs for proper waste handling. These agencies also enforce the relevant rules, laws, and policies. Their task aims to make sure communities follow guidelines and reduce pollution from waste. In the Philippine setting, some of these regulatory bodies that the government organized to fulfill the aforementioned tasks include the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, specifically its Environmental Management Bureau (DENR-EMB), and at the municipal level, the MENRO.

The DENR is responsible for conserving, managing, and sustainably utilizing the Philippines' diverse environment and natural resources. This includes overseeing forest and grazing lands, mineral reserves, and public domain lands. The Department also regulates all-natural resource activities to ensure that benefits are distributed fairly among current and future generations of Filipinos. Guided by specific objectives, the Department aims to ensure the availability and sustainable use of natural resources, enhance productivity to meet increasing demands, facilitate their contribution to national development, promote equal access across society, and protect important terrestrial and marine areas that are vital to the country's natural and cultural heritage (DENR, 2024).

One of the bureaus of the DENR that is mandated with the task of enforcing environmental protection laws is the EMB. The DENR-EMB works together with different stakeholders to enforce Republic Act 9003, also known as the Ecological

Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. This law aims to establish a well-organized and environmentally friendly solid waste management program that prioritizes public health and the environment. By encouraging proper segregation, collection, storage, treatment, and disposal of solid waste, the legislation promotes the use of eco-friendly waste products and ensures sustainable waste management practices (DENR-EMB, 2024).

At the local level, the Municipality of M created an office devoted particularly to enforcing RA 9003 and other environmental statutes in the country and to implementing programs, projects, and activities relevant to the enforcement of the said legislation. In 2020, the MENRO, alongside item positions for the office, was created so that the municipality's 10-Year Solid Waste Management Plan (2020-2029) would be approved by the National Solid Waste Management Commission (NSWMC). Consequently, in November 2021, the MENRO officially operated with its first and new department head, the researcher himself.

Part of the regulatory framework that the researcher, as the founding head of the MENRO, crafted is the enforcement of RA 9003 in the business establishments in the entire municipality. As provided under the Local Government Code of 1991 (RA 7160), the MENRO is mandated to implement programs and projects to address environmental and natural resources concerns of the municipality in coordination with various government and non-government institutions to access services and financial assistance for effective management and a dynamic environment and natural resources.

MENRO envisions an economically flourishing and self-governing municipality with a booming economy and industry vitalized by an ample and sustainable environment and natural resources fulfilled by the residents of the municipality,

collective care, concern, efforts, and actions for a maintainable, clean, and green environment.

Expected to come up with an effective and dynamic environment and natural resources management, MENRO has the mission to insistently endeavor for the most effectual and practical approaches to reforestation, ecological waste management, protection and preservation of flora and fauna, regulation and monitoring of mining and quarrying with the enforcement of all applicable environmental laws, and sustenance of all other ongoing initiatives to keep the environment and natural resources are in an excellent state with the utilization of all conjunct measures and fitting technologies.

The MENRO requires all the business firms in town applying for business permits to comply with the requirements of the office before they can be granted the MSWMCC. Fortunately, almost all business establishments applying for MSWMCC comply with all the requirements set forth by the MENRO, manifesting an authority over these entities.

Data Collection

This study used the MSWMCC, a regulatory document for solid waste management issued by the MENRO. To choose documents for analysis, the researcher set clear criteria to keep data strong and accurate. Primarily, the document had to match the research questions exactly. Next, the researcher checked who created the document and made sure its source has authority and credibility. This step helped confirm that the information was reliable. Then, the date of the document was reviewed to confirm it fits current waste management practices. The researcher also

looked at how much the document covered important topics, including the role of non-human agents in waste systems. Clear and exact wording in the document was required so the content could be easily understood. The study also made sure the document was easy to access and followed ethical rules. This final check guaranteed fair and legal document use. Following these steps, the researcher ensured that every document provided solid and trustworthy information. This thorough process helped analyze non-human agents in solid waste management with confidence and clarity. This method improved reliability and gave local managers clear insights about how rules and tools influence solid waste management decisions today.

Relevance to Research Questions. In this study, the researcher made sure that the document was related to the research topic, which in this case focuses on understanding how non-human agents, such as regulatory issuances, compel people to act on proper solid waste disposal. Important sources considered by the researcher include legislative texts, notices, policy guides, and reports published by regulatory bodies. Creswell and Creswell (2018) stressed that only texts clearly linked to the study objectives should be chosen. For instance, in the assessment of policy success, a document detailing specific enforcement actions, fines, and their practical consequences proves helpful for thorough analysis. Here, the MSWMCC is the document chosen by the researcher for the data analysis because it bears relevance to the research problem; it can provide rich answers to the research questions.

Authority and Credibility of the Source. The researcher chose to use a document from trusted and official sources. The sources considered by the researcher to be trusted and official include government agencies, well-known environmental organizations, and universities. For example, in this study, the MENRO is a valid government institution, a regulatory body in solid waste management, that can supply

useful, detailed records for analysis. Using a document from a valid institution ensures the data is reliable (Bowen, 2009). Bowen (2009) also highlighted that choosing papers from dependable organizations helps confirm that the data are accurate. He further stated that reports from official offices and recognized non-governmental groups offer clear information about how the policy works. In this study, the MSWMCC was chosen for data analysis because it is issued by the MENRO, a valid and recognized government regulatory body in solid waste management.

Timeframe. To make sure the study's results remained relevant and useful, the document chosen for review had to be recent and reflect current solid waste management practices, laws, and regulations. This approach is essential for properly examining the existing power and the role of non-human agents in waste management. Focusing on up-to-date papers, the research aimed at producing an analysis that matched ongoing changes in rules and enforcement. Creswell and Creswell (2018) stress that using current information is vital for understanding and interpreting events as they happen, which boosts the study's accuracy and trustworthiness. In this study, the researcher selected the latest MSWMCC available at the MENRO to ensure that the data matched the current legal, regulatory standards, and operational context while reflecting environmental conditions.

Scope and Coverage. The researcher, in this dissertation, checked that the selected material covered every key topic in solid waste management. This means that the document included clear information on enforcement methods, compliance rules, and penalties linked to certification processes. Flick (2018) says documents must cover all parts of the research topic to give a full understanding. For solid waste management, relevant documents include regulations, enforcement notices, compliance reports, and certifications. Together, these documents show how non-

human agents use their power to enforce solid waste management laws. Covering these areas lets the researcher analyze how well these agents work and how they perform in the regulatory system. Following Flick's (2018) ideas, the researcher chose the MSWMCC of the MENRO for analysis in this study because it has detailed data on how rules are enforced and what requirements must be complied with. The MSWMC helped the researcher see how non-human agents hold and use authority. It gave clear evidence on enforcement actions, compliance criteria, and penalties. This information guided the analysis of the agents' role and effectiveness in enforcing solid waste management. The researcher ensured the coverage of the MSWMCC met the dissertation's main objectives.

Clarity and Specificity. In this dissertation, having clear and specific details in the chosen document, the MSWMCC, is essential for strong analysis. When documents are straightforward and rich in detail, they create a solid base for finding significant results and insights. Yin (2018) notes that accurate, detailed information helps researchers understand and assess data well, ensuring that the results are strong and trustworthy. In contrast, documents that are vague or too broad do not provide enough depth or accuracy. This lack can slow down analysis and could lead to unclear or wrong conclusions. Therefore, choosing documents with precise, clearly defined content is vital to keep the study's results valid and dependable. This careful selection supports the overall quality of the research outcomes.

Accessibility and Ethical Considerations. Having legal access to research materials is important for keeping the research process honest and lawful. Researchers need to make sure that every document they use was collected legally and follows all copyright rules and usage limits. This means getting permits or licenses to avoid infringement problems (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). Here in this present

investigation, the researcher did not need to get permission or approval from any higher officials because he serves as the head of the MENRO and issues the MSWMCC himself. This approach kept the research ethical and legally sound.

Furthermore, using documents ethically means strictly following confidentiality and data protection rules. Researchers must keep private information about people and organizations safe. They do this by removing names or other personal details from documents and by keeping data secure from hacking or leaks. Following these ethical rules is crucial in protecting the trust and rights of everyone involved and to meet high research honesty standards (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). In this dissertation, the researcher removed the names of people, places, and organizations; contact details like office phone numbers, email addresses, location, and even websites and social media pages; dates; and signatures. He also made sure that all other sensitive details were kept safe from any unauthorized access or disclosure. He also monitored data handling and followed all privacy policy requirements.

Carefully applying these standards in the selection of the document for analysis, the researcher worked to gather and prepare data that would allow clear, useful examination and reliable research outcomes aligned with the present study's goals. This careful data selection aimed at ensuring that the resulting dataset would support meaningful insights, sound conclusions, and coverage of the research questions.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Employing Cooren's (2021) ventriloquial analysis framework, the conduct of the analysis of this study involved four (4) phases. The first phase was *identification*, which involved the determination of the explicit and implicit invocation (figures) and

animations (vents). Phase 2 involved *grouping and assigning activities* where figures and vents were grouped into clusters, and then these clusters were assigned to activities. In this phase, clusters were also grouped into collections, and the main activities were identified. Phase 3 was *relating*, which included relating clusters and collections to main voices by tracing back chains of authorship, possibly including a visual model. In this phase, unseen principals, as authors, were identified. These unseen principals are the invisible forces that give voices to the figures to speak out messages and compel them to act. The lower and higher unseen principals were identified through asking this question: *Can you think of a possible higher unseen principal that could have ventriloquized the figures aside from the legal framework?*

The last phase, Phase 4, is *showing*, which involves selecting vignettes of “powerfully illustrative sequences” and accompanying these with an elaboration of the voices that manifested themselves in them (Cooren, 2021). In accomplishing this phase, the researcher discussed the messages voiced out and actions performed by each of the figures in the results and discussion section of this dissertation. Collaborative sensemaking with the researcher’s adviser was employed in the analysis phase of the study, which guided the researcher in the rigorous analysis process.

Table 1 presents the matrix of Ventriloquial Analysis of the Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC).

Table 1.

Matrix of Ventriloquial Analysis of the Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC)

PHASE 1 <i>(Identification of Figures and Vents)</i>		PHASE 2	PHASE 3
FIGURES	ANIMATIONS / VENTS	ACTIVITIES What is it made to do? What does it perform?	AUTHORSHIP
Official Seal or Logo	Authoritative document	Representing the government	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Legal Framework
Letterhead			<i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Public trust and confidence
Certificate Number	Sequential Organization of Documents Validity and Credibility, and Authenticity of the document	Facilitating Ease in Tracking and Record Keeping	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Documentary Organization and Filing <i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Legitimacy
RA 9003	The authority of the law to ecologically manage solid waste	Representing the government's initiatives for environmental protection and sustainability	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Solid waste management dilemmas and environmental degradation <i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Ecological integrity Environmental Stewardship (Obligation to God)

Declaration of Compliance	Alignment to Business and Ecological Regulatory Framework	Affirming compliance Informing the public about legal compliance	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Solid waste management regulatory standards <i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Ecological integrity Personal Wellbeing of Business Owners
Date of Issuance	The start of the validity and legality of the document	Clarifying and reminding the validity period of the document	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Relevance and Timeliness of the Document <i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Legitimacy
Place of Issuance	Geographical Point of Reference	Defining geographical accountability	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Jurisdictional Relevance <i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Costumers' Welfare, Trust and Confidence
Date of Inspection	The validation and attestation of the compliance of the business entities	Substantiating or providing proof of the business entity's compliance	<i>Unseen Principal:</i> Solid Waste Management Regulatory Standards <i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Justifiable enforcement and evidentiary standards

Signatory	The document is authorized, official, and authentic by an authorized certifying individual	Affirming Compliance with regulatory standards	<p><i>Unseen Principal:</i> Regulatory Office and Solid Waste Management Regulatory Standards</p> <p><i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Legitimacy and Authenticity Public trust and confidence</p>
QR Code	Officiality and Authenticity of the Document	<p>Facilitating the verification of the officiality and authenticity of the document (agent of verification)</p> <p>Keeping the digital record of the data associated with the document</p>	<p><i>Unseen Principal:</i> Legitimacy</p> <p><i>Higher Unseen Principal:</i> Business Owner's and the General Public's trust and confidence</p>

Ensuring Plausibility in the Findings

Plausibility refers to how believable or likely a statement or event is. It shows whether a claim is credible (van der Helm, 2006), consistent (Connell & Keane, 2006), or coherent (Fischer & Dannenberg, 2021), or in line with what people already believe or understand (Boone et al., 2010). These beliefs include prior information, theories, or conclusions based on historical data and other sources. This idea connects to judging how well a statement or story about the future fits our current knowledge (Glette-Iversen, Aven, & Flage, 2022). In qualitative research under the positivist paradigm, scholars use terms like adequacy, trustworthiness, accuracy, and credibility when they assess validity and look for truth. Plausibility often replaces words such as authenticity, goodness, and credibility in these discussions and debate practices.

Qualitative communication research looks at how people make sense of events and build stories, and this involves plausibility (Klein, 2021). Because communication studies depend on people's subjective views, researchers must work carefully to keep their methods valid and reliable (Brink, 1993). Checking the strength of qualitative communication studies is especially critical in technical and scientific communication since it can change academic discussions and professional work (Blakeslee et al., 1996). Even though communication research often uses numbers, many researchers favor descriptive methods that focus on detailed description (Gondwe, 2020). This choice brings up questions about the basic beliefs behind communication research and whether the field needs strict measurements or values deep interpretation instead. Saludadez (2021) points out that plausibility shows that qualitative communication research is trustworthy. In that study, researchers made sure their work was plausible in two major ways. First, empirical plausibility checks whether the results match what

the participants of the studied group say. Second, theoretical plausibility checks if the results agree with past research and ideas from the wider academic community in different fields overall.

When assessing how believable or trustworthy qualitative research is, researchers use the same quality standards for all qualitative designs, including the “big three” approaches. Standards from quantitative studies, such as internal validity, generalizability, reliability, and objectivity, are not fit for judging qualitative work (Korstjens & Moser, 2018). Instead, qualitative researchers ask, “*Can the findings be trusted?*” and talk about trustworthiness (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Many definitions and measures of trustworthiness exist (Korstjens & Moser, 2017), but the most common criteria, as defined by Lincoln and Guba (1985), are credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability, and reflexivity. These criteria help ensure the trustworthiness or plausibility of research findings.

Credibility. This is the confidence that can be placed in the truth of the research findings. Credibility establishes whether the research findings represent plausible information drawn from the participants’ original data and are a correct interpretation of the participants’ original views (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Strategies to achieve credibility include prolonged engagement, persistent observation, triangulation, and member check. This present study ensured credibility by executing persistent observation, and triangulation. Member checking was done because the study did not involve interviewees.

Persistent observation. This involves identifying those characteristics and elements that are most relevant to the problem or issue under study, on which you will focus in detail (Tracy, 2010; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In this study, the

researcher persistently conducted visual observation on the MSWMCC for him to identify the elements that are most relevant to the research problem.

Triangulation. This involves using different data sources, investigators, and methods of data collection. Here, the researcher only performed investigator triangulation. Data triangulation was not performed because there was only one document that was used in the study, the MSWMCC. Investigator triangulation is concerned with using two or more researchers to make coding, analysis, and interpretation decisions. In this current investigation, investigator triangulation was ensured as the researcher was assisted by his dissertation adviser in the conduct of the identification of figures, animations, or vents, activities, and authorship; analysis; and interpretation. Meanwhile, method triangulation means using multiple methods of data collection. This was not done anymore since the researcher only used Cooren's (2021) Ventriloquial Analysis Methodological Framework, which alone is a very complicated research analysis approach.

Transferability. This refers to the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The researcher facilitates the transferability judgment by a potential user through thick description. The strategy to achieve transferability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) is through thick description, which is describing not just the behavior and experiences, but their context as well, so that the behavior and experiences become meaningful to an outsider (Tracy, 2010). In terms of transferability, the study passed in this standard as its results can be transferred to other contexts or settings utilizing different sets of research documents. Although this study did not involve describing participants' behavior and experiences, the researcher, with the guidance of his dissertation adviser, provided a thick description of the results of the ventriloquial analysis,

incorporating figures of the significant parts of the MSWMCC that represent the figures.

Dependability. This points to the stability of findings over time. Dependability involves participants' evaluation of the findings, interpretation, and recommendations of the study, such that all are supported by the data as received from participants of the study (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In terms of dependability, the study satisfies this said plausibility standard. Though the present investigation is a textual analysis using Cooren's (2021) Ventriloquial Analysis Methodological Framework that does not directly involve research participants, this study still ensures dependability. Since the study did not involve participants, it was the researcher's dissertation adviser, who is an expert in CCO and ventriloquial analysis in the country, who evaluated the findings, interpretation, and recommendations of this study, supported by relevant data.

Confirmability. This refers to the degree to which the findings of the research study could be confirmed by other researchers. Confirmability is concerned with establishing that data and interpretations of the findings are not figments of the inquirer's imagination, but clearly derived from the data. The strategy to achieve dependability and confirmability, is (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), is through an *audit trail*, which transparently describes the research steps taken from the start of a research project to the development and reporting of the findings. The records of the research path are kept throughout the study (Tracy, 2010). In this study, confirmability through audit trail is ensured by the researcher by incorporating, under the data analysis section of this dissertation, the ventriloquial analysis matrix, which explicitly reflects the step-by-step process conducted by the researcher to arrive at desirable answers to the research questions.

Reflexivity. This refers to the process of critical self-reflection about oneself as a researcher (own biases, preferences, preconceptions), and the research relationship (relationship to the respondent, and how the relationship affects participants' answers to questions). The strategy to achieve reflexivity is (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) through a diary, which involves examining one's own conceptual lens, explicit and implicit assumptions, preconceptions, and values, and how these affect research decisions in all phases of qualitative studies (Tracy, 2010). As a qualitative researcher, he has to acknowledge the importance of being self-aware and reflexive about his own role in the process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting the data, and in the pre-conceived assumptions he brings to his research (Mauthner & Doucet, 2003). In this dissertation, the researcher ensured reflexivity by disregarding his own biases, preferences, and preconceptions during the conduct of the ventriloquial analysis of the MSWMCC, especially since he was the one who designed, crafted, and issues the said regulatory document in solid waste management.

CHAPTER V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents and discusses the answers to the research questions of this dissertation: 1) what figures appeared in the solid waste management compliance certificate that ventriloquized its authority; and, 2) what does the compliance certificate perform in solid waste management?

Figures that Appeared in the Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate

The Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC) issued by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) as a regulatory issuance in solid waste management can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1.
 The Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC)

</p>												
<h2 style="margin: 0;">MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT COMPLIANCE CERTIFICATE</h2> <p style="margin: 0;">Issued Pursuant to RA 9003</p>												
<table border="1" style="margin: auto; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Certificate No.</td> <td style="padding: 2px;">: MSWMCC-RO8-SMS-01012022-0001</td> </tr> </table> <p style="margin: 5px 0 0 0;">This is to certify that</p> <p style="margin: 10px 0 0 40px;"><i>Name of Business Establishment</i></p> <p style="margin: 0 0 0 40px;">located at</p> <p style="margin: 10px 0 0 40px;"><i>Address</i></p> <p style="margin: 0 0 0 40px;">owned and managed by</p> <p style="margin: 10px 0 0 40px;"><i>Name of Proprietor</i></p> <p style="margin: 10px 0 0 0;">is hereby granted this Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC) by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) after having complied with all the requirements for proper ecological solid waste management mandated under Chapter 3, Article 2, Section 21 & 22 of RA 9003 otherwise known as the Solid Waste Management Act of 2000.</p> <p style="margin: 10px 0 0 0;">Issued this ___ day of _____ at the Municipality of _____, Philippines.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0 0 0; font-size: small;"> The MSWMCC is issued pursuant to Republic Act 9003 otherwise known as the "Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. Non-compliance with the mandated requirements demanded for proper solid waste management shall be sufficient cause for cancellation or non-issuance of this certificate. Business permits (new or renewal) are only granted upon presenting or acquiring this certificate. No business application shall be approved without this certification. </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin: 10px 0 0 0;">	Digitally signed by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office. This document is certified official by the MENR Office.	Location:	Municipal Sports Center,	Date:	07-05-2024 3:07 PM							
Certificate No.	: MSWMCC-RO8-SMS-01012022-0001											
Date of Inspection : _____ Date of Approval : _____ Date of Release : _____		Digitally signed by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office. This document is certified official by the MENR Office.	Location:	Municipal Sports Center,	Date:	07-05-2024 3:07 PM						
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<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20%; text-align: center;">	MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES OFFICE (MENRO)											
	MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES OFFICE (MENRO)											

There was a total of ten (10) figures identified from the analysis of the MSWMCC – **official logo, letterhead, certificate number, RA 9003, declaration of compliance, date of issuance, place of issuance, date of inspection, signatory, and QR code.**

First and Second Figures: Seal or Logo and the Letterhead

The MSWMCC bears the logo of the Municipal Government. The official seal or logo is located in the topmost left part of the letterhead of the compliance certificate. Figure 2 displays the official seal or logo and the letterhead on the MSWMCC.

Figure 2.
The Official Seal or Logo and the Letterhead on the MSWMCC

The official seal or logo in the MSWMCC incarnates the authority that issued the document. It presentifies or represents the authority of the municipal government where the document was crafted, legalized, authorized, and issued.

The official seal or logo symbolizes the authority and legal power of the provincial government of (Name of the Province), as well as the national government of the Philippines, as governed by their respective legislations, including the national constitution.

The question of why the official seal or logo represents the government and its authority can be answered by understanding that this figure is influenced by an unseen principal, which is the legal statute of the country.

Furthermore, the official seal or logo represents the government and its authority because it is mandated to do so by a higher unseen principal - public trust and confidence.

As a partner figure, the letterhead of the MSWMCC, the topmost line states the name of the country, the name of the province, and the name of the municipality, as in this arrangement:

Republic of the Philippines
Province of (Name of the Province)
Municipality of _____
Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office

This configuration signifies a hierarchical order of authority and its representation in the issuance of the MSWMCC.

When the MSWMCC is granted to a business entity that has adhered strictly to all the requirements for ecological solid waste management, the certificate is prominently displayed within their business establishment. The inclusion of the official seal or logo and the letterhead instills a sense of trust and confidence in people or customers who see the certificate, as they perceive the business establishment to be an authorized entity to do business. Viewing the official seal or logo engenders trust among the patrons of the business agency that the products and services offered by the agency are of competitive quality, satisfactory, and, most importantly, clean and hygienic, as the business has complied with the regulatory standards for ecological waste management for business establishments.

Moreover, when business customers observe the official seal or logo on the MSWMCC, a sense of confidence is cultivated toward the compliant business agency, as they believe they will not be deceived. The presence of the official seal or logo signifies the integrity of the business firm, indicating that it adheres to legal statutes

and that scamming customers or providing them with subpar services would result in violations of legal business standards. Consequently, such violations could lead to sanctions, such as permit revocation or even closure. With the official seal or logo present on the MSWMCC, business managers and their personnel become cautious in their operations to ensure compliance with the legal framework governing business activities.

Third Figure: Certificate Number

In the MSWMCC, the certificate number is also indicated. Figure 3 illustrates the certificate number on the MSWMCC.

Figure 3.
The Certificate Number on the MSWMCC

The certificate number in the compliance certificate speaks about the sequential organization of the compliance certificates issued by the local government regulatory body, the MENRO, making it beneficial for the said office in its efforts or documenting and organizing released compliance certificates. The certificate number with the date of approval and issuance embedded in it conveys a significant message to the business owners of the period of validity of the compliance certificate. Beyond that

period, they need to apply for the renewal of the compliance certificate in the succeeding year.

The certificate number in the MSWMCC performs the act of facilitating ease in tracking and record keeping. Serving as a unique reference point, the certificate number allows for the easy identification and retrieval of specific certificates, aiding in the organization and maintenance of compliance records. Furthermore, in times the MSWMCC is used as material evidence in court proceedings, especially in legal disputes over ownership, the certificate number can be used as evidence to establish the rightful owner of the business firm. When a violation against RA 9003 is committed by a business entity despite of its compliance of the mandated regulatory requirements for solid waste management, say the business organization established an open dumpsite at the back of their establishment, which is a violation to the national legal stature in solid waste management, the certificate number is beneficial in instituting and proving the legitimate owner of the business that committed the violation.

As a unique reference point, the certificate number in the compliance certificate serves as a mechanism that enhances the legality and authenticity of the compliance certification and its conferment process. The certificate number, as a unique reference point, is known to both business owners and the general public, especially the customers, as being organized, recorded, and filed in the records section of the issuing regulatory body, the MENRO.

Fourth Figure: RA 9003

The law, RA 9003, is aimed at promoting resource conservation through reuse, recycling, and composting. This helps reduce the use of new materials and prevents the depletion of natural resources. RA 9003 is considered a milestone in Philippine

legislation, as it lays the foundation for a more sustainable and responsible approach to solid waste management. While there are still challenges to overcome in its full implementation, the law provides a crucial framework for guiding the country towards a cleaner, healthier, and more sustainable future.

In the municipality where the MENRO, the local government regulatory body issuing the MSWMCC, RA 9003 is also being implemented through the implementing office of the local government, the MENRO. As an implementing local government office of RA 9003, the MENRO also crafted various programs, projects, and activities that would facilitate the execution and accomplishment of proper and ecological solid waste management in the municipality. Some of these programs, projects, and activities crafted and executed by the MENRO in alignment with the implementation of RA 9003 include the establishment of Barangay Ecological Solid Waste Management Committee (BESWMC), which is a multi-sectoral organization in the barangays headed by the barangay chairperson. The BESWMC is the lead organization in the barangay, mandated to create and execute plans for solid waste management.

The MENRO is also actively conducting a series of information, education, and communication (IEC) campaigns on RA 9003, putting an emphasis on proper segregation of wastes at source. Aside from symposiums on RA 9003 in the barangays and in schools, the MENRO also conducts a house-to-house campaign on proper solid waste segregation at source, along with the distribution of flyers on RA 9003.

Aside from these initiatives, the local government regulatory body in solid waste management also intensifies its campaign in every barangay in the municipality to establish and operationalize their Materials Recovery Facilities (MRFs) where the

recyclables – paper, plastic, glass, and iron – collected in the barangay are processed and stored. The office also encourages all the barangays to establish a barangay composting facility where all the biodegradables are disposed of and composted.

In addition to that, since RA 9003 mandates that all establishments that are sources or generators of solid wastes be included in the implementation of the law, the MENRO included all the business establishments in the municipality by regulating their operations in consideration of their adoption and execution of proper solid waste management practices in their respective area of business jurisdiction. This is the reason why the MENRO requires all the business entities in town to comply with all the requirements for solid waste management before they can be conferred with an MSWMCC.

RA 9003 is identified to be one of the figures that compel business entities to act in solid waste management. In conformity with Cooren's (2018) conceptualization of ventriloquism, RA 9003 is ventriloquized or given a voice to convey a message of the legal authority to ecologically manage solid wastes in the country. Figure 4 shows RA 9003 on the MSWMCC.

Figure 4.
RA 9003 on the MSWMCC

Since RA 9003 is ventriloquized, fundamentally it conveys an idea to the people that they are given the legal power and the mandate to manage the solid wastes they produce in manners which do not hurt or cause further harm to the environment.

Another thing is that RA 9003 is saying now that ecological solid waste management is already entrusted and mandated to the people, it has become their responsibility, obligation, and accountability to the country so that when they fail to adhere and they fall short in their conformity with the legislation they would consequently face legal repercussions.

Also, as RA 9003 voices the message of the legal authority to ecologically manage solid wastes, the legislation is also encouraging the people to conceptualize multifarious means of managing garbage that do not pose threats to the environment encompassing such fundamental approaches as recycling of plastic wastes, reduction of wastes at source by executing proper waste segregation, and the reutilization of reusable materials.

Delving into a deeper note, as it is ventriloquized, RA 9003 puts across its message that its ultimate purpose is to guide the entire country toward a cleaner, healthier, safer, more secure, and sustainable future. It also wants the people to know that it advocates a remarkable shift from conventional waste disposal approaches to a more ecologically conscious method that prioritizes waste reduction, reuse, recycling, and composting, as discussed earlier.

Given a voice to speak, RA 9003 is empowering local governments to implement effective waste management programs, ensuring that the health and well-being of the people are protected. With this empowerment of this legal environmental statute, the national down to local governments craft and execute various programs, projects, and activities in alignment with the goal of achieving proper and ecological

solid waste management. As elaborated at the onset of the discussion in this portion, the MENRO which is a local government regulatory body and an implementing agency, created multifarious various program, projects, and activities in solid waste management from the organization, establishment and functionalization of BESWMCs, the education of the residents on proper solid waste segregation to the establishment and functionalization of barangay MRFs. It is because of this voice given to RA 9003 that the MENRO and the barangays in the municipality are given the legal authority, power, and accountability to execute best practices for solid waste management. Accountability is included aside from legal authority and power bestowed by the voice of RA 9003 because power and authority come with great responsibility and accountability. Once an entity is given power (which is always geared toward achieving something), it has to act and perform its authority because the failure of accomplishing the goal that comes with the power given means it has to be so accountable for its failure that it should face repercussions.

RA 9003 screams its vision for the entire Philippines, where waste is not a problem nor a burden anymore but a resource, where communities are empowered to manage their waste responsibly, and where the environment is safeguarded for the generations to come.

Ensuing Cooren's (2016) Non-Human Agency framework, RA 9003 performs the role of representing the government's initiative for environmental protection. When RA 9003 performs this act, it tells us of the utmost care, concern, and compassion of the Philippine government for its people. If the National Government does not really possess care, concern, and compassion for its people, it would not be exhausting their time, effort, and even resources in engaging in endeavors of conceptualizing initiatives just to protect the environment.

In essence, the environment does not only include the plants and animals per se, but also includes the people, the human beings, since they are considered higher forms of animals in scientific parlance. Grounded on this thought, when the Philippine government implements measures for environmental protection, that is tantamount to saying that it expresses its care, concern, and compassion for its people by protecting their health and well-being in its efforts to protect the environment from deteriorating.

RA 9003 also executes the action of representing the ingenuities of the government for environmental sustainability. In defining environmental sustainability, it is all about meeting the present needs without compromising future generations. It is also about ensuring that our planet's natural resources and ecosystems are protected and preserved for present and future generations. It's about living in a way that doesn't deplete these resources or damage the environment, allowing future generations to enjoy a healthy and thriving planet. In RA 9003's performance of the event of presentifying the government's initiatives for environmental sustainability, this sustainability does not only refer to the environment alone but more so it refers to the sustainability of the lives of the people, that is meeting their needs to survive at the present without depleting and destroying the environment and natural resources that in turn destroys their lives, as destruction to the environment eventually results in the destruction of the lives of the people.

Having said that RA 9003's performance of these actions is a manifestation of the government's care, concern, and compassion for its people, the government, with this, is also calling the entire Filipino nation to cooperate in all its initiatives, to love ourselves, and to love the environment. As a famous adage of Algernon Sidney in the 17th century goes, "God helps those who help themselves." The government in this sense helps its people in protecting themselves from adverse impacts of

environmental degradation caused by inappropriate management of their solid wastes, that is why it is also motivating its people to help themselves, too, by cooperating, and taking part in the implementation of programs, projects, and activities geared toward the accomplishment of a healthier, safer, and sustainable environment through ecologically fitting solid waste management practices. In relation to this, we, too, should manifest love not just for the environment but more so for ourselves.

Also, RA 9003's representation of the initiatives of the government for environmental protection and sustainability is a concrete manifestation of the government's vow to the people, which is to become a government of the people, by the people, and for the people. Through RA 9003, the government made the environmental law presentify and perform the action it is told to do to show to the entire Filipino nation that the government is owned by the people, executed by the people, and for the benefit and welfare of the people. Delving deeper, it is the people, represented by national and local officials, who administer, manage and operate the government. RA 9003 was crafted and approved by the people duly represented by the lawmakers – the congressmen, the senators, and the president of the country. The environmental legal framework was also enacted into law for the purpose of benefiting and advancing the welfare of the Filipino people.

Moreover, RA 9003's performance of the event of representing the government's initiatives for environmental protection and sustainability is also a manifestation of its fulfillment of its vow manifested in the preamble of the 1987 Philippine constitution (Senate Electoral Tribunal, 2016), which aptly says:

“We, the sovereign Filipino people, imploring the aid of Almighty God, in order to build a just and humane society, and establish a Government that shall embody our ideals

*and aspirations, **promote the common good, conserve and develop our patrimony, and secure to ourselves and our posterity, the blessings of independence and democracy under the rule of law and a regime of truth, justice, freedom, love, equality, and peace, do ordain and promulgate this Constitution.***

The lines in the above preamble of the 1987 Philippine constitution saying, **“...promote the common good, conserve and develop our patrimony, and secure to ourselves and our posterity...”** is an unambiguous expression of the ultimate mission of the government to advance the wellbeing of its people, to sustain and develop the Filipino land, and to safeguard and ensure the sustainability of the environment for the sake of the future generations.

RA 9003 is ventriloquized to voice out the legal authority to ecologically manage solid wastes in the country and executes the action of representing the government's initiatives for environmental protection and sustainability because it is acted upon or persuaded by the unseen principal, which is the solid waste management dilemmas and environmental degradation. And, higher unseen principals which include ecological integrity and environmental stewardship (which is our obligation to the Divine Creator as His children).

When RA 9003 is acted upon or animated (persuaded to act) by an unseen principal in the form of solid waste management dilemmas and environmental degradation, the environmental legal framework voices out a significant message of the legal authority to ecologically manage solid wastes and performs the action of representing the government's initiative for environmental sustainability. Solid waste

management dilemmas such as the escalating volumes of toxic solid wastes in the environment result in environmental degradation in the forms of air and water pollution, soil contamination, ocean acidification, and desertification. Because of these environmental degradation occurrences, RA 9003, as a figure, is compelled to act to voice out the need to ecologically manage solid wastes.

Due to the injurious threats to life of the abovementioned environmental degradation occurrences, RA 9003 is pushed to voice out the message and to perform the event for it needs to safeguard the environment and natural resources from further deterioration. If it does not execute its role of being given a voice to speak and to perform an act in solid waste management, the people will continually overlook protecting the environment, and it will possibly face deterioration. The Filipino people will someday lose a place to live in.

Additionally, because those environmental degradation occurrences really result in various diseases like dengue, cholera, respiratory and cardiovascular ailments, lead poisoning, skin illnesses, and even cancer, RA 9003 is forced to speak out and act in order to protect the people from these adverse effects of environmental degradation to their health and well-being. The legislation's leniency in voicing its message for ecological solid waste and performing its act of representing the government's efforts for environmental protection and sustainability, in which the people are innately part of, would jeopardize their health and personal well-being, and may even face loss of lives.

Besides, RA 9003 also needs to safeguard the people from the fatal calamities that result from the deterioration of the environment caused by improper solid waste management. As climate change is caused by open burning of wastes, it also causes such harmful natural calamities as super typhoons, heat waves, flooding due to

excessive rainfalls, what not. With these, RA 9003 is forced to speak out and perform its tasks to prevent the loss of people's lives due to these catastrophes.

On a higher level, a higher unseen principal, which includes ecological integrity and environmental stewardship (which is our obligation to God as His children), animates RA 9003 as a figure. As elaborated, ecological integrity as a higher unseen principal points to the state in which natural processes occur as expected in a particular region. Areas that possess ecological integrity exhibit regular patterns of rainfall, fires, and other ecological processes. These areas harbor ecosystems that sustain both indigenous living and non-living species. Furthermore, in the realm of climate change, ensuring ecological integrity entails avoiding an increase in global greenhouse gas emissions through the transfer of mitigation outcomes, in comparison to a scenario where such transfers did not take place.

This concept encompasses the safeguarding and conservation of natural resources, biodiversity, and the general well-being of our planet. The notion of ecological integrity holds significant importance in guaranteeing the sustainability of our planet and the welfare of all living organisms. It serves as a fundamental principle in international agreements such as the Paris Agreement, where preventing an increase in greenhouse gas emissions resulting from climate change mitigation efforts is imperative. It is for the pursuit of maintaining and sustaining this ecological integrity that RA 9003 speaks out its message to the people and performs its tasks in solid waste management.

At a higher level, another unseen principal is environmental stewardship. This principle highlights the idea that as humans, we are responsible for taking care of the natural world, which is a gift from the Divine Creator. It is also because of this obligation

to the Divine Creator that the said legislation performs the task of representing the government's efforts for environmental protection and sustainability.

In a general sense, RA 9003, as a non-human agent incarnated in the MSWMCC, is ventriloquized to speak about the authority to ecologically manage solid wastes, and accomplishes the event of representing the government's initiatives for the protection of the environment and for sustainability because it animated or acted upon by the unseen principals, solid waste management dilemmas and environmental degradation, and on a higher level, by ecological integrity and environmental stewardship which is our ultimate obligation to the Divine Creator as His children.

In the ventriloquial analysis process of the MSWMCC, it was found that all of the figures that appeared from the document were ventriloquized (given voices to communicate certain messages) and animated (acted upon or persuaded to perform certain tasks to accomplish something). Eventually, the researcher has theorized that if all those higher unseen principals were grouped according to their common nature, he would arrive at four (4) major much higher unseen principals which correspond to the National Motto – Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Maka-kalikasan, at Makabansa (For God, People, Nature and Country). This National Motto is specified in Chapter III, Section 40 of Republic Act No. 8491, popularly known as the Flag and Heraldic Code of the Philippines, which echoes the last four lines of the pledge of allegiance (Supreme Court E-Library, 2019).

As mentioned, the National Motto echoes the last four lines of the Pledge of Allegiance to the Philippine Flag (Panunumpa ng Katapatan sa Watawat ng Pilipinas), which says in both Filipino (Executive Order No. 343, S. 1996, 1996) and English (Rabe, 2023) versions:

Filipino Version	English Translation
Ako ay Pilipino	I am a Filipino
Buong katapatang nanunumpa	I pledge allegiance
Sa watawat ng Pilipinas	To the flag of the Philippines
At sa bansang kanyang sinasagisag	And to the country it represents
Na may dangal, katarungan at kalayaan	With honor, justice and freedom
Na pinakikilos ng sambayanang	That is put in motion by a nation that
Maka-Diyos,	is
Maka-tao,	For God, Humanity,
Makakalikasan, at	Nature and
Makabansa.	Country.

Figure 5 shows the authority of the figures as ventriloquized and animated by much higher unseen principals, the National Motto - *Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Makakalikasan, at Makabansa* (For God, People, Nature and Country).

Figure 5.
The Ventriloquized-Animated Authority of the MSWMCC as a Non-Human Agent in the Accomplishment of Organization Goals

As can be construed from the figure, grouping the higher unseen principals according to their common nature would arrive at four groups corresponding to the National Motto, as in below:

Maka-Diyos

- Environmental Stewardship (Obligation to God)

Maka-tao

- Public trust and confidence
- Personal Wellbeing of Business Owners
- Costumers' Welfare, Trust and Confidence
- Business Owner's and the General Public's trust and confidence

Makakalikasan

- Ecological integrity

Makabansa

- Legitimacy
- Justifiable enforcement and evidentiary standards
- Legitimacy and Authenticity

Under the Maka-Diyos unseen principal is environmental stewardship (which is our obligation to the Divine Creator). Environmental stewardship is under Maka-Diyos in the sense that people are considered pro-God if they nurture, protect, and care for all the creations of the Divine Creator, which in this case is the environment and natural resources. This suggests that the figures in the MSWMCC, and even the certificate itself as a non-human agent, are ventriloquized and animated or acted upon by the National Motto, specifically, the Maka-Diyos motto. It is the figures' state of being pro-God that moves them to communicate certain messages and perform certain tasks, which also compels business owners to participate in solid waste management, inculcating in them the notion that protecting the environment is the people's primary obligation to the Divine Creator who created us as His children. In short, it is our obligation to the Divine Creator to protect our environment, which persuades us to participate in solid waste management.

Furthermore, classified under the Maka-tao (pro-people) cluster are the unseen principals of public trust; personal well-being of business owners; customers' welfare, trust, and confidence; and business owners and the general public's trust and

confidence. These unseen principals are placed under the Maka-tao group because all these invisible entities compel the figures to communicate certain messages and perform certain tasks that promote the welfare of human beings, the people. In simpler parlance, it is the figures' pursuit of being Maka-tao that drives them to move human agents to participate in solid waste management because the end result of the human actors' participation in solid waste management is their personal well-being.

The unseen principal of ecological integrity is placed under the third National Motto, which is Makakalikasan. It is in the sense that maintaining the ecological integrity of the country demonstrates our being Makakalikasan (pro-nature). This much higher unseen principal of Makakalikasan (pro-nature) ventriloquizes or gives voices to and animates or act upon the figures in the MSWMCC to communicate messages and perform actions to move human actors to participate in solid waste management to maintain the ecological integrity of the country. This pursuit manifests both the human and non-human agents' state of being Makakalikasan (pro-nature).

Finally, the three higher unseen principals of legitimacy, justifiable enforcement and evidentiary standards, and pursuit of legitimacy and authenticity are placed under the fourth, much higher unseen principal, the National Motto, which is Maka-bansa. It is because all these higher principals point to one single concept - the pursuit of legitimacy. Being legal or pursuing being legal means conforming to the laws of the land, the laws of the country. The laws of the country were crafted and approved exclusively for the welfare of the entire country. So, if a human or non-human agent or a figure demands legality, that means he or she has great concern for the country, has great care for the welfare of the country. Following Cooren's (2018) concept of ventriloquism, it is the Maka-bansa (pro-country) much higher unseen principal that moves the higher unseen principals - legitimacy, justifiable enforcement and

evidentiary standards, and pursuit of legitimacy and authenticity – to ventriloquize or give voice to and to animate or act upon the figures to communicate vital messages and perform important tasks that persuade the human agents to participate and accomplish proper solid waste management.

So, with all those much higher unseen principals ventriloquizing and animating human agents to move human actors to participate in solid waste management, what is the authority of these non-human agents in accomplishing proper solid waste management?

The National Motto - Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Maka-kalikasan, at Makabansa (For God, People, Nature and Country) – acting as much higher unseen principals ventriloquize and animate the figures in the MSWMCC to communicate messages of environmental protection and sustainability, and animate them to perform tasks in solid waste management. The voices that are given and the persuasion or animation to act by the National Motto bestow a certain kind of authority on the figures in the MSWMCC, which compels the human actors to act in solid waste management. The researcher calls it the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority.

The Ventriloquized-Animated Authority Theory, the researcher theorized, is that kind of authority that the figures and the whole non-human agent, the MSWMCC, derive from their being ventriloquized (given voices to speak) and animated (acted upon to act) by some higher unseen principals. The voices given to the figures by more powerful unseen principals grant them the strength and the power to speak about influential messages that move human agents to act. Likewise, the force of persuasion to act exerted on the figures by a more powerful unseen principal also pushes the human actors to perform something geared toward the accomplishment of organizational goals.

The figures in the MSWMCC are bestowed with a Ventriloquized-Animated Authority by the much higher unseen principals, National Motto - Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Maka-kalikasan, at Makabansa (For God, People, Nature and Country). These much higher unseen principals ventriloquize or give voices to the figures in the compliance certificate so that they can communicate with power and influence messages associated with environmental protection and sustainability. These messages voiced out by figures in the document push people to act – in this scenario, to participate in solid waste management. In like manner, these much higher unseen principals animate or act upon these figures to perform activities that also move the people to act, also in this scenario, to participate in solid waste management.

When the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority of each of the figures in the compliance certificate combine together, they sum up to this kind of authority of the entire MSWMCC, which is stronger and more influential, compelling the people, human agents, to act and participate in the accomplishment of proper solid waste management. In other words, as the individual figures in the compliance certificate work together, building up the entire MSWMCC into a unified, complete, and independent non-human agent, the document possesses a Ventriloquized-Animated Authority stronger and more influential than that of the individual figures contained in it.

Carrying with it and using the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority, the MSWMCC, as a result, effectively persuades the personnel of the MENRO to rigorously conduct the compliance certification process, requiring business entities to accomplish the requirements for certification, demanding the office's inspection team to conduct onsite validation and documentation of compliance, and pushing the

approving officer to approve and release the certificate if the business entity's compliance is proven true.

Similarly, the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority possessed by the MSWMCC pushes the business owners, who are human agents, to participate in an orientation on RA 9003; provide five (5) separate, properly labelled, and color-coded trash bins; display a tarpaulin on proper solid waste segregation and penal provisions of the law; and execute proper solid waste disposal practices, completing the compliance certification process.

Principally, it is the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority of the MSWMCC, a non-human agent, that pushes both the MENRO personnel and the business proprietors and their staff, both human agents, to actively participate in the accomplishment of proper solid waste management in the municipality.

In the end, the National Motto - Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Maka-kalikasan, at Makabansa (For God, People, Nature and Country) – which serves as the much higher unseen principal, is what the national government dreams the Filipino people to become, as a motto also serves as a guiding principle. The government wants the Filipino people to embody this motto that will guide them in becoming productive and responsible citizens of the country. Associating this with the present investigation, the accomplishment of proper solid waste management in the municipality caused by the configuration of human and non-human agents also results in the accomplishment of the national goal indicated in this National Motto. The human agents, compelled by non-human agents, participating in appropriate, responsible, accountable, and sustainable ecological solid waste practices make them Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Maka-kalikasan, at Makabansa.

Fifth Figure: Declaration of Compliance

Figure 6 presents the declaration of compliance on the MSWMCC.

Figure 6.

The Declaration of Compliance on the MSWMCC

As can be seen on the figure, the entire text of the compliance certification comprises the declaration of compliance of the business entities aptly saying:

...is hereby granted this Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC) by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) after having complied with all the requirements for proper ecological solid waste management mandated under Chapter 3, Article 2, Sections 21 & 22 of RA 9003, otherwise known as the Solid Waste Management Act of 2000.

In the paragraph above, the phrase *"is hereby granted"* refers to the business entity that has successfully complied with all the requirements set forth by the MENRO as mandated under RA 9003, to which the MSWMCC is awarded. The conferment of this compliance certificate by the MENRO signifies that the entity has successfully met all the necessary criteria and obligations for the adequate management of solid waste

in an ecologically responsible manner in their business establishment as explicitly stated in the above paragraph: *“after having complied with all the requirements for proper ecological solid waste management mandated under Chapter 3, Article 2, Section 21 & 22 of RA 9003 otherwise known as the Solid Waste Management Act of 2000.”*

As plainly stated in the text, the compliance certificate is granted to the entity after demonstrating full adherence to the requirements outlined in Chapter 3, Article 2, Sections 21 & 22 of Republic Act 9003. The specific sections mentioned in the aforementioned paragraph – *Chapter 3, Article 2, Section 21 & 22*, outline the specific demands of RA 9003 for solid waste management. Section 1 mandates that the solid wastes be segregated at source, be it at the public and government offices, schools, religious buildings, industrial institutions, homes, and in this case, business establishments. Section 2 mandates that these institutions, which are generators of solid wastes, provide separate, properly labelled and color-coded trash bins to facilitate ease in solid waste disposal, adhering to proper waste segregation. Since business establishments generate waste, the MENRO deemed it necessary to include them in the mandatory practice of proper waste segregation at source by regulating their operation in the manner of letting them undergo a compliance certification process. The fulfillment of the stipulated requirements under these specific sections of RA 9003 means that the entity has demonstrated its commitment to environmentally sound waste management practices as mandated by the law.

The awarding of the MSWMCC is a formal recognition by the MENRO that the entity has not only met but exceeded the standards set forth in the Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. It signifies that the entity has demonstrated compliance with the ecological and environmental regulations aimed at promoting sustainable waste

management practices and protecting the environment. This certificate serves as tangible evidence of the entity's dedication to responsible waste management and its commitment to upholding legal and environmental standards in the handling of solid waste.

The declaration of compliance voices out various communicative messages in relation to the business entity's alignment with the business and ecological regulatory framework. This figure suggests to the approving officer to declare compliance for the purpose of recognizing and appreciating the efforts of the business entities in complying with all the regulatory standards. Compliant business establishments undergo mandated activities and requirements like participating in a one-day orientation on RA 9003, providing five (5) separate, properly labelled and color-coded trash bins, and printing and displaying a tarpaulin indicating the proper segregation of solid wastes in their business establishment. The completion of all these essential conditions entails the spending of a certain amount of money, the allotment of time, and the exertion of efforts and energy on the part of the complying business entity. This figure needs the MENRO to recognize and appreciate these efforts of the compliant business establishment to align and conform with business and ecological regulatory frameworks.

In addition, this figure suggests to the approving officer to declare compliance for the purpose of giving the general public an opportunity to know that the business establishment is law-abiding, and has care and concern for the environment and for the people. This figure extends beyond a mere formal statement of adherence to regulations; it embodies a persuasive force that guides the approving officer towards declaring compliance. This figure serves a larger goal: to provide transparency and ongoing assurance that the business establishment follows legal rules, respects the

environment, and cares fully for its community. When the members of the public or a customer see the MSWMCC, they receive these clear messages of compliance, environmental responsibility, and community welfare. This transparency not only fosters trust and confidence among consumers, investors, and stakeholders but also demonstrates the business's care and concern for the environment and the well-being of the community.

Also, this figure, as it voices out the business establishment's alignment to business and regulatory frameworks, communicates the message about the business establishment's values and principles. This figure also communicates a message of integrity, responsibility, and respect for the environment and society at large. In the declaration of compliance's public profession of the business entity's alignment with business standards and regulatory frameworks, the business establishment illustrates its willingness to be held accountable, to operate with integrity, and to prioritize the well-being of both the environment and the people it serves.

In another concept, this figure, in its proclamation of the business entity's alignment to standards and frameworks, suggests to the approving officer to declare compliance to make the compliant business entity a role model to other businesses to make them emulate what the compliant business entity did. This figure speaks to the public to follow that the compliant business establishment did so that there would be an escalation of the number of business firms that conform to the mandates of the legal statute in solid waste management, speeding the accomplishment, in turn, of proper solid waste management in the municipality.

Along with that, this figure suggests to the approving officer to declare compliance so that it can make a pronouncement to the general public that if compliant business entities can comply, other businesses also can. If others can, why can't you?

It's like this figure screams to the general public, especially to other existing businesses: *"Everyone, this business entity made it. You can make it, too. It's that easy!"*

Apart from that, on the business owners' end, this figure's proclamation of the business entity's alignment to business standards and regulatory frameworks communicates the notion of the business agency's obedience to legal mandate and that there is fear for legal sanction for disobedience. It cannot be denied that business owners possess a common knowledge that for every legislation, there are associated penal provisions in cases where the mandates of the law are not fulfilled and are contradicted. With this in mind, business owners manifest their obedience to the mandates of the law to prevent themselves from facing legal consequences for their waywardness.

Alongside the figure's proclamation of the business entity's alignment to business standards and regulatory frameworks is its conveyance of the message of business owners' personal benefit. Business owners operate business activities because they want to earn a living; they want to improve their economic standing in society. For them to be granted the legal authority, rights, and privileges to engage in business activities to earn a living, business owners have to align with business standards and regulatory framework.

Carrying with this figure's message of a business entity's conformity with business standards and regulatory framework is the notion of the business owner's desire of having some peace of mind. For the business proprietors, conforming to the mandates of the legislation for compliance by undergoing the certification process and securing the MSWMCC would give an opportunity not to worry about their business

facing legal consequences and even closure due to disobedience to regulatory standards.

Likewise, on the part of the general public or the customers, this figure tells them that the business is not just law-abiding, but more so, it has deep concern for the welfare of the nation and of the environment. It also tells the general public, the customers, the other business entities, and the aspiring business proprietors about the commendable efforts of the compliant business entity in satisfying all the mandated requirements for solid waste management in business establishments. Besides, it also raises motivation in other existing businesses and aspiring business operators to do the same.

Sixth Figure: The Date of Issuance

The date of issuance is a vital component of a certificate, providing essential information regarding its authenticity, validity, and legal status. It is important for both the issuing authority and the recipient to ensure proper documentation and verification. Figure 7 shows the date of issuance on the MSWMCC.

Figure 7.
The Date of Issuance on the MSWMCC

In the MSWMCC, the date of issuance represents the official commencement of the validity and legality of the MSWMCC. As the businesses have to participate in an orientation on RA 9003 that would teach them about the provisions of the law, the five (5) categories of solid wastes, the proper segregation of solid wastes, and the penalties should their businesses commit violations to RA 9003, the issuance date declares the business entity to be compliant with the mandates of RA 9003 and can legally operate business.

The date of issuance tells the business when to refresh their knowledge of the law, as they will have to renew their compliance certificate by undergoing the same certification process they underwent the previous year.

Seventh Figure: The Place of Issuance

The place of issuance on the compliance certificate provides the geographical jurisdiction and accountability related to RA 9003 compliance. Figure 8 displays the place of issuance on the MSWMCC.

Figure 8.
The Place of Issuance on the MSWMCC

The figure tells who monitors and regulates such compliance. It also tells who polices or maintains order if the site is unclean or not, well-maintained or not, indicating the practices performed by the business entity in solid waste management.

The place of issuance tells where the location of the MENRO is so that in cases some individuals would like to verify the veracity of a business entity's compliance, it would be easy for them to visit the office and accomplish their purpose. Also, prospective business owners would have an idea where to go when they express their desire to undergo the compliance certification process.

Also, the place of issuance tells the MENRO the specific or definite geographical area covered by the authority of their office, and the coverage, too, of the implementation of the solid waste management program. The place of issuance defines the MENRO's geographical accountability and tells the office that the MSWMCC should only be issued to compliant business entities located in the area within the jurisdiction of the office. The compliance certificate is only valid and legal within the place it is issued.

The place of issuance authorizes the business entity to operate in its defined area of jurisdiction. If they extend their operations to locations beyond the geographical area defined by this figure, the MSWMCC loses its authority to permit the business entity in that area, causing them to be legally accountable for that violation of business operation standards. Eventually, the compliance certificate also loses its power to protect business entities from legal repercussions.

Eighth Figure: The Date of Inspection

The date of inspection is a critical piece of information on a compliance certificate as it demonstrates the validity of the inspection, the timeliness of compliance, and ongoing adherence to regulations.

In the solid waste management compliance certification process, the date of inspection is indicated on the MSWMCC. Figure 9 shows the date of inspection on the MSWMCC.

Figure 9.
The Date of Inspection on the MSWMCC

The solid waste management compliance certification process for business establishments involves various steps. One of these is the conduct of an on-site inspection of the complying business to see and to prove its compliance with the requirements for certification. After the business owners' participation in the orientation on the mandates of RA 9003, the five (5) categories of solid wastes and the proper ways of segregating them, and the penal provisions of the law, they are now given by the MENRO some enough time to comply with other requirements like the provision of five (5) separate, properly labelled and color-coded trash bins, and the display of a tarpaulin indicating the proper segregation of wastes.

Once ready, that means all the rest of the requirements have been satisfied by the business owners, they will now notify the monitoring and inspection team of the

MENRO that their business establishment is now ready for inspection. Upon knowing this notification from the business entity, the records section now prepares the MSWMCC, indicating the date of issuance, place of issuance, date of approval, and date of inspection. Together with the application form the business owner filled out at the onset of this application for compliance certification, the records personnel now submit the MSWMCC to the approving officer, the head of the MENRO. The approving officer now signs the portion of the business owner's application form indicating the recommendation for the monitoring and inspection team to conduct an on-site inspection. Aside from signing the said document, the approving officer also affixes his signature on the MSWMCC in the anticipation that the business entity has successfully complied with the rest of the requirements.

When the MSWMCC is already signed by the approving officer, the monitoring and inspection section of the MENRO now goes to the location of the business entity carrying three documents – the release log book, the inspection checklist, and the MSWMCC. Using the inspection checklist, the onsite inspectors meticulously checks the completeness of the trash bins, the labels, and its colors if all conforms with the standards mandated by RA 9003. They will also see if the proper waste segregation system is printed legibly and displayed at a conspicuous space in the business establishment. If all of these requirements are checked in the inspection checklist, that means the business entity is compliant. With this the MSWMCC will be released to the compliant business firm. The inspectors now instruct the business owner or his authorized representative to sign on the release logbook to document the receipt of the compliance certificate. They will now take photos of the trash bins and the displayed tarpaulin together with the business owner receiving the compliance certificate to document the inspection activity.

In the event that the inspectors find out during their onsite inspection that there are still other requirements that are not met by the business owners, the inspectors (as they are given the authority by the MENRO head to do so) automatically declare the MSWMCC already signed by the approving officer null and void. They will then indicate on the inspection checklist the reason why the compliance certificate was declared null and void and declare the business entity as non-compliant. The conferment of the certification to the business entity is also denied.

However, the inspection team still gives consideration or a chance to the business entity by giving some time to provide the lacking requirements and complete them. The inspection team of the MENRO now waits for the business owner if they are ready for inspection. Once the inspection team receives a notification from the business entity that they are ready for inspection, the process is performed again.

The date of inspection also instills in the minds of the general public, the customers, and even other regulatory bodies that the compliance certification process of the MENRO is not that easy and that it entails an organized, rigorous procedure before the MSWMCC is granted.

On the business owners' end, this figure, with the message it voices out, makes them feel confident that there are some people (the MENRO's inspection team) who can vouch and attest to their compliance. With this, they will not have to worry in cases when other regulatory entities apart from the MENRO visit their establishment and scrutinize the validity and legitimacy of their compliance and the operations of their business. The date of inspection alone can tell them that all of these have already been validated. And if they are still skeptical about the veracity of the compliance of the business entity, they can call the attention of the inspection team of the MENRO, who conducted the onsite inspection, and look into the inspection checklist.

Ninth Figure: The Signatory

The signatory comprises the name of the individual approving the compliance certificate with their signature above it. Figure 10 displays the signatory on the MSWMCC.

Figure 10.
The Signatory on the MSWMCC

The signatory (the name and signature of the approving officer) on the MSWMCC tells the document that it is official, legal, and authentic. The signatory, being placed at a conspicuous area in the compliance certificate, voices the message that the document is official and that it carries the weight of the issuing or approving authority. Bearing the weight of the issuing or approving office suggests that it is backed or supported by their power and influence. When something happens, like somebody questioning the legitimacy of the document, the approving authority is there to defend and support the document's legitimacy. The approving officer is there to vouch for the veracity of the compliance of the business entity.

It convinces anyone who reads the certificate that the document is real to its truest essence, not a fraud nor a forgery. The signatory executes the task of affirming compliance with regulatory standards in solid waste management. The signatory's performance of the task of guaranteeing, proclaiming, and professing the pious satisfaction of all the mandated requirements for solid waste management in business establishments does not only proves the entity's compliance of all the regulatory

requirements but also teaches the business entities to adhere to the mandates of the law, in this case, those of RA 9003.

Tenth Figure: The QR Code

In the MSWMCC, a QR code is also placed at the bottom of the signatory for some significant reasons. Figure 11 shows the QR code on the MSWMC.

Figure 11.
The QR Code on the MSWMCC

A QR code is placed adjacent to the MENRO logo and a text that is enclosed in a box that says:

Digitally signed by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office, (name of the municipality), (Name of the Province). This document is certified official by the MENRO.

Location: (Name of the Municipality) Municipal Sports Center, (Name of Barangay), (Name of the Municipality), (Name of the Province)

Date: (Date when the document was digitally signed)

The objective of including the text above right adjacent to the QR code is to affirm the legality and the officiality of the document. Also, it is one way of telling somebody who comes across the document that the document is genuinely certified true and authentic by the certifying officer of the MENRO, which is the head of the office.

When the QR code is scanned, a certain text appears. Below is the sample text when the QR code is scanned:

Digitally signed by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office, (name of the municipality), (Name of the Province). This document is certified official by the MENRO.

Location: (Name of the Municipality) Municipal Sports Center, (Name of Barangay), (Name of the Municipality), (Name of the Province)

Date: 07-18-2024 | 10:42 PM

July 18, 2024

TO : **NAME OF THE BUSINESS ENTITY**
Address of the Business Establishment

RE : **Issuance of Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate**

Doc. Ref. Code	MENRO-OMENRO-MSMCC-01	Rev.	0
Effectivity	07-18-2024	Page	1 of 1

The QR Code makes permanent the authorization of the certificate as it is kept in a digital folder in the MENRO's computer system. Further, it indicates the easy access to the verification of the authenticity of the certificate. The above information is kept so that when the said data is needed, it would be easy for the records personnel of the office to locate and retrieve it.

The QR code in the MSWMCC is ventriloquized to voice out the concept that the document is indeed official and authentic. It speaks about its provision of direct and verifiable proof of the document's officiality and authenticity.

Likewise, using the voice given to it, the QR code speaks about transparency, which is greatly associated with officiality, legitimacy, and authenticity – as it gives permission to anyone with access to the compliance certificate to independently verify its validity. As a consequence, trust in the compliance certificate is established, ensuring that the document meets the requirements of the regulatory standards and has been issued by a legitimate regulatory body in solid waste management.

The QR code tells that the document has been processed through official channels – from the personnel who prepared the certificate, to the one who checked the compliance of the business entity to the required standards in solid waste management for business organizations, to the approval of the document. As the QR code speaks about itself as an extension of the issuing body's voice that certifies the document's legitimacy, it increases the document's authority.

The QR code becomes an active participant in the communication process, "speaking" on behalf of the certificate to affirm its authenticity and official status. It reinforces the document's credibility through direct interaction, thereby embodying the principles of transparency, trust, and compliance.

Likewise, as the QR code performs its tasks of facilitating the ease of the verification of the MSWMCC's authenticity, it operationalizes the concept of authenticity by enabling real-time verification. When scanned, it provides immediate access to relevant information, such as the issuing authority's records or a certification database, thereby performing the role of an authenticating agent. This process transforms the abstract notion of authenticity into a concrete, actionable reality, facilitated by the QR code's digital interface.

Aside from this act, the QR code is also seen to perform the action of keeping a digital record of the data associated with the document. Through its performance of this event, the QR code ensures that the information remains accessible and verifiable over time. This function aligns with the role of non-human agents in Cooren's framework, where the QR code continuously performs the task of safeguarding the document's history and its associated data, making it available for future verification. This archival role contributes to the document's long-term validity and reliability.

As a figure, the QR code's performance of its tasks of facilitating the ease of the verification process automates and secures the process. This, in turn, reduces the possibility for human error or fraud in the performance of the verification process. The QR code's involvement in this process transforms the MSWMCC into an interactive, verifiable entity, rather than a static piece of paper.

Figure 12 illustrates the figures ventriloquized and animated in the MSWMCC.

Figure 12.
The Figures Ventriloquized and Animated in the MSWMCC

The Performance of the MSWMCC as a Non-Human Agent Teleacting the Authority in the Accomplishment of Solid Waste Management

There are six (6) acts that the certificate performs in accomplishing solid waste management– ***representing the government, regulating business operations in accordance with solid waste management practices, affirming business entity’s compliance, informing the general public of the business entity’s participation in solid waste management, authorizing business operations in consideration with solid waste management, and documenting business entity’s participation in solid waste management.*** Each of these acts is elaborated in the succeeding narrations below. Figure 13 displays the activities or events performed by MSWMCC.

Figure 13.
The Activities or Events Performed by MSWMCC

Representing the Government

The compliance certificate performs the act of representing the Philippine government and its dedication to sustainable development and environmental stewardship. It surpasses its administrative function and serves as a powerful symbol of the government's guiding principles, ideals, and aspirations.

Primarily, the compliance certificate exemplifies the authority of the entire Philippine government. It clearly shows that the government is always firmly committed to enforcing all laws and regulations on proper solid waste management. Making sure that every business establishment follows these legal requirements and takes part in protecting and sustaining the natural environment, this activity of the MSWMCC underlines the vital role of the government as a careful guardian of the environment and public health.

Next, this official compliance certificate demonstrates the provisions set by RA 9003. It strongly highlights the government's legislative work on responsible solid waste management that actively promotes practical steps that reduce harm to the environment, conserve resources, and protect public health. Therefore, this document is clear proof of the government's ongoing dedication to following these mandatory legal requirements.

Additionally, the certificate clearly shows how the government actively protects the clean environment and responsibly supports sustainability. It highlights the government's firm position in addressing environmental problems, saving vital resources, and building a strong culture of responsibility and accountability toward nature. In this way, the certificate becomes a clear symbol of the government's determination to create an ongoing, lasting, and sustainable future for all its citizens and the natural world.

Beyond the government's legal rules and environmental programs, this certificate also demonstrates the government's care, concern, and respect for its people and the natural world. It represents the government's effort to protect the health and well-being of the citizens and to preserve soil, water, air, and resources that sustain life. Because unsafe waste can harm public health and cause diseases, the government makes sure that business entities and communities follow solid waste management practices. In this way, the certificate stands as a real symbol of the government's values and steady promise to build a healthy, fair, and sustainable future for all.

Adding to that, the document shows the government's dream of a nation that is pro-God, pro-people, pro-nature, and pro-country. It states the government's hope for a society that embraces faith, prioritizes citizens' social welfare and overall well-being, cares deeply for their needs, respects the environment, and builds strong, lasting national unity and pride. The certificate thus assumes the role of a symbol representing the government's determination to realize this vision and forge a future where both people and nature thrive in harmonious coexistence.

Generally, the compliance certificate transcends its mere status as a document as it assumes the role of a potent and authoritative non-human agent that encapsulates the Philippine government's unwavering commitment to sustainable development, environmental stewardship, and the well-being of its people. It teleacts the government's authority, legal mandates, environmental initiatives, cherished values, and vision for a brighter future for all.

Regulating Business Operations in Accordance with Solid Waste Management Practices

The compliance certificate issued by the MENRO serves as a non-human agent that performs the act of regulating business operations in the municipality in accordance with solid waste management practices. In its regulation of business activities in the municipality, it carries with it the notion of the municipality's commitment to enforcing sound waste management practices. It also represents the town's vision for a clearer, healthier, and more sustainable future.

The certificate exemplifies the MENRO's belief that business entities should also be held accountable for their solid waste management practices because they are also generators of various kinds of solid waste. With this, the MENRO sees to it that businesses comply with solid waste disposal practices mandated by RA 9003. It is for this reason that the MENRO requires the business establishments to undergo the compliance certification process.

In addition, the certificate acts as a public declaration of a business's commitment to the regulatory standards outlined by the MENRO as mandated by RA 9003. It tells the general public that the business establishment has successfully undergone the certification process, meeting all the regulatory requirements. With this, trust and confidence are established among customers, investors, and stakeholders. As an example, a restaurant displaying the compliance certificate demonstrates its dedication to adhering to the regulatory standards in solid waste management alongside practicing responsible waste disposal, eco-friendly packaging, and efforts to reduce environmental impact. The document also gives assurance to the customers that the food and services they receive are clean, hygienic, and safe.

Securing the compliance certificate is not a one-time achievement, as business entities must maintain continuous compliance and accountability. It reminds the business entities and the general public that environmental responsibility is an incessant journey. Because of this, business establishments are required to consistently adhere to the prescribed standards and practices for solid waste management, ensuring their commitment to environmental responsibility and active contribution to a sustainable future. As an instance, a manufacturing company granted a compliance certificate may be required to submit regular reports on waste generation, recycling rates, and disposal practices to ensure continuous monitoring and accountability.

As it regulates business operations in the municipality, the certificate also promotes various regulated practices in solid waste management, as already conveyed to business owners who participated in the orientation on RA 9003 as part of the compliance certification process. These practices include proper waste segregation, recycling, composting, proper waste disposal, and waste reduction at source. This is to ensure that business agencies operate in a manner that effectively minimizes their environmental impact. In order to reduce the volume of waste sent to disposal facilities and to promote resource recovery, business entities, as part of the regulation, are required to separate the wastes they generate into different categories – biodegradable, recyclable, residual, special, and healthcare wastes.

As part of the compliance process, business owners or their authorized representatives participate in the orientation on RA 9003, where they are encouraged to implement recycling and composting efforts in their respective establishments to minimize waste production and to conserve resources. They are encouraged to establish linkages with local recycling entities and facilities and establish composting

mechanisms. A grocery store, for example, is encouraged to partner with a nearby recycling company to collect plastic bottles and cardboard boxes, diverting these waste materials from disposal facilities and promoting the circular economy.

Also, as part of the regulatory standards, business owners are strongly required to dispose of their solid waste accountably by conforming to the guidelines set by the municipality, through the MENRO, for waste collection and disposal. This makes sure that solid wastes are properly handled and do not pose risks to public health or to the environment.

In addition to these measures, business establishments are encouraged to practice approaches to reduce waste generation, such as the minimization of packaging, using reusable materials, and actively aiming to reduce the volume of waste they produce in their respective jurisdictions. Stores in the municipality are actually motivated to switch to reusable shopping bags, reduce packaging, and promote customers bringing their own bags.

As it regulates operations of business entities in the municipality, the certificate represents the municipality's commitment to responsible solid waste management and transparency by holding business entities accountable for their environmental impact. It also symbolizes a vision for a clearer, healthier, and more sustainable future, where business establishments play a crucial role in proper solid waste management to protect the environment and the well-being of the residents.

Affirming Business Entity's Compliance

As a non-human agent, the compliance certificate performs the act of affirming the business entity's compliance with all the requirements of the regulatory standards in proper solid waste management for business establishments. As it affirms the

business's compliance, it also represents the remarkable outcome of the business entity's efforts to undergo the meticulous compliance process that entails thorough inspections and evaluations conducted by the MENRO. It tells the general public a fact that, when a business organization is granted the certificate, the business has successfully undergone the rigorous assessment to ensure its solid waste management practices align with the legal standards established by the MENRO.

As the certificate affirms the business entities' compliance, it also communicates to the general public that the business has taken concrete steps to conform with the regulatory standards for solid waste management. Actually, all business entities are obliged to implement specific solid waste management processes, such as providing separate trash bins for the various categories of wastes, including biodegradable, recyclable, residual, special, and healthcare wastes. Aside from these bins to be easily accessible, they must be properly labeled and color-coded to facilitate easy and accurate segregation of wastes by both employees and customers. In addition to that, the businesses are required to display an educational material, such as a tarpaulin that informs the general public about the proper segregation of solid wastes and the penalties for violating RA 9003.

Moreover, as it affirms compliance, the certificate goes beyond the initial inspection and satisfaction of all regulatory requirements for solid waste management. This document places ongoing accountability on every business establishment to consistently uphold and strictly enforce proper solid waste management standards over time. It holds companies accountable for their actions, and the certificate acts as a steady reminder that following solid waste management regulations is mandatory. It warns that failing to meet these standards after certification leads to significant legal consequences for non-compliance with the rules under the law.

When a business establishment no longer adheres to regulatory standards, the MENRO has the authority to revoke its certificate. This revocation can result in various sanctions, such as legal action, financial penalties, or suspension of the business's operating license. As an example, if a certified restaurant affirmed of its compliance with solid waste management regulatory standards fails its solid waste segregation obligations by mixing biodegradable with residual wastes or improperly disposing of hazardous waste, its certification would be revoked. The loss of the certification not only destroys the restaurant's reputation but also exposes it to potential penalties and legal repercussions. The general public may also lose their trust and confidence in the establishment, which results in significantly reduced overall customer patronage over time.

The compliance certificate acts as a strong and reliable tool to show that a business follows environmental rules. It gives the public confidence that the business met the necessary standards through careful and thorough assessments, inspections, and detailed paperwork and records. The certificate also holds the business establishment responsible for keeping these standards, and it can face serious legal penalties if it fails. In this way, the certificate builds a culture of openness, responsibility, and care for the environment among businesses. This supports the municipality's goals of sustainability and the health and well-being of the public.

Informing the General Public of the Business Entity's

Participation in Solid Waste Management

The compliance certificate, acting as a non-human agent, is key to clear communication between businesses and the public, as it informs everyone about the business's involvement in solid waste management. Placing this certificate in a visible

spot at the business establishments shows the community that the business firmly commits to proper solid waste management and genuinely dedicates itself to meeting its environmental obligations. This direct form of communication builds trust, supports transparency, and reinforces overall accountability.

When the members of the public see the compliance certificate, they know the business does more than just follow the rules; it practices proper solid waste management practices. This active approach shows that the business cares about reducing the harm its operations can cause to the environment. For example, a retail store displaying this certificate will sort its waste carefully, separating recyclables, organic materials, and hazardous waste. The business then makes sure these different types of waste are properly sent to the right facilities that handle them safely. All of these steps show that the business is not only meeting legal requirements but is also truly dedicated to supporting sustainability efforts.

Also, the compliance certificate stands for a business's real care and concern for the environment. It shows that the company sees how important it is to protect natural resources and will take the steps needed to do this. A certified manufacturing company, for example, uses waste reduction methods like choosing biodegradable packaging materials or using efficient production steps to cut down the total waste it produces. These actions, shown by the certificate, prove that the company cares about more than just profit and is firmly committed to shrinking its ecological footprint. This commitment to the environment connects with customers who are more aware of environmental issues and want to support businesses that focus on sustainability initiatives.

In addition to showing that a business is involved in solid waste management, the certificate plays a key role in motivating the public to follow similar steps. When

people see a nearby business take concrete actions to handle its waste responsibly, they may think about their own waste habits and make changes. For example, if a coffee shop accomplishes this certificate, it might promote using reusable cups and containers, set up easily accessible recycling bins for customers, and offer clear and simple information about why reducing waste matters. These clear efforts, backed by the certificate, not only show the coffee shop's commitment to sustainability but also encourage customers to consider how they can cut down on waste in their everyday lives.

The effect of a business's certified compliance can go beyond its own customers, shaping the wider community and encouraging the use of more sustainable waste practices. This broader influence helps build a shared sense of environmental responsibility. When a school achieves compliance, it might set up a full solid waste management program with recycling bins, composting of organic material, and simple lessons on environmental care. As parents, teachers, and students see the school's efforts, they may feel inspired to use similar waste strategies at home or push for better waste management in their local areas.

At its core, a compliance certificate is more than just a rule to follow; it serves as a tool for supporting and protecting the environment. It tells everyone that a business commits to managing its solid waste in a responsible way. This certificate highlights the company's care for the planet and underlines that protecting the environment is a job we all share, whether we are individuals, companies, or communities. Serving as an example, a business establishment with this certificate can encourage others to use green waste methods. This builds a shared effort toward sustainable waste habits and caring for nature. In the end, it helps grow an awareness

about the environment that aids today's community and those who will live here in the future.

Authorizing Business Operations in Consideration

With Solid Waste Management

As a ventriloquized non-human agent, the compliance certificate formally authorizes the operations of businesses within the municipality in line with solid waste management rules. It confirms the business has met the necessary environmental regulatory standards and is therefore allowed to carry on its commercial activities. Obtaining this certificate grants the business formal permission to proceed, under the condition that it continuously complies with all the solid waste management regulations. It also reminds the business of its ongoing duty to follow all these rules daily.

After a business gets the compliance certificate, it can do more than meet solid waste management rules. It also gains the power to help achieve solid waste management goals. This power lets companies create and carry out plans, ideas, and steps that improve their waste handling work. For example, a factory can use its certificate to start a project inside the business to cut down on waste. It could change how it makes products to create less scrap or set up recycling efforts that include every person who works there. The certificate gives the company the approval it needs so it can come up with fresh ideas and take the lead beyond just following basic rules.

Obtaining the compliance certificate gives business establishments strong protection from legal problems. This document proves that the business has followed environmental rules set by the Municipality and meets the necessary legal requirements. As an example, a restaurant with this certificate can work with peace of

mind because its way of disposing of waste is lawful. It sorts food scraps correctly, handles harmful cleaners safely, and takes part in recycling programs. Doing this, the restaurant avoids legal trouble like fines, penalties, or a shutdown of its license. Beyond this, the certificate acts like a shield, keeping the business inside the legal lines. It also shows that the business cares about protecting the environment. In this wider sense, having the compliance certificate not only protects the company from environmental law violations but also emphasizes its dedication to eco-friendly practices. It shows responsibility to the community and its future generations.

Moreover, the compliance certificate gives the businesses the power to take part in activities that match the town's environmental goals. As an illustration, a store chain with this certificate can work with the local government departments or non-government groups to set up community clean-up days or run educational events about handling waste properly. Because of the certificate, the business establishments can help people about the environment and how to recycle, reuse, and reduce trash. Taking part in these projects shows that the company is serious about caring for the planet. It also improves the business's image as a responsible member of society. At the time, working with neighbors creates trust and goodwill. Customers see the business supporting local causes, which makes them more likely to return and stay loyal. In the end, holding the certificate helps the business grow stronger ties with the community while supporting a cleaner environment.

Also, having the certificate gives companies a competitive edge. Many customers care about environmental issues, and they choose to support business entities that follow proper solid waste management rules. A construction company, for example, with this certificate can promote itself as eco-friendly by using sustainable materials, reducing waste at building sites, and disposing of debris. This proof of

environmental care helps the company stand out. As a result, the certificate becomes an important part of the company's brand, showing customers that it takes sustainability seriously and earns their trust.

The certificate is not just a regulatory requirement. It helps business establishments grow and stay safe. This certificate gives business companies the power to work inside the municipality and makes them promise to focus on handling their solid waste. Successfully getting the certificate not only lets them stay legal but also encourages them to create and use eco-friendly methods. Proving they meet the environmental regulatory standards, businesses can avoid legal risks like fines and penalties. They can then join community efforts, improve their public image, and gain a strong competitive edge in their market. In the end, the certificate stands for a full plan on how to run a business in a way that cares for the environment.

Documenting Business Entity's Participation

In Solid Waste Management

The compliance certificate, being a non-human agent ventriloquized by unseen principals, effectively documents each business entity's participation in solid waste management. As it formally records these efforts, the certificate provides a strong, clear, transparent, public official record that helps reaffirm the company's commitment to environmental sustainability.

Recording the process is carefully detailed, thorough, and complete. The MENRO team not only checks businesses during inspection but also formally keeps records of their compliance for later use. These lasting records are important because they let us confirm that businesses still meet the rules even after the certificate is issued, offering a clear history that can easily be checked at any time it is needed.

When the compliance certificate is issued, it marks the end of a full process that records every part of a business's solid waste management system. This process includes keeping a full record that shows how the business meets all the rules and standards set by the authorities. A business establishment, for example, that gets certified must have clear, written proof that it uses separate bins for different kinds of waste. These include bins for biodegradable materials, recyclable items, ordinary trash, special waste, and healthcare waste. The bins must be correctly labeled and looked after so they stay clean and ready for use. The compliance certificate also confirms that the way the company gets rid of waste follows the required environmental rules. This can cover agreements with licensed waste collection services or joint projects with recycling centers. Issuing the certificate, the authorities ensure that the company's waste disposal work stays up to standards. This gives everyone confidence that the waste is handled in the right way over time. It serves as proof for inspectors that the company follows environmental safety rules consistently.

This set of records is not just paperwork because it is a key tool to make sure that every action can be tracked and traced. If someone needs to check a company's compliance – because of an audit, a court inquiry, or public concern from citizens – the compliance certificate works as solid proof that the company followed all relevant environmental rules. If a question comes up about how the company disposed of its solid waste at any point, this certificate helps verify that it met official requirements at the last inspection. Such traceability is vital for keeping transparency and accountability, since it gives a clear, reliable record of the company's environmental practices over time.

The compliance certificate also carefully records what happened during the on-site inspection, which is a key step to confirm a business is taking part in solid waste

management. In these inspections, the MENRO team goes to the business site to look at how it handles waste. The inspectors follow a detailed list to check that every rule is met. They verify the business has the right number of trash bins, that the bins are labeled correctly, that they are colored according to categories, and that waste is sorted into the correct groups. The checklist can also include checking that the business shows teaching materials, like tarpaulins, that teach workers and customers how to separate their waste properly, safely, and responsibly.

To further confirm that a business follows the rules, the MENRO inspection team takes photos of key details during their visit. This includes pictures of trash bins to show they are used correctly and kept clean, and images of posters or banners that show the business teaches staff and customers about proper solid waste management. These photos add extra proof that the business meets the required standards. Additionally, when the inspector photographs the owner or an authorized representative receiving the compliance certificate, it becomes a formal record of completing the whole compliance process. At the same time, the recipient signs a logbook that tracks all issued certificates, which strengthens the official compliance records. These records help regulators check compliance at any time.

These detailed records are very important as they ensure the compliance certificate is not just a paper but a living proof of the business's ongoing work toward sustainable practices. This documentation shows how committed the business is to taking care of the environment and provides a strong way to be responsible. If the business ever needs to show proof of following the rules or answer questions about its solid waste management practices, the compliance certificate and its related records give a full and checkable history of its efforts to meet environmental standards. This method not only makes the certificate more trustworthy but also helps the

business gain confidence from regulators and the local community it actively supports and partners with local residents.

In this dissertation, the compliance certificate is analyzed as a significant non-human agent in the context of organizational leadership and governance. Through this ventriloquial analysis, it becomes clearer that the certificate means more than just an administrative paper. Driven by unseen principals that represent the authority and intentions of the government, the document performs six (6) distinct functions which include representing the government, regulating business operations in accordance with solid waste management practices, affirming a business entity's compliance, informing the public of a business entity's participation in solid waste management, authorizing business operations, and documenting business entity's participation in solid waste management. Comprehending how the compliance certificate functions as an independent and authoritative agent within the municipal regulatory system is vital.

The idea of non-human agents performing leadership roles is not new and has already been investigated by communication scholars such as Clifton et al. (2021), arguing that artifacts play a crucial role in shaping leadership within organizations. In an educational setting, for example, leaders rely on artifacts such as schedules, role definitions, and meeting agendas to guide and influence instructional practices. Rather than passive instruments, these artifacts are active non-human agents that assist leaders in structuring professional communities, building trust, and promoting collaborative action. Similarly, in the field of solid waste management program implementation, the compliance certificate is considered an artifact used by the MENRO to shape behavior, enforce compliance, and accomplish the organization's environmental goals.

As an artifact, the compliance certificate stands as a unified and complete agency on its own. However, it is intrinsically knotted with the actions and objectives of the regulatory body, the MENRO, which is responsible for its issuance. When the certificate represents the government, it not only serves as a symbol but as a complete representation of the government's authority. As an example, when a business establishment displays the compliance certificate, it effectively displays its endorsement by the municipal government, suggesting that it operates within the legal and environmental framework established by the government. This act of representation is not passive. It actively conveys the presence and influence of the government within the business sector, ensuring the upholding of environmental standards throughout the community.

In the context of business operations, the certificate serves as a regulatory instrument that enforces environmental standards, particularly in proper solid waste management. It functions as a mechanism through which the government's guidelines on solid waste management are put into effect. As an illustration, consider a situation in which a manufacturing plant must obtain a compliance certificate to legally operate. The certificate verifies that the plant's solid waste management practices adhere to the strict requirements outlined in RA 9003, which include proper solid waste segregation, recycling, composting, and proper disposal practices. Associating these proper solid waste management practices through the certificate, the government not only protects the environment but also encourages a sense of accountability and sustainability within the business community.

Adding to that, the compliance certificate stands as official confirmation of a business establishment's compliance with the environmental standards, conveying an authoritative and binding endorsement. This confirmation is important in upholding

public trust and confidence. A hospital, for example, that has been granted the compliance certificate is publicly recognized for adhering to the highest solid waste management standards. This public recognition reassures patients and the community that the hospital is committed to protecting public health and the environment, thereby preserving its reputation and operational legality.

The certificate also helps the public see how a business entity handles its solid waste. Logging and sharing a company's actions, it creates a clear record of its environmental care. A retail chain, to give an illustration, that receives a compliance certificate can display it in ads to show its sustainability goals. This improves its brand image and attracts customers who prefer eco-friendly businesses. Beyond informing people, the certificate encourages other companies to follow the same path, creating a ripple effect that spreads green practices. It also builds broader trust in the local community. This strengthens trust and accountability. Understanding how the certificate works as an independent, authoritative non-human agent in the municipal regulatory system is important and vital.

Furthermore, the compliance certificate gives businesses the legal and full operational approval necessary to run their activities within the jurisdiction of the document. This approval depends on the business continuously following solid waste management rules, which the certificate details and enforces. A food processing factory, for instance, that holds this certificate may carry out its production processes, provided it meets waste handling standards at all times. If the factory fails to comply, authorities can revoke the certificate, and the business will lose its approval to operate. This demonstrates the certificate's role in granting permission for operations while also enforcing adherence to environmental regulations.

The compliance certificate serves many different purposes and has a very important function in the city's solid waste management system. It works as an official record that clearly shows how a business takes part in handling its solid waste. This record keeps detailed inspection notes, lists of compliance steps, and photo proof. Such complete records help make sure everything is open and accountable. When inspectors visit a business site, the MENRO team takes pictures of the solid waste segregation bins and the educational poster. They also note when the business owner accepts the compliance certificate. These files are not just for the sake of documentation. They are key tools for checking ongoing compliance and for proving proper solid waste practices if they are ever challenged by authorities.

In general, the compliance certificate has many roles in the municipal solid waste management system. It helps the government assert authority, regulate business operations, check compliance, inform the public, authorize business activities, and record each business's solid waste management participation. Through these actions, it not only enforces regulatory standards but also influences business decisions and encourages environmental responsibility. The certificate is also essential for the MENRO, ensuring businesses follow solid waste management practices across the municipality and supporting the agency's environmental goals. It creates transparency and accountability, showing both the government and the public that businesses follow the rules.

The Non-Human Agency of MSWMCC

As discussed in the rationale of this dissertation, it is indisputable that our world is filled with artifacts that play an active role in the processes created and designed by humans. Cooren et al. (2006) emphasize the dynamic and symbolic relationship

between humans and these artifacts, emphasizing their influence on the way we perceive, understand, and explore the world. According to Cooren et al. (2006), a comprehensive understanding of the world requires acknowledging the diverse contributions of both human and non-human agencies, as they collectively shape our existence.

Also mentioned in the rationale of this dissertation, the primary objective of this investigation is to illuminate the communicative authority embedded in non-human agents, specifically the MSWMCC, surpassing conventional human-centric perspectives. By exploring the roles these non-human agents play in presentifying someone or something and in conveying directives and influencing behavior, the dissertation aims to clarify their ability to motivate and mobilize business entities toward proactive engagement in effective waste management practices.

As found in this investigation, the MSWMCC is seen as a non-human agent involved in organizational dynamics and accomplishment. As a non-human agent, the MSWMCC has the “ability to act or speak on behalf of someone else, known as the principal” (Cooren, 2011). The compliance certificate is a non-human agent because it has the capacity to “act from a distance or to teleact; teleaction is representation, which is the act of making present or presentifying the principal in communicative practices (Cooren, 2006). The principal that the certificate is “acting or speaking on behalf of” is the Philippine government and its initiatives for environmental protection and sustainability because, as Saludadez (2015) puts it, the term “principal”, in narrative economy, refers to a collective entity such as a group, or organization, or society (Saludadez, 2015). Simply put, the certificate is a non-human agent because it acts or speaks from a distance (teleact or presentify) on behalf of the Philippine government, and it does and speaks about its initiatives for environmental protection

and sustainability by means of proper solid waste management. This relates to the study of Aspøy's (2024), which found that, on behalf of the principals (the tree cutters for economic use), tree species speak about their values and benefits as trees to forest scientists that shape their decision-making practices – which tree to propagate, to transfer, or to cut.

Additionally, as found in the study, the certificate is not just a mere document because it possesses agency for having the capacity to cause change or transformations through a series of activities (Cooren et al., 2006). In the certificate's causing of changes or transformations involving a series of actions, it compels business owners to learn about the mandates of RA 9003, provide five (5) separate, properly labelled and color-coded trash bins, display educational material on proper solid waste segregation, and perform ecologically sound practices in solid waste management. These are a series of actions that manifest business owners' participation in solid waste, a distinct transformation in business owners and in their establishments, caused by the certificate as a non-human agent. Taupin's (2019) study bears a relationship with this present investigation in the sense that both focused on the non-human agents' ability to bring change and transformations, as it found that oceans (the Atlantic Ocean) have the capacity to change the institutional planning and surfing practices in a seaside town in the southwest of France.

The changes or transformations in business owners and in their establishments lead to the accomplishment of proper solid waste management in the municipality, propelled by the certificate, demonstrating that non-human agents, as Cooren (2006) described in his non-human agency framework, participate in communicative practices that drive organizational dynamics and contribute to organizational accomplishment. This bears a connection with what Saludadez (2021) found in her paper that digital

media play a vital role in accomplishing educational goals of individual courses through teacher-student interactions in the University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna.

The MSWMCC as a Textual Agent

One of the agencies that fills the world we live in exists in the form of textual documents. That means that everything written on paper exhibits textual agency. The MSWMCC is a written document that also possesses textual agency because it plays a crucial role in shaping organizational structures (Cooren, 2008). As a textual agent, the compliance certificate leads in the molding of the organizational structures of the regulatory bodies in solid waste management. At the municipal level, the personnel of the MENRO assigned to different divisions and sections define and perform their roles in the compliance certification process, as needed in the issuance of the certificate.

In like manner, the certificate, being a textual agent, performs actions, as textual agents do, that may be categorized into “assertives, commissives, and directives” (Cooren, 2008). As found in this investigation, the certificate is seen to perform six (6) acts - ***representing the government, regulating business operations in accordance with solid waste management practices, affirming business entity’s compliance, informing the general public of the business entity’s participation in solid waste management, authorizing business operations in consideration with solid waste management, and documenting business entity’s participation in solid waste management.*** All these acts can be distinguished according to Cooren’s (2008) categorization of acts performed by textual agents.

Employing the category of assertives proposed by Searle (1979) and Vanderveken (1990), the certificate performs the acts of informing, indicating, saying,

telling, asserting, attesting, certifying, and proclaiming. Specifically, a textual agent, the certificate performs the acts of ***informing the general public of the business entity's participation in solid waste management, and affirming business entity's compliance, and documenting business entity's participation in solid waste management*** (as documenting aims to keep the document for future assertive activities).

Furthermore, the certificate possesses a unique power to create an intangible impact as it performs commissive actions like swearing, accepting, or agreeing (Cooren, 2008). As the certificate performs the action of ***representing the government***, it commits to the entity it is representing to speak about it and its goals on its behalf. Also, the certificate agrees to and accepts the tasks of voicing about environmental protection and sustainability through solid waste management and of performing acts to achieve these goals.

As a textual agent, additionally, the certificate also performs directive acts like demanding, exerting pressure, commanding, instructing, prohibiting, permitting, authorizing, and allowing (Cooren, 2008). When the certificate performs the act of ***regulating business operations in accordance with solid waste management practices***, it also executes its role as a textual agent of demanding, commanding, and exerting pressure on business owners to comply with all the mandated requirements for certification.

The certificate's ability to perform directive acts by permitting and authorizing is demonstrated in its execution of its task of ***authorizing business operations in consideration of solid waste management***. In short, the certificate completes its commissive acts by granting the business owners the legal rights to engage in business activities.

The same performance of textual agency's assertive, commissive, and directive tasks was also demonstrated by peace process documents, as textual agents, in Isla's (2024) study on the authority of peace process documents as non-human agents. In this study of Isla's (2024), the peace process documents exerted its authority in its ability to guarantee the execution of those stated stipulations. This authority resulted from the peace process documents' execution of directive, commissive, and assertive acts.

Just like Isla's (2024) study, this present investigation contributes to the body of communication knowledge that textual agents, indeed, have the power to assert, to facilitate commitment, and to direct in order to accomplish organizational goals and objectives.

As found in the analysis of this study, the MENRO personnel are animated or acted upon by the National Motto (Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan, Makabansa), pushing them to ventriloquize the certificate to speak of or do something (figures) in solid waste management. In this case, the MENRO personnel act as both ventriloquists and dummies; ventriloquists because they give voice to the certificate, and dummies because they are acted upon by vents.

Performing the ventriloquial analysis necessitates the identification of figures that are **implicitly** or **explicitly** invoked and made to say things by people, and on the other hand, the vents that lead people to say what they say and act how they act. As said, figures can be invoked **explicitly or implicitly**. An explicit invocation means that the utterance directly mentions the figure (literally: ex-plied, unfolded, open) while an implicit invocation means the utterance indirectly mentions the figure (literally: im-plied, wrapped up, hidden). In this case, the certificate is ventriloquized by the people who crafted, approved, and released it – the personnel of the MENRO, who are acted upon

by vents or animations (unseen principals) which is the National Motto (Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan, Makabansa). With its being ventriloquized, the certificate was found to incarnate various explicit and implicit figures discussed in the results section of this chapter.

As this study was anchored on the Montreal School of Organizational Communication, which theorizes Communication as Constitutive of Organization (CCO) (Saludadez, 2021), or organization and communication are seen as equivalent, communication is not just a tool used within an organization but is actually what shapes and defines the organization itself. In other words, the organization is seen as something that emerges from communication, and the organizational structure is a configuration of agents (Saludadez, 2021). The organization of the MENRO, being a local government regulatory body in solid waste management, arises from the communicative practices actively participated in by the office's personnel and non-human agents, like the compliance certificate.

The CCO is greatly intertwined with Cooren's (2016) ventriloquism, which is the main research methodology utilized in this present study, as Cooren's (2021) ventriloquial analysis approach answers the question of how voices enter interactions. Cooren's (2016) ventriloquialism relates to this concept of CCO by exploring how different voices (or perspectives) or ventriloquized agents (agents that are given voices) enter into interactions within an organization. Ventriloquism seeks to understand not only what these voices are saying and how they shape realities within the organization, but also how these voices interact and influence each other in communicative practices that form an organization. In the context of this present investigation, the figures and vents that surfaced in the ventriloquial analysis of the certificate, enter into and participate in the communicative interactions of an

organization, the MENRO, that eventually shape realities within and define and form the organization.

In addition, written issuances such as the compliance certificate, acting as a textual agent performs tasks (assertives, commissives, and directives) that lead to the accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives. In the ambit of this dissertation, the compliance certificate contributes to the accomplishment of the national vision through proper solid waste management.

CHAPTER VI
RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS,
AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This dissertation on the ventriloquial analysis of the compliance certificate within Cooren's (2006) non-human agency framework under the overarching concept of the CCO of the Montreal School of Organization contributes to our knowledge in communication in its ability to demonstrate that the Non-human Agency Framework of Cooren (2006) is able to surface an often-neglected reality in organizational communication which is the ability of the non-human agents to contribute to the emergence, shaping, and defining of organizations.

Summary

This study examined a compliance certificate issued by a government regulatory body in solid waste management, the MENRO. It sought to answer the research questions: 1) what figures appeared in the solid waste management compliance certificate that ventriloquized its authority; 2) what does the compliance certificate perform in solid waste management?

This study is anchored on the Non-Human Agency Framework advanced by Francois Cooren (2006), which attempts to explain 'how one can act from a distance' or 'teleact' or the act of making present or presentifying something or someone in communicative practices. Teleaction can happen in a manner that non-humans represent other entities. Using Cooren's (2010) Ventriloquial Analysis Approach, this study analyzed the Municipal MSWMCC, a document issued by the MENRO, a local government regulatory body in solid waste management in a municipality. From the

analysis, it was revealed that there is a total of ten (10) figures explicitly invoked in the certificate – 1) official logo, 2) letterhead, 3) certificate number, 4) RA 9003, 5) declaration of compliance, 6) date of issuance, 7) place of issuance, 8) date of inspection, 9) signatory, and 10) QR code. Also found in the analysis are six (6) acts that the compliance certificate performs in accomplishing solid waste management – 1) representing the government, 2) regulating business operations in accordance with solid waste management practices, 3) affirming business entity's compliance, 4) informing the general public of the business entity's participation in solid waste management, 5) authorizing business operations in consideration with solid waste management, and 6) documenting business entity's participation in solid waste management. As a textual agent, the MSWMCC performs assertive, commissive, and directive acts.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, the researcher advances the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority Theory, which posits that non-human agents possess ventriloquized and animated authority. This means that non-human actors, especially those that are incarnated in the issuances from regulatory bodies participating in communicative praxis, possess power and influence from their being ventriloquized and animated. By ventriloquized we mean being given voices by the entity they are representing to speak about something or someone. In addition, by being animated we mean the non-human agents are being pushed or compelled to act or do something by the entity they are representing.

Ventriloquized-Animated Authority is that kind of authority that the non-human agents derive from their being ventriloquized (given voices to speak) and animated

(acted upon to act) by some higher unseen principals. The voices given to non-human agents by more powerful unseen principals grant them the strength and the power to speak about influential messages that move human agents to act. Likewise, the force of persuasion exerted on the non-human agents by a more powerful unseen principal also pushes the human actors to perform something geared toward the accomplishment of organizational goals.

Moreover, these non-human agents are compelled to act and do things because of the influence of the National Motto - Maka-Diyos, Makatao, Makakalikasan, and Makabansa. Animated by the extensive influence of the National Motto, the non-human agents are very much capable of doing some authoritative actions – affirm, direct, require, admonish, motivate, deny, and even punish.

In the ambit of this dissertation, the MSWMCC possesses ventriloquized- animated authority. This means that figures present in the compliance certificate carry a ventriloquized- animated authority because of their ability to speak up about the legal provisions and stipulations of RA 9003 they are representing, which is the National Motto, an entity with authority and power considerably higher than the non-human agents. With the influence of the National Motto, non-human agents speak with power, force, and might, making them authoritative, too.

When business firms fail to comply with regulatory standards articulated by the figures in the compliance certificate, they will face legal repercussions, including denial of certificate conferment, imposition of monetary penalties, suspension of operations, and even closure. All these are voiced and performed by the non-human agents through the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority they gained from their powerful unseen principal, the National Motto.

With this, it is the Ventriloquized-Animated Authority possessed by the MSWMCC that compels business establishments in a municipality to comply with regulatory standards and requirements set by the MENRO, granting them the legal authority to operate their businesses.

Thus, as a textual agent, the compliance certificate possesses this authority that compels business entities to participate in solid waste management, contributing to the accomplishment of organizational goals and the national vision. With this, this study contributes this concept that non-human agents, like the compliance certificate which is a textual agent, really exert influences on and contribute to organizational dynamics and accomplishment as they participate in various communicative practices that shape and define organizations, as emphasized by the concept of CCO (Communication as Constitutive of Organization) under the Montreal School of Organizational Communication.

Implications

The results of this dissertation have several implications. These include offering a deeper understanding of the regulatory mechanism, significantly impacting policy and enforcement, improving compliance strategies, and providing legal and organizational insights. Additionally, it offers a framework for future research, practical applications in environmental management, and broader implications for regulatory effectiveness.

In identifying the figures invoked in the MSWMCC, this study reveals who and what the MENRO uses to enforce proper solid waste rules as outlined in the compliance certificate. It clearly maps how human and non-human entities work together to enforce these laws. This detailed mapping deepens our understanding of

the intricate regulatory frameworks and reveals the diverse methods and strategies through which compliance is consistently achieved.

Through the explicit demonstration of how vital non-human agents are for embodying and enforcing RA 9003, this study's findings could significantly guide policy-makers to thoroughly assess these agents' effectiveness when making new regulations or updating current existing ones. Identifying the different roles non-human agents fulfill effectively can lead to more targeted and efficient regulatory strategies, which could result in higher compliance rates across waste management programs.

Additionally, the actions these agents take – representing, asserting/informing/affirming, directing/requiring/regulating, authorizing, and documenting – show how compliance is enforced. Regulatory bodies and agencies can use this knowledge to improve how they communicate, enforce rules effectively and quickly, making sure their instructions are clear and possess strong authority and emotional impact to make people follow them.

Understanding that non-human agents gain their authority through their representation of the Philippine government and its environmental protection and sustainability initiatives provides legal scholars and organizational communication theorists with significant insights and guidance. It emphasizes how legal principles should be integrated into organizational practices at every level and how non-human agents can serve as effective proxies for legal authority in diverse regulatory environments.

Utilizing Cooren's (2018) Ventriloquial Analysis Methodological Framework, this study offers a methodological framework that future research can apply to examine other regulatory documents and contexts. This methodological contribution benefits scholars who want to investigate non-human agents' roles in various

regulatory and organizational settings, giving them a clear instrument to guide their analysis.

In the field of environmental management, environmental managers can use these findings for practical advice on using non-human agents to enforce environmental rules. Knowing what each agent does and how they act, professionals can create and run compliance programs that show why following environmental laws matters, ensuring everyone understands their role in protecting the environment.

Finally, the study's focus on how non-human agents hold power and work well to enforce rules shows that they could improve regulation in many fields. This points to using similar methods in other public policy and regulations to strengthen overall governance and enforcement systems, making laws clearer and more effective across sectors.

Recommendations

This study carefully showed and examined results that explain how non-human agents, through a regulatory body's directive, hold authority in solid waste management. This paper emphasizes how these agents drive compliance and shape practices in this area. Noting the urgent need for more research and theory in communication studies, the researcher offers a set of recommendations to deepen knowledge and academic work on this topic. These suggestions seek to build greater understanding of how authority works and how communication functions within regulation. Following these recommendations, future studies can uncover the processes of authority and detailed communication in regulatory systems.

Theoretical

Future researchers and scholars interested in non-human agents' authority can study complex relationships by using Actor-Network Theory (ANT) together with Speech Act Analysis as matching methods. Combining these two frameworks, scholars can fully understand how non-human agents use power and influence across different and emerging contexts. This integrated approach offers a detailed view of the roles and impacts of these agents.

J.L. Austin, an Oxford philosopher, first formally introduced Speech Act Analysis as a branch of pragmatics to study how words perform actions and share information in ongoing communication research. American philosopher Jon Searle originally proposed the theory, and Austin expanded it in his book *"How to Do Things with Words."* Later on, Genova (1972) developed this concept into three distinct main acts: perlocutionary, illocutionary, and locutionary.

Locutionary acts describe what is happening in the world. They explain how speech works clearly. Illocutionary acts happen when we promise to do something, while assertive acts also state facts. Examples include giving instructions (directive), making announcements (declaratory), and making promises (commissive). Perlocutionary acts focus on how our words change or influence our listeners. These acts cover things like sharing opinions or giving someone information.

Using Speech Act Analysis, scholars can study how language's performative quality works. They can see how words do more than convey meaning and actually carry out actions. With this approach, researchers examine how users interact with non-human agents to investigate the agents' authority. They classify each utterance into locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary acts. This lets them track how non-human agents direct behaviors, assert influence, and affect listeners. The study sheds

light on the way non-human agents employ language and communication to exercise authority. It helps clarify how these speech patterns reveal power structures and control in those interactions and contexts.

Still, Latour's (1980) Actor Network Theory (ANT) is a framework first introduced in Science and Technology Studies (STS) in the early 1980s. It was created by French sociologist Bruno Latour with Michel Callon, and John Law. ANT offers a distinctive viewpoint on understanding social processes and remains widely used today (Wiltshire, 2020).

The ANT (Latour, 1980) says that everything in nature and society is part of dynamic networks of interactions. Nothing exists outside these links. It clearly shows the connections between human and non-human agents. These agents build networks that constantly shape situations and guide actions. Unlike approaches that focus only on technology or only on society, ANT treats both as truly equally important. In ANT, actants refer to all elements in these networks, and actors are simply groups of these elements working together. The concept of translation fully describes how power struggles change ideas as they move through the network (Wiltshire, 2020).

Since its inception, ANT has been applied in a number of disciplines, including organizational analysis, informatics, health studies, geography, sociology, anthropology, feminist studies, technical communication, and economics (Wiltshire, 2020). Originally, ANT was developed to understand innovation and knowledge creation in science and technology.

The ANT (Latour, 1980) is a simple instrument for looking at the complex web of links that show how non-human agents hold power. According to the ANT, everything belongs to connected networks of actions, and both people and non-human elements can shape the results. Researchers can draw out the network of members

– both human and non-human – and look at how these actors work together to influence power hierarchies by using the ANT in their studies. Studying power links, the changes that ideas go through, and team efforts inside these networks, scientists can really deeply, clearly, and truly uncover how non-human agents gain and keep their authority over time.

Combining ANT and Speech Act Analysis, future researchers can carefully and fully explore how non-human agents hold authority and reveal the nuances of their effects and interactions in complex systems. This cross-disciplinary method deepens our detailed understanding of how non-human agents systematically operate in social, technical, and organizational settings. It also provides valuable, clear, practical insights to guide further studies in this field.

Practical

The researcher proposes making the MSWMCC easily accessible online so that business entities can apply for and manage their certificate more conveniently by incorporating a feature on it in the municipal website. This can also include an online verification system for customers and other regulatory entities to check if a business is certified.

Information, education, and communication campaigns, trainings, and seminars may be conducted to educate both the business owners (and their employees) and the customers about the value and importance of the compliance certificate. It is significant that everyone understands how this certification contributes to a cleaner environment and why it matters for our community.

A community campaign may be organized to encourage people to support only those business establishments that have been granted the compliance certificate.

Through this, the customers can play a role in promoting proper solid waste management practices by choosing to patronize certified business entities.

Businesses may be required to display their compliance certificates in a visible spot, such as near other permits and licenses in their respective establishments. This not only demonstrates their commitment to proper solid waste management but also reassures the customers that they are supporting responsible businesses.

The MENRO team should conduct regular field monitoring and inspections to ensure that businesses are indeed displaying their compliance certificates as required and are consistently practicing proper solid waste management. This will help maintain high standards and encourage continuous compliance with the regulatory framework for proper solid waste management.

Finally, it is vital to conduct future research involving those compliant business owners to assess their level of implementation of the proper solid waste management practices they pledged to consistently and continuously execute during the certification process. Future research may also be conducted to assess how effective regulatory issuances, aside from the compliance certificate, in influencing human behavior and in compelling to act. Understanding what effectively works and what does not will help refine our strategies and ensure that we are making a real impact in the shaping of organizations and in accomplishing organizational goals and objectives.

The researcher believes that these recommendations can help create a more environmentally conscious community and ensure that everyone plays their respective parts in maintaining a healthy and sustainable environment.

Epilogue

What have you truly learned?

On the morning of September 9, 2024, as I sat before the panel for the defense of my doctoral dissertation at the University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna, one question stood out – posed by one of my panel members, Dr. Emely M. Amoloza – *what have you truly learned from the analysis of your study?*

As a teacher, an environmental management practitioner, and a communication scholar, this question resonated deeply with me. It led me to a profound realization – communication’s ultimate purpose is to inspire people to action, to move them towards achieving meaningful goals. It is not just about sharing information but about compelling others to act in ways that matter most.

In my journey, I have come to understand that every word I speak, every message I convey, must always be intentional, almost like *figures* in a ventriloquist’s performance, each carefully chosen to voice something significant and to drive purposeful actions. But I have also learned that I am not alone in this. Surrounding me are countless non-human entities – ideas, symbols, plants, animals, technologies – ready to join me in my every communicative endeavor, amplifying my voice and shaping the outcomes in ways I might not always take notice of.

This awareness has taught me to be mindful, to handle these figures and entities with extra care, knowing that they possess the power to influence understanding and action. Because, at its core, communication is more so about understanding and being understood. We do not listen just to respond; we listen to understand. We speak not just to be heard, but to be truly comprehended.

Besides, when communication is effective, when understanding is achieved, there is harmony, love, and care. Understanding leaves no room for chaos, destruction, and even bloodshed and death. It builds a world where people are driven to act with utmost compassion, sharing our shared space a paradise on Earth.

In my dissertation, I found that François Cooren's concept rings factual – the world is indeed filled with a plethora of entities that shape our existence. And with this understanding, I am more committed than ever to using communication as a force for good, to shape a world where understanding leads to positive actions, and where our collective efforts make the world a better place to live in.

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APPENDIX A

Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Samar
Municipality of
**MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENT
AND NATURAL RESOURCES OFFICE**

09761035051
menro. samar@gmail.com
@menro
https:// .ph

MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT COMPLIANCE CERTIFICATE

Issued Pursuant to RA 9003

Certificate No. : **MSWMCC-RO8-SMS-01012022-0001**

This is to certify that

Name of Business Establishment

located at

Address

owned and managed by

Name of Proprietor

is hereby granted this Municipal Solid Waste Management Compliance Certificate (MSWMCC) by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) after having complied with all the requirements for proper ecological solid waste management mandated under Chapter 3, Article 2, Section 21 & 22 of RA 9003 otherwise known as the Solid Waste Management Act of 2000.

Issued this ___ day of _____ at the Municipality of _____, Samar, Philippines.

The MSWMCC is issued pursuant to Republic Act 9003 otherwise known as the "Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. Non-compliance with the mandated requirements demanded for proper solid waste management shall be sufficient cause for cancellation or non-issuance of this certificate. Business permits (new or renewal) are only granted upon presenting or acquiring this certificate. No business application shall be approved without this certification.

MICHAEL JUDE T. CASALJAY, LPT, MAEd
Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Officer

Date of Inspection : January 18, 2024
Date of Approval : January 18, 2024
Date of Release : January 18, 2024

Digitally signed by the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office, Samar. This document is certified official by the MENR Office.
Location: Municipal Sports Center, Samar
Date: 07-05-2024 | 3:07 PM

MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES OFFICE (MENRO)
GF, Municipal Evacuation Center, National Highway
, 6709 Samar
Eastern Visayas, Philippines